

CEPE 2025

*Rome University Tor Vergata
24-26 September*

Computer Ethics: Philosophical Enquiries

*Artificial Intelligence:
Normative Implications and Philosophical Challenges*

Book of Abstracts

Chairs & Editors:

Antonio Marturano *INSEIT and University of Rome Tor Vergata*

Marco Innamorati *University of Rome Tor Vergata*

Computer Ethics: Philosophical Enquiries (CEPE) is a INSEIT conference series. The CEPE conference series is recognized as one of the premier international events on computer and information ethics attended by delegates from all over the world. CEPE is held biennially. Conferences are held about every 24 months, alternating between Europe and the United States.

The CEPE 2025 Conference is held at the *University of Rome, Tor Vergata*; Department of History, Cultural Heritage, Education and Society from September, 24th to 26th, 2025, in collaboration with the *Ionian University Research Team*, IHRC (Information: History, Regulation and Culture) and *The University for Peace UNO* Rome branch.

CEPE 2025 - Main theme

Artificial Intelligence: Normative Implications and Philosophical Challenges

We have invited submissions for the CEPE 2025 Conference. The main theme will be on “Artificial Intelligence: Normative Implications and Philosophical Challenges”. As AI continues to pervade various aspects of human life, from healthcare to governance, it brings forth a plethora of normative questions and philosophical dilemmas that demand rigorous examination and reflection.

Artificial intelligence technologies raise profound ethical, legal, and social questions that intersect with fundamental philosophical inquiries. The CEPE 2025 Conference aims to explore the normative implications of AI development and deployment, as well as the philosophical challenges it poses to our understanding of freedom, agency, responsibility, autonomy, and society.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to:

1. Ethical considerations in AI design, development, and deployment
2. Algorithmic bias and fairness in AI systems
3. Gender bias in designing AI systems
4. Privacy and data protection in the age of AI
5. Legal and regulatory frameworks for AI governance
6. Human rights and AI ethics
7. AI and the future of work
8. Autonomous systems and moral decision-making
9. Philosophical foundations of AI ethics
10. The nature of consciousness and AI
11. AI and the concept of personhood
12. Social implications of AI based technologies
13. Human interaction with Intelligent embodied systems
14. Leadership and governance of AI
15. History of philosophical debates on AI
16. AI in military and warfare
17. Cyberharrassment and cyberbullism
18. Democracy and political implications of AI use
19. Information access and search engines and other related topics.
20. AI in science fiction
21. Use of AI in education: ethical and philosophical problems
22. Learning: philosophical problems
23. Other topics related to risk: cybersecurity, internet studies, cryptocurrencies, green transition and the Internet of Things.
24. AI and Copyright
25. AI and cultural heritage ethics

We have welcomed submissions from scholars working in philosophy, ethics, law, computer science, social science, psychology, history, education and related disciplines. Both theoretical and empirical contributions are encouraged.

The CEPE 2025 Book of Abstracts has been made possible with the support of Eni Spa

Cepe 2025
Computer Ethics: Philosophical Enquiries

Provisional Conference schedule

Day 1 - September 24th

<i>Time</i>	<i>Activity</i>
9,30-12,45	<i>Pre-conference Doctoral symposium</i> (in Italian for PhD students) Le sfide dell'IA Institutional Welcome: D, Orecchia (Univ. di Roma Tor Vergata)
	<i>Roundtable</i> Chair: A. Marturano (Univ. Di Roma Tor Vergata)
9,30-11,45	<i>Aspetti giuridici ed etici della IA</i> – Andrea Rossetti; <i>LLMs: loro applicazione nell'industria editoriale</i> – Nicola Mastidoro; <i>L'impatto dell'IA nel mondo del lavoro, della cultura e della educazione</i> – Sergio Bellucci.
11,45-12,00	<i>Coffee Break</i>
12,00-12,45	Chair: P. Terracciano (Univ. Di Roma Tor Vergata) <i>Geopolitica dell'Intelligenza Artificiale</i> - Alessandro Aresu
12,00-14,00	<i>Registration</i>
12,45-13,40	<i>Institutional welcomes</i>
12,45-12,55	Tor Vergata Rector (or delegate)
	Other Authorities:
13,00-13,30	Department – TBA; UPEACE – S. Bellucci; INSEIT – K. Miller; AICA – S. Garro; SIFM – F. Magni; Eni – TBA; Ionian University Team – M. Botti
13,30-13,40	Conference organizers address
13,40-14,40	<i>Parallel sessions Round 1</i>
	<i>Special Session INSEIT Fellows</i> <i>Session 2</i> <i>Session 3</i>
	<i>Chair: K. Miller</i> <i>Chair: C. Cappa</i> <i>Chair: H. Bergier</i> (INSEIT President) (U. Roma Torvergata) (Regis University)
13,40-14,00	Mazi Felici & Lavazza Welch & Bednar
14,20-14,40	Kostantis & Faras Sacan Zatini
14,40-15,00	Bottis Viola Brandner & Krampe
15,00-15,45	<i>Plenary Session</i> <i>Keynote Speaker 1 - Derrick De Kerckhove</i>
15,50-16,30	<i>Parallel sessions Round 2</i>
	<i>Session 4</i> <i>Session 5</i> <i>Session 6</i>
	<i>Chair: A. Rossetti</i> <i>Chair: E. Spence</i> <i>Chair: S. Miller</i> (Uni Milan Bicocca) (Univ. of Sydney) (Charles Sturt University)
15,50-16,10	Brey Kitsos, Pappa & Alexandropoulou Koga
16,10-16,30	Popotas Gabriels & Miranovic Fantino
16,30-16,50	Howdle Hauer Korolieva
16,50-17,10	Casanovas De Vroomen Mitra
17,10-17,40	<i>Coffee break</i>
	<i>Workshop</i>
17,40-18,25	<i>Past and future of Artificial Intelligence: roads to freedom, roads to dystopia</i> <i>F. Grodzinsky, G. Roncaglia</i> (chair)
18,30-19,30	<i>Parallel sessions Round 3</i>
	<i>Session 7</i> <i>Session 8</i> <i>Session 9</i>
	<i>Chair: I. Lipinska</i> <i>Chair: C. Welch</i> <i>Chair: R. Foschi</i> (Poznan University) (Univ. of Portsmouth) (U. Roma Sapienza)
18,30-18,50	De Zwart Conklin & La Rosa Katsenou
18,50-19,10	Brosnahan Marinopoulou & Chorianopoulou Innamorati
19,10-19,30	Iglezakis Lorenzi Bouchagiar, G.
19,30-21,30	Welcome Aperitif @ University Hall

Day 2 - September 25th

<i>Time</i>	<i>Activity</i>		
9-10,30	<i>Parallel sessions Round 4</i>		
	<i>Session 1</i>	<i>Session 2</i>	<i>Session 3</i>
	<i>Chair: C. Lorenzi</i> (Univ. Rome Tor Vergata)	<i>Chair: K. Gabriels</i> (Maastricht University)	<i>Chair: A. Elder</i> (Univ. Minnesota Duluth)
9-9,20	Chaleplioglou, Koulouris & Vraimaki	Bouchagiar, A.	Catena
9,20-9,40	Nefeli-Vidaki & Petratza	Froeberg	Mitselou
9,40-10	Corona	Despotidou & Dogouli	Placani
10-10,20	Loh	Shimizu	Barresi
10,20-10,40	Naeem	Kumar	Spear
10,40-11.10	<i>Coffee break</i>		
11,10-12,00	<i>Parallel sessions Round 5</i>		
	<i>Session 4</i>	<i>Session 5</i>	<i>Session 6</i>
	<i>Chair: M. Bottis</i> (Ionian University)	<i>Chair: S. Conklin</i> (Washington University)	<i>Chair: P. Brey</i> (University of Twente)
11,10-11,30	Papadouli	Lipinska & Krzanowski	Rigou
11,30-11,50	Branford	Liu & Liu	K. Miller, Grodzinsky & Wolf
11,50-12,10	Papadopoulou	Hadiya	Dolcini
12,15-13,00	<i>Plenary Session</i>		
	<i>Keynote Speaker 2 – Mario De Caro</i>		
13,00-15,00	<i>Lunch Break</i>		
15,00-16,10	<i>Parallel sessions Round 6</i>		
	<i>Session 7</i>	<i>Session 8</i>	<i>Session 9</i>
	<i>Chair: M. Innamorati</i> (U. Roma Tor Vergata)	<i>Chair: J. Branford</i> (University of Hamburg)	<i>Chair: S. Bauzon</i> (U. Roma Tor Vergata)
15,00-15,20	Spence	Rautenberg	S. Miller
15,20-15,40	Woodley	Koga	Pachou-Fokiari & Billiri
15,40-16,20	Petrocchi	Kampman Walther	Volpini
16,20-16,40	Bergier	Carnevale & Nino	Pisano
16,40-17,00	Marturano		Chantavaridou & Kapidakis
17,00-17,30	<i>Coffee Break</i>		
17,30-18,15	<i>Plenary session</i> TBA		
	<i>Chair: D. Pulcini (Univ. of Rome Sapienza)</i>		
18,20-19,00	<i>Parallel sessions Round 7</i>		
	<i>Session 10</i>	<i>Session 11</i>	<i>Session 12</i>
	<i>Chair: Chair S. Tassis</i> (PotamitisVekris Law Firm)	<i>Chair: F. Magni</i> (Univ. of Pavia)	<i>Chair: K. Shimizu</i> (Meiji University Tokyo)
18,20-18,40	Soulier	Balistreri	Elder
18,40-19,00	Cecchine & Gurtler	Kagioglou	Krzanowski
19,00-22,00	<i>Social Dinner @ Tenuta di Pietra Porzia</i>		

Day 3 - September 26th

<i>Time</i>	<i>Activity</i>		
9,30-10,30	<i>Parallel sessions Round 8</i>		
	<i>Session 1</i>	<i>Session 2</i>	<i>Session 3</i>
	<i>Chair: A. Spear</i>	<i>Chair: R. Krzanowski</i>	<i>Chair: G. Salmeri</i>
	<i>(Grand Valley State University)</i>	<i>(Pont. Univ. John Paul II Krakow)</i>	<i>(U. Roma Torvergata)</i>
9,30-9,50	Schultz	D. Miller	Marceau & Lacroix
9,50-10,10	Morelli	Titz & Lundgren	Kruse
10,10-10,30	Hauser	Dimitriou	Papandritsa
10,30-11,00	<i>Coffee Break</i>		
11,00-12,30	<i>Plenary sessions</i>		
	<i>Keynote Speaker 3</i>		
11,00- 11,45	<i>Joseph Weizenbaum Award Speech</i>		
	Frances Grodzinsky		
11,45-12,30	<i>Conference Organizers Final comments</i>		
	A. Marturano, M. Innamorati, K. Miller		

Keynote Speakers

Mario De Caro

is a professor of Moral Philosophy at Roma Tre University, and regularly a visiting professor at Tufts University. He has been a Fulbright Fellow at Harvard, a Visiting Scholar at MIT, and president of the Italian Society for Analytic Philosophy. He is the president of the Italian Society of Moral Philosophy, a member of the executive board of the International Federation of Philosophical Societies, the literary executor of Hilary Putnam and member of the Italian Association of Philosophy executive board. He has given talks at more than one hundred universities in seventeen countries and has written seven books in Italian and edited twenty volumes. He is associate editor of *The Journal of the American Philosophical Association*, writes for *Il Sole 24 Ore* and *La Stampa*, and is a consultant for ENEL on the ethics of artificial intelligence. His areas of expertise include moral philosophy, metaphysics, ethics of AI, philosophy of mind, philosophy of film, and the history of early modern philosophy.

Derrick De Kerckhove

is the author of world renowned books *The Skin of Culture* and *Connected Intelligence* and Professor in the Department of French at the University of Toronto, in Toronto, Ontario, Canada. He was the Director of the McLuhan Program in Culture and Technology from 1983 until 2008. One of the world's leading scholars on the social phenomena of the Web, after studying with Marshall McLuhan, Derrick De Kerckhove undertook in-depth research on the media's ability to influence human perceptual reality, starting from the assumption that mass media are actually definable as psychotechnologies. He also elaborated the concepts of web hyperpertinence, in relation to the degree of relevance that specific connections establish with the content they convey, and webnness, or a specific cognitive dimension, a real form of connective intelligence constituted by users connected to the Internet.

Fran Grodzinsky

is the recipient of International Society for Ethics and Information Technology (INSEIT)/Joseph Weizenbaum Award in Information and Computer Ethics. This prestigious award is delivered every two years to an individual who has made significant contributions to the field of information and computer ethics through his/her research, service, and vision. The recipient's work should have broad professional, theoretical or societal impact. Dr. Grodzinsky's teaching focus includes Computer Ethics, Software Engineering, Systems Analysis and Design, Networking, and Human Computer Interaction. Her research focuses on issues related to society and technology. She has presented internationally on topics such as autonomous agency, open source, privacy, intellectual property and the responsibility of software developers. Dr. Grodzinsky joined the Sacred Heart University faculty in 1985 and became Professor Emerita in 2018.

CEPE 2025
Abstracts

Artificial Intelligence in Embryo Selection: Ethical Implications and Challenges

Prof. Maurizio Balistreri, DISTU, University of Tuscia, maurizio.balistreri@unitus.it

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in the field of in vitro fertilization (IVF) is reshaping the process of embryo selection, presenting profound ethical challenges and raising critical questions about its implications for individuals and society. The presentation investigates two primary models of AI-driven embryo selection. The first model operates based on the preferences and values of prospective parents, allowing them to exert significant influence over the decision-making process. The second model, in contrast, relies on parameters established by programmers or health professionals, shifting the locus of decision-making to external agents. Each model carries distinct ethical considerations, including concerns about autonomy, fairness, and accountability.

One of the key ethical dilemmas associated with AI-driven embryo selection is its potential to exacerbate social inequalities. By enabling access to highly advanced reproductive technologies, this practice risks creating disparities between those who can afford such technologies and those who cannot, further entrenching social divides. Additionally, the reliance on AI introduces concerns about the dehumanization of reproduction. The intimate, deeply personal act of choosing to have a child risks being reduced to a computational process, raising questions about the role of technology in shaping one of humanity's most fundamental experiences.

Moreover, the introduction of AI into embryo selection could redefine the concept of parental responsibility. Parents may face new pressures to justify their choices, especially if they are empowered to select embryos based on AI-generated predictions about potential outcomes such as health, intelligence, or physical attributes. This raises broader societal concerns about the increasing influence of enhancement-oriented mindsets, where children are valued not simply for who they are but for how they align with preconceived expectations.

The presentation also explores the implications of a potential future where AI could select embryos from a vast population, transcending the individual family unit. In such scenarios, ethical questions arise about the nature of parental love and societal perspectives on enhancement. Would such a future alter our understanding of unconditional love, or would it reshape societal norms regarding what constitutes an "ideal" child? These considerations touch upon deeply philosophical questions about the values we uphold as a society and the role of technology in shaping them.

Finally, this paper evaluates the comparative ethical concerns of AI-driven embryo selection versus genome editing interventions. While both technologies aim to influence reproduction, they differ in their potential to deepen social injustices. AI-based embryo selection may perpetuate inequities by privileging certain traits or characteristics, while genome editing might involve direct alterations to the genetic makeup of embryos, raising distinct concerns about consent, safety, and long-term consequences.

This analysis underscores the urgent need for robust ethical oversight in reproductive technologies. Without careful consideration and regulation, the integration of AI into embryo selection risks undermining fundamental ethical principles, such as equality, dignity, and autonomy. By addressing these challenges, society can better navigate the complex intersection of technology, reproduction, and human values.

Through an examination of these ethical issues, this presentation intends to contribute to the broader discourse on the responsible use of AI in reproductive medicine. It advocates for a balanced approach that acknowledges the transformative potential of AI while safeguarding against its potential harms. As we stand at the frontier of technological advancements in reproduction, this paper calls for a collective effort to ensure that innovation aligns with humanity's core ethical values.

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in in vitro fertilization (IVF) is transforming the process of embryo selection, raising critical ethical questions. This presentation examines two primary models of AI-driven embryo selection: one based on the preferences and values of prospective parents, and the other determined by the parameters set by programmers or health professionals. Ethical challenges inherent to these models include the potential for increased social inequality, the dehumanization of reproduction, and the redefinition of parental responsibilities. Furthermore, the talk explores the implications of a future where AI might select embryos from a vast population, prompting reflection on the nature of parental love and societal attitudes toward enhancement. Finally, the presentation evaluates whether AI-driven embryo selection could deepen social injustices compared to genome editing, underscoring the urgent need for robust ethical oversight in reproductive technologies.

Unveiling HEARTH Teams Leadership, a Human-Centric Leadership Model for Remote and Tech-Hybrid Teams

*Dr. Emily Barresi, Strategic Leadership PhD Candidate Regent University,
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As artificial intelligence and robotics rapidly integrate into the global business domain, the need for effective leadership in managing remote and sociotechnical teams is more pressing than ever. This paper introduces a pioneering leadership

model, HEARTH (Human Ethics Approach for Remote and Tech-Hybrid) Teams Leadership, set to launch in early 2025 as the culmination of doctoral studies at Regent University. The model equips leaders with a comprehensive, human-centric approach to navigating the complexities of remote teams and those employing AI, robotics, and other modern technology in roles traditionally held by humans.

HEARTH Team Leadership focuses on seven elements related to three main components: culture, human ethics, and technical literacy. The model emphasizes fostering a collaborative and inclusive culture that bridges the gap between human and AI/robotic team members and considers the competencies leaders need for technology-mediated environments. Human-centered ethical considerations are at the core, addressing issues such as algorithmic bias, fairness, privacy, and the impact of AI on human rights and societal norms. Additionally, the model underscores the necessity for leaders to possess a high level of technical literacy to effectively oversee AI and robotic systems integration and ensure their alignment with organizational values and goals. The model is encapsulated by trust and transparency, which are foundational factors for teams of this composition.

The uniqueness of this framework lies in its dual focus on human-centered leadership principles and the integration of advanced technologies like AI and robotics within remote work environments. While many leadership frameworks exist, they often overlook the intricacies of navigating trust and collaboration in the context of rapidly evolving technology integration in everyday tasks. By emphasizing the importance of human-centric values in leadership, such as empathy, communication, and transparency, alongside the necessary integration of modern technologies, this framework offers a holistic approach to addressing the challenges faced by remote and tech-hybrid leaders. It acknowledges the modern working interplay between human dynamics and technological advancements, highlighting the need for a balanced approach that prioritizes both aspects to foster trust, collaboration, and success in work settings where modern challenges, such as automation displacement and loneliness, exist.

Leaders will gain insights into HEARTH Teams Leadership’s theoretical foundations and practical applications, which aim to equip leaders with the skills and knowledge required to lead with transparency in an increasingly AI-driven world. The model’s development is not just informed, but enriched by interdisciplinary research spanning leadership, industrial and organizational psychology, philosophy, ethics, law, computer science, and social sciences, ensuring a robust framework that addresses the multifaceted challenges of leading tech-hybrid teams. The practical application of the model is relevant across industries, from technology teams, agricultural operations, law enforcement, government and policy-making, aviation, medicine, and beyond.

Participants will explore how HEARTH Team Leadership can transform leadership practices and promote ethical, inclusive, and effective management of remote and tech-hybrid teams. This topic and model will contribute to the broader discourse on the normative implications and philosophical challenges of remote work, robotics, and AI in contemporary society. Because technical literacy in leadership is imperative, this model contributes to a human-centric focus in leading to the future of work.

AI as Mere Mimicry: Why Artificial Intelligence Lacks Genuine Ethical Agency from an Aristotelian-Thomistic Perspective

Prof. Hugolin Bergier, Regis University (Denver, CO), hbergier@regis.edu

This paper argues that, despite their sophisticated behaviors, artificial intelligence (AI) systems fundamentally lack genuine ethical agency because they possess no interiority or intentionality. Using Aristotle’s distinctions between product (*poiêton*), making (*poiêsis*), and acting (*praxis*), this analysis demonstrates that AI actions fall firmly within *poiêsis*—mere production or mimicry—rather than *praxis*, which involves moral deliberation and intention. Thomas Aquinas’s clear separation between interior acts (intentions of the will) and exterior acts (mere actions) further supports the claim that AI cannot achieve moral agency, as genuine morality requires an internal act of will. Additionally, drawing from G.E.M. Anscombe’s insights on intentional action, the paper shows that AI systems lack “knowledge without observation”—a critical component of genuine intention. Thus, AI operates purely through externally observable processes and fails to exhibit the rational, interior principle required for Aristotelian virtues like *phronesis* (practical wisdom) or even *techne* (craft knowledge). Ultimately, the paper concludes that, regardless of complexity, AI remains an advanced instrument rather than a moral agent, underscoring the necessity for human responsibility in the ethical governance of AI.

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AI case-law before the AI Act: artificial intelligence regulation by the case-law of the Court of Justice on the GDPR

Dr. A. Bouchagiar, PhD candidate at the Ionian University (Corfu, Greece), Antonios.Bouchagiar@ec.europa.eu

The AI Act is well-known as the first legal framework on artificial intelligence (AI) in the world. It entered into force on 1 August 2024 and will be fully applicable two years later. However, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) already includes provisions that regulate certain AI applications, such as Article 22 on automated individual decision-making. Such provisions have been expansively interpreted by the Court of Justice of the EU in recent judgments. For example, the Schufa case can be seen as the precursor of future case-law on artificial intelligence. The case concerned data subjects that were unable to obtain a loan by banks due to their low score by agencies assessing the creditworthiness of individuals at the banks' request. When attempting to object to that outcome and to obtain explanations on their low score, they were trapped in a lacuna. On the one hand, the bank replied that it had merely relied on the agency's score on which it lacked expertise to provide further explanations. On the other hand, the agency replied that its only client was the bank and that it was up to the bank to decide whether to enter in a loan contract with a given person. The Court of Justice covered that lacuna by ruling that there was already a *de facto* automated decision at the level of the agency in cases where a low score excluded an individual from the credit market or where the score predetermined the terms of the loan to be granted by the banks (judgment in Schufa, paras 40-73).

Moreover, in several cases the Court has set out the precise modalities for data subjects to receive a copy of their personal data from controllers (Article 15 GDPR), such as by patients requesting data from their medical practitioners or by individuals requesting data from commercial agencies rating their creditworthiness at the request of banks (judgments in *Österreichische Datenschutzbehörde* and in *FT*). Article 15(1)(h) GDPR provides specifically that the controller must inform the data subject on the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, and provide at least meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject (see similar provisions in 2 Articles 13(2)(f) and 14(2)(g) GDPR). In a recent case where the judgment is still pending but the Advocate General's opinion has been issued (opinion in *Dun & Bradstreet Austria*), the Court is asked what level of detail credit rating agencies must provide on the operation of their algorithms in order to provide data subjects with "meaningful information" under Article 15(1)(f) GDPR and how this can be reconciled with the protection of those agencies' trade secrets. The judgment in this case will normally be issued before the deadline for submission of papers.

The proposed paper will analyse the above case-law and the lessons that can be drawn from it on the regulation of AI in the EU. In particular, the paper will research into general principles of EU law on the regulation of AI, which possibly stem from the Charter of Fundamental Rights and are reflected in the GDPR. Such general principles stemming from

EU primary law would exist independently of any secondary legislation, and therefore they would apply before and after the entry into force of the AI Act.

Indicative Bibliography:

EU legislation

Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence, OJ L, 2024/1689, 12.7.2024.

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1.

Case-law of the Court of Justice of the EU

Judgment in Case C-634/21 SCHUFA Holding (Scoring) ECLI:EU:C:2023:957.

Judgment in Case C-307/22 FT (Copies du dossier médical) ECLI:EU:C:2023:811.

Judgment in Case C-487/21 Österreichische Datenschutzbehörde ECLI:EU:C:2023:369.

Opinion of Advocate General Richard de la Tour in Case C-203/22 Dun & Bradstreet Austria ECLI:EU:C:2024:745.

Articles in law journals

Binns R. and Veale M. (2021). Is that your final decision? Multi-stage profiling, selective effects, and Article 22 of the GDPR. *International Data Privacy Law*, 319.

Colonna L. (2024). Teachers in the loop? An analysis of automatic assessment systems under Article 22 GDPR. *International Data Privacy Law*, 3.

Dewitte P. and Ausloos J. (2024). Chronicling GDPR Transparency Rights in Practice: The Good, the Bad and the Challenges Ahead. *International Data Privacy Law*, 106.

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Paal B. (2023). Case Note: Article 22 GDPR: Credit Scoring Before the CJEU. *Global Privacy Law Review*, 127.

Thouvenin F., Früh A. and Henseler S. (2022). Article 22 GDPR on Automated Individual Decision-Making: Prohibition or Data Subject Right? *European Data Protection Law Review*, 183. 4

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Emotiveillance: Inferring emotions in the age of artificial intelligence

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Emotions, as physical and mental states resulting from neurophysiological changes, can be seen as among our innermost data (Schacter, Gilbert & Wegner, 2011; Ekman & Davidson, 1994; Panksepp, 2004; Barrett, Lewis & Haviland-Jones, 2016). They can be hidden from and imperceptible to others, when kept secret and unexpressed. Still, contemporary uses of Artificial Intelligence ('AI') can be aimed at emotion-inferring (Chan, 2021; Katirai, 2023; ARTICLE 19, 2021; Macey-Banzon, Beaver & Taub, 2024).

These AI-implementations could benefit society in various areas, ranging from the protection of health (e.g., emotion recognition for therapeutical purposes) to traffic safety (e.g., detection of physical/mental states linked to fatigue of drivers with a view to preventing accidents) (Artificial Intelligence Act, 2024, recitals 18, 44). However, such AI-uses could pose critical risks for the right to privacy and the protection of personal data. A prime example is surveillance aimed at emotion recognition in the area of education, which can involve vulnerable individuals (i.e., minors) and intrusive processing of sensitive data (like opaque processing of biometric data), resulting in privacy invasions, but also limitations to other human rights and freedoms (Barrett, 2020).

This contribution aims to examine how AI-implementations aimed at emotion-inferring could be adequately regulated to eliminate or minimise their impact on the right to privacy and the protection of personal data. First, it assesses whether and the degree to which AI-implementations aimed at emotion-inferring can interfere with privacy. Second, it detects the main regulatory challenges of subjecting AI-implementations aimed at emotion-inferring to the European legal regime on, on the one hand, privacy and personal data protection and, on the other hand, AI. Third, it recommends a classification approach to AI-implementations aimed at emotion-inferring with a view to adequately tackling the challenges identified and, ultimately, eliminating or minimising the impact of such implementations on the right to privacy and the protection of personal data.

More precisely, this contribution approaches the concept of 'emotion' from a law and psychology perspective (Bornstein & Wiener, 2010; Maroney, 2006), with a view to addressing definitional challenges and drawing linkages between the notions of 'law', 'artificial intelligence' and 'emotion'. Moreover, it scrutinises AI-implementations aimed at emotion-inferring to detect their opportunities and limitations and assess their possible impact on the right to privacy

and the protection of personal data. On the basis of their potential impact, it recommends a classification approach to such AI-implementations.

The recommended scheme relies upon the long-developed, well-established and standardised assessment of legality, legitimacy and necessity that is typically applied by the European Court of Human Rights ('ECtHR'), when establishing an interference of a state measure or practice with a human right or freedom. After examining case law of the ECtHR on surveillance and privacy, this contribution analyses the specific elements of the legality-, the legitimacy- and the necessity-test; it then elaborates a fully-fledged Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment ('FRIA') that could be performed by an independent expert authority in a mandatory, targeted and ex ante fashion.

Building upon growing literature on ex ante regulation of technological uses via FRIAs (Gerards, 2024), the recommended classification approach determines the detailed steps to be followed by the proposed independent expert authority with a view to: addressing the 'who', the 'what', the 'why' and the 'how' of an intended AI-use; accordingly classifying the concrete AI-use; identifying opportunities and limitations; assessing legality, legitimacy and necessity of the AI-use at hand; and giving a 'go', 'no-go' or 'go-in-condition' decision before the actual AI-implementation in the real world.

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Policing AI: Towards an ethical framework for AI risk assessment in criminal investigation contexts

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Artificial intelligence (AI) applications are fast becoming critical tools in police work, aiding with data analysis, investigation, and crime prevention. AI can enhance efficiency, improve decision-making, or optimise resource allocation in law enforcement. However, the use of AI in police applications – inherently a high-risk context – also comes with significant risks that can hold severe implications for all individuals and groups involved. Beyond ethical reflection of notions like fairness, privacy, transparency, or accountability, it is thus necessary to introduce robust risk assessment adhering to high ethical standards in view of concrete use cases. The purpose of AI risk and impact assessment frameworks, then, is to identify the specific risks and (potential) impacts of AI applications and to classify these applications accordingly, with the objective of applying appropriate measures for mitigating the harms they may

cause to individuals or groups. Translating high-level ethical principles into practical tools and putting risk assessment into practice, however, comes with several challenges, not least due to the contingent nature of risk tolerance and risk prioritisation. In the past years, the extensive progress in the research and application of AI has been accompanied by efforts to collect, define, and justify frameworks with abstract ethical principles (HLEG 2019; Hagendorff 2020; Jobin et al. 2019). In addition, there are emerging initiatives to make these AI ethical principles operationalisable for evaluations, certifications, standards or regulatory attempts, among them the IEEE 7000 Series, the German Standardisation Roadmap on AI, the AI Ethics Impact Group (AIEIG) framework to operationalise AI ethics, or NIST AI 100-1. However, many remain in the draft stage or have not been further developed for specific use cases. Furthermore, these approaches are mostly limited to a medium level of framework setting, while the concrete, practical level of the sector-specific proposal is still missing in many places. In this paper, we offer an in-depth engagement with the challenges of selecting and operationalising ethical principles in the context of AI risk assessment. We propose a concrete solution in the form of a risk matrix developed in the context of the VIKING1 project, i.e., a framework for the application of ethical principles to the process of developing and implementing AI systems in police investigation contexts that classifies applications according to their risks. We first offer a comparative analysis of existing frameworks for ethical risk assessment and their value for different stakeholders. Drawing, among others, on the Cap.AI approach (Floridi et al. 2022), we argue that a dynamic and iterative approach is best suited for meeting the complex social, technological, legal, and ethical challenges of AI risk assessment, particularly in the complex contexts in which police applications operate. Based on this theoretical foundation, we then propose a matrix model for assessing the risks and impacts of AI system in police applications such as facial recognition, voice recognition, object detection, and text classification systems. We illustrate the practical application of the matrix with the help of a concrete use case from the VIKING project. Keywords: AI ethics, policing, risk assessment, risk matrix

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Naturalizing Artificial Intelligence and the Social Project

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The ethical challenges posed by artificial intelligence (AI) are already widely acknowledged, with a vast array of normative analyses detailing how these specific technologies—or their particular technical characteristics—give rise to such concerns. While the value of such inquiry, and the importance of redressing the many salient issues identified, especially in the face of rapid proliferation and integration of AI into society, is not disputed. I nevertheless contend that such ethical inquiry alone does not suffice to fully capture the relevant ethical concerns generated by such emerging technologies. Rather, with AI increasingly coming to form part of our social “infrastructure” (Heilinger, 2022), shaping our relationships to each other and ourselves (cf. Author, 2024), the urgency of situating AI ethics within broader questions of social and moral progress becomes apparent. Accordingly, I propose that there is a need for further ethical investigations (cf. van Maanen, 2022) that move beyond a narrow consideration of the technologies themselves to

engage the normative and structural conditions that form part of the background conditions of AI, underpinning, for example, AI's development and integration. As such, there is a need to appreciate the broader sense in which they are socio-technical systems. Drawing on Philip Kitcher's concept of the "ethical project" (2011), I therefore argue for an expanded ethical inquiry that situates AI within our ongoing social project, understood as the continuous collective endeavour to foster human co-flourishing (cf. Kitcher, 2017). To this end, I explore how AI may serve as both a facilitator and inhibitor of this project, depending on whether it reinforces "suspect norms" (Little, 1998) or enables emancipatory possibilities (Author, Forthcoming). Central to this argument is the notion of "naturalizing technology"—in this case AI—building on Hickman's (1990; 2001) interpretation of John Dewey's philosophy of technology. The import of both Dewey and Hickman's work for AI ethics remains sorely underrealized. Naturalizing AI, as developed here, entails two interconnected tasks: (1) recognizing AI as emerging from and dynamically coupled to human lives, shaping and being shaped by existing norms, and (2) critically assessing the "aDordances" AI introduces, as technologies enable certain actions and foreclose others (cf. Brey, 2000; 2010, Klenk, 2022). Of course, these points have also found more recent articulation—particularly in post-phenomenology (cf. Ihde, 1990, 2002; Verbeek, 2005, 2011). However, it is worth presenting these insights from a Deweyan vantage since, unlike these schools, his philosophy was always inherently normative, directed towards the reconstruction of human experience. This approach underscores the importance of interrogating the desirability of the norms that AI reflects and perpetuates, since as Dewey famously noted, "[t]he fact that something is desired only raises the question of its desirability; it does not settle it" (1929, p.260). Accordingly, in naturalising AI, these technologies appear as a useful heuristic for pointing critical attention to existing features of socio-technical life. It also suggests a positive and a negative normative task. While the positive—i.e., asking what AI might do for enabling social progress—is more ambitious, it is bracketed here. Rather, the very possibility of social progress is something that must be preserved, and so the negative task is to ascertain what AI technologies—e.g. in perpetuating or cementing suspect norms—may be doing to hinder or curtail such possibilities for future progress. Through this I introduce the idea of an ethical backstop; a conceptual safeguard that seeks to protect against the erosion of those mechanisms—here once more following Dewey (1919)—needed to facilitate an open and inclusive society. By examining AI's role in shaping "experiments in living" (Anderson, 2014)—i.e., practical eDorts to reconfigure social practices and values—I position AI ethics as a means of navigating the broader social project in which these technologies are embedded. By combining and balancing existing granular ethical analyses of AI with higher-order reflections on the social project, AI ethics can become better equipped to recognising the full spectrum of ethical issues that accompany these technological innovations. Accordingly, it will be argued that adopting this dual perspective illuminates underappreciated ethical stakes of AI, which are vital for traversing the interplay between technological innovation and social progress.

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Responsible Deployment of AI Systems: The AIRDAU approach

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The literature on responsible and ethical AI has largely concentrated on the development of general guidance and governance models for AI and of approaches towards responsible development and design of AI systems – approaches such as Ethics by Design and Ethically Aligned Design. Relatively little attention has been paid to frameworks for the responsible deployment of AI systems. While development choices and government regulations are certainly important, many social and ethical implications of AI systems result from the choices and circumstances of deployment: choices made in hardware and software acquisition, institutional frameworks and policies, and decisions made by various stakeholders in the deploying organization.

This paper presents an approach for the responsible deployment of AI systems by organizations. The approach is called AIRDAU, which is an acronym for AI Responsible Deployment and Use. This approach is based in part on earlier work by the author and other researchers in the context of the EU-funded SATORI and SIENNA projects. The paper focuses on deployment of AI systems by organizations because AI systems are usually deployed within an organizational context, in which case the deploying organization bears primary responsibility for their deployment and subsequent use.

The AIRDAU approach will be developed in three steps. First, a perspective will be presented on the responsibility of deploying organizations for the ethical and social consequences of the systems that they deploy. It will be argued that organizations deploying AI have a responsibility to anticipate and mitigate potentially harmful and ethical consequences from the use of their systems, since they control and own these systems, influence their outcomes, and benefit from their use. This makes their accountability essential for ethical compliance and public trust.

Second, a general model will be presented for the responsible deployment of AI systems by organizations. This model does not include specific ethical guidelines and principles for the deployment of AI, but rather defines generic practices and organizational structures and procedures that are needed for responsible deployment. It is based on a model of the IT life cycle that is found in the two most widely accepted reference frameworks for IT management: ITIL and COBIT. The IT life cycle is thought of to consist of five subsequent processes: development of IT management strategies, acquisition and design of IT systems, deployment and implementation, service operation, and continuous monitoring, evaluation and improvement. Beyond this lifecycle, there is also the general IT governance strategy of the organization. For each of these six components of the IT lifecycle, guidelines and requirements are formulated for the responsible deployment of AI systems. For example, for the IT management strategy, it is recommended that it includes the adoption and communication to relevant audiences of ethics guidelines for AI systems, defines corresponding ethics requirements within role and responsibility descriptions of relevant staff, and includes policies for the implementation of the ethics guidelines and monitoring activities for compliance and performance. Similarly, for the acquisition and design phase, it is recommended that the business objective for which a system is needed is evaluated against the ethics guidelines that are defined to be part of the IT management strategy, and subsequent actions like procurement or in-house development take into account the relevant ethical guidelines for AI systems.

Ultimately, these guidelines and requirements—defined for each component of the IT lifecycle—will ensure that ethically aligned AI systems are acquired and deployed, that clear ethics guidelines govern their responsible use, and that accountability is distributed across various organizational units and roles. They will also establish processes for ethical assessment, risk management, continuous monitoring, and mitigation, while ensuring that managers, system operators, and end-users receive adequate training in responsible AI practices. As a result, the organization will be better equipped to minimize undesirable impacts and uphold ethical standards in AI deployment.

As stated, this is a general model for responsible deployment by organizations, and does not include substantial ethics guidelines. In step 3 of the paper, however, it will be explored how the model would handle specific ethics guidelines for AI. A number of guidelines are proposed that are widely accepted in the AI ethics literature and in approaches towards responsible AI. These include guidelines for human agency and liberty, privacy and security, fairness and non-discrimination, individual, societal and environmental well-being, transparency and accountability. It will be shown how these guidelines can be translated into specific operational guidelines for the responsible deployment of AI within the AIRDAU approach. This illustrates that AIRDAU is a robust and flexible approach that can accommodate a wide range of ethics guidelines AI, and is capable of equipping organizations with the tools and resources needed for the responsible deployment of AI systems.

The hidden risks of Ai-Driven medicine: why hemisphere theory matters for clinical ethics

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The introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) scribes in clinical settings is emblematic of an ongoing shift in the healthcare landscape. These systems, designed to passively record, transcribe, and summarise patient-clinician interactions, are touted as a means of alleviating the administrative burden on healthcare professionals, allowing them to refocus on direct patient care. However, their integration raises ethical, epistemological, and practical concerns that go beyond the typical discussions of privacy, security, and bias. This paper argues that a crucial yet underexamined aspect of AI's role in clinical practice is the nature of attention and its influence on medical decision-making.

Drawing on Iain McGilchrist's hemispheric model of cognition, this study explores how AI systems constitute an expression of left-hemispheric attention — favouring abstraction, categorisation, and rule-based processing over the right hemisphere's holistic, context-sensitive, embodied and intuitive engagement with the world (McGilchrist, 2009, 2021). This distinction is not merely a matter of cognitive preference but has profound implications for how clinicians engage with patients, interpret medical data, and make ethical decisions.

McGilchrist (2021) highlights how the right hemisphere plays a critical role in assessing the 'morality of actions, moral reasoning, and promoting prosocial norms' (p. 1343), a view supported by multiple studies (e.g., Hecht, 2014; Kuhl & Kazén, 2008; Miller et al., 2010; Mychack et al., 2001; Schultheiss, 2018). If AI scribes and decision-support systems become an increasingly dominant presence in the clinical environment, we risk subtly reinforcing left-hemispheric dispositions, prioritising efficiency, standardisation, and protocol adherence at the expense of deeper clinical intuition, empathy, and relational understanding.

A key promise of AI scribes is their potential to restore the doctor-patient relationship by reducing the cognitive and administrative overload imposed by electronic health records (EHRs) (Tierney et al., 2024). However, we must weigh this benefit against the possibility of clinicians becoming overly reliant on these systems, leading to a gradual erosion of their own ability to engage in the kind of nuanced, patient-centred reasoning that characterises true medical expertise (Dreyfus & Dreyfus, 1986). AI systems remain fundamentally constrained by their inability to grasp meaning the way that human beings do. They process language statistically to manipulate symbols rather than experientially to intuit meaning (reproducing a left-hemispheric approach to language), generating responses that appear coherent but lack the depth of understanding that comes from experience and embodied cognition (Jaeger et al., 2024; McGilchrist, 2021, Vigneau et al., 2011).

The unchecked proliferation of AI in clinical settings risks exacerbating a broader epistemic shift that has been underway for decades — a shift toward construing knowledge as primarily explicit, quantifiable, and rule-governed, rather than as something that also emerges from implicit, tacit, and contextual understanding (McGilchrist, 2009, 2021; Mumford, 1967). This shift is particularly concerning in medicine, where effective practice depends not only on the application of protocols and evidence-based guidelines but also on the clinician's ability to read subtle cues, synthesise disparate sources of information, and navigate the complex, often ambiguous reality of human health (Ambady et al., 2002; Bateson, 1973; Hong & Oh, 2020; Lee et al., 2019; Levinson et al., 1997).

If AI systems reinforce a mode of clinical reasoning that is predominantly left-hemispheric in nature, detached from the experience of both patients and practitioners (Shin et al., 2024), we risk diminishing the moral and relational dimensions of medicine. Ethical decision-making in healthcare has traditionally been informed by a balance of deontological, consequentialist, and virtue-ethical considerations, but AI, insofar as it mirrors left-hemispheric morality, aligns most naturally with rule-based, utilitarian frameworks (Dreyfus & Dreyfus, 1986; McGilchrist, 2009, 2021). This alignment could lead to an overemphasis on efficiency and cost-effectiveness, sidelining the more nuanced, context-sensitive judgments that arise from clinical wisdom and moral intuition.

To mitigate these risks, it is crucial to approach AI integration with an awareness of its cognitive and ethical ramifications. Rather than allowing AI to dictate the scope of medical practice, we must ensure that its implementation supports rather than supplants the right-hemispheric, meaning-oriented aspects of clinical expertise (Dreyfus & Dreyfus, 1986; McGilchrist, 2009, 2021). This may involve fostering a culture of critical engagement with AI-generated outputs, and emphasising the continued cultivation of human clinical judgment and patient care. Additionally, interdisciplinary dialogue between clinicians, ethicists, AI developers, and philosophers can help shape AI policies that prioritise the preservation of medicine as both a science and an art.

The future of AI in healthcare should not be reduced — left hemisphere style — to a binary choice between wholesale adoption and outright rejection. Instead, it must be guided by an understanding of human cognition and the attention that technological interventions cultivate.

By applying hemisphere theory to AI integration, we can better foster an approach that complements rather than displaces the human aspect of clinical practice, ensuring that medicine remains rooted in human understanding, relational depth, and the full breadth of cognitive and ethical reasoning.

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E(thi)cological Co-evolution: Ethical Roadmaps for Symbiotic AI Interaction

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The aim of this paper is to critically examine the ethical debate that has emerged in the European context to regulate the rise and spread of Artificial Intelligence based technologies. In this sense, it has been demonstrated that the introduction of autonomous algorithmic systems in various fields, for instance in trading or healthcare, has produced innumerable advantages, given the great capacity of AI systems to process and analyze massive amounts of data. However, the same introduction has also generated the possibility of producing certain risks, such as various forms of biases and algorithmic discrimination. It is evident that, within the context of this framework, a number of bodies have been established by the European Union with the objective of producing an adequate body of ethics and legislation. The purpose of this initiative is to stem the potential risks posed by the automation process. In order to explore this theoretical production, a methodology is adopted that is inspired by Michel Foucault's approach. This methodology is a genealogical one, which is utilized in order to map the ethical debate that has been produced on the subject, and to illuminate the epistemological and ontological regimes on which certain ethical perspectives are founded. In this sense, the initial section of the paper identifies two primary and contraposed views that underpin ethical approaches to AI: the human-centric and algorithm-centric perspectives. The human-centric approach, widely endorsed in European regulatory frameworks (e.g., White Paper on Artificial Intelligence, 2020; EU AI Act, 2024), advocates aligning technological development with human values and socio-economic priorities. However, the humanistic presupposition embedded in this framework often overlooks the extent to which AI systems operate as expansive, self-regulating networks that

capture human behaviours to achieve predefined objectives. These networks, by virtue of their design, are prone to biases that may perpetuate discriminatory practices and exacerbate systemic inequities. E(thi)cological Co-evolution: Ethical Roadmaps for Symbiotic AI Interaction 3 Conversely, the algorithm-centric perspective emphasizes the technical architectures underpinning AI systems, framing ethical concerns as challenges of operationalizing moral principles within system design. This approach risks reducing ethics to a set of procedural or computational constraints, sidestepping deeper questions about the relational and structural dynamics between humans and technology. This binary opposition presupposes a metaphysical dualism, perpetuating a polarized ethical debate over the primacy of either human or technological agency. To surpass this rigid opposition, we propose to rethink Human-AI interaction in the light of the notion of symbiosis. After a brief recall of the history of the notion of Human-AI symbiosis, invented by J.C.R. Licklider, we analyze its potential to transform the way we conceptualize intelligence and agency in socio-technical systems. Drawing on Katherine Hayles' concept of 'cognitive assemblages', we challenge rigid human-technology distinctions, demonstrating that AI systems exhibit analogous cognitive capabilities by receiving, processing, and interpreting environmental data flows to enact agency. The metaphor of symbiosis, adapted from biological contexts, highlights the cooperative and coevolutionary dynamics between humans and AI, suggesting that their interaction constitutes an evolving cognitive ecology rather than a dichotomy. Finally, we advocate for an "e(thi)cological" perspective that reconceptualizes ethical evaluation as a roadmap for fostering symbiotic enhancements in human-AI interaction. This perspective moves beyond static normative models to embrace an integrated approach, recognizing AI not merely as tools but as active sociotechnical participants in shaping new forms of collective agency and societal organization.

AI-Assisted Self-Expression: A Challenge to Authenticity?

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As Artificial Intelligence (AI), and particularly generative AI (GenAI), is becoming increasingly central in debates in and outside academia, concerns arise regarding the authenticity of –possibly AI-generated– visual and written digital content (Floridi, 2024; Lee, 2023). While these discussions are relevant, in this paper I argue that there is another, perhaps more urgent, form of authenticity at stake in our AI-driven digitized lives, namely the kind that can be attributed to human beings, also known as personal authenticity. This research aims to make a case for the inclusion of this notion of authenticity into the repertoire of normative concepts –including autonomy, privacy, and accountability, among others (Müller, 2023)– which current conversations within the philosophy and ethics of AI revolve around. To support this argument, the paper takes off with an analysis of the philosophical understanding of authenticity, which differs from hyper-individualistic “deviant forms” (Taylor, 2018, p. 23) present in everyday language as well as in self-help movements (Guignon, 2004; Varga, 2014). By critically assessing insights from philosophers who can be grouped under the loose tradition of authenticity (Ferrara, 1993), spanning from the second half of the 18th century to the present, I propose a non-essentialist, intersubjective definition of authenticity that includes an existential dimensional and an ethical one. Put very briefly, authenticity is not a fixed attribute, but a continuous attitude of owning oneself. This requires acknowledging that one possesses a certain degree of freedom to create oneself, taking responsibility for who one is in one's relations with others, as well as understanding the world around oneself and one's place in it, among other features. This theoretical lens also provides a justification for the normative force underlying authenticity. As an individual as well as a social virtue, is central to the good life (Guignon, 2004): it “allows to live (potentially) a fuller and more differentiated life, because more fully appropriated as our own” (Taylor, 2018, p. 74), while it also enables responsible relations with others (Golomb, 1995). In times characterized by relativism and loss of meaning, authenticity is considered the “last measure of value and a common currency” (Varga & Guignon, 2023), offering a pathway to a meaningful life. For reasons like these, many authors defend authenticity as an ethical ideal (Bauer, 2017; Varga, 2014) or speak of an ethic of authenticity (Ferrara, 1993, 2002; Taylor, 2018). Because the ideal of authenticity is focused on action, that is, on living authentically rather than on being authentic, the growing use of AI in digitized social life leads to numerous ways in which it might impact authenticity. For this research, however, I illustrate this by examining one concrete aspect of authenticity in relation to a specific kind of GenAI technology. Particularly, the paper explores how –partially– outsourcing forms of digital self-expression to Large Language Models (LLMs), such as OpenAI's ChatGPT or Google's Gemini, affects authenticity. In a basic sense, what is meant by self-expression is the expression of one's identity to others, for example, through verbal activity. Digitally, there is a wide range of possibilities for verbal self-expression, e.g. social media profiles, posts, and messages to others. What are the implications for authenticity when such expressions are generated with the help of an LLM? Several hypothetical scenarios are played out in this research to find that AI-assisted self-expression may constitute what Jean-Paul Sartre, a key philosopher in the tradition of authenticity, calls bad faith (Sartre, 2007), in other words, inauthenticity. This argument rests on the affirmation that self-expression plays a crucial role in an authentic life on a direct and an indirect level. On a direct level, living authentically involves being true to oneself (Trilling, 1972), that is, owning up to who one is in one's expressive actions. On an indirect level, authenticity requires creating and discovering oneself (Taylor, 2018, p. 74), and self-expression,

which entails thinking about oneself, is one of the key means to do so. In sum, this research paper problematizes the relationship between authenticity and AI and sheds light on its ethical implications. By examining the specific case of turning to LLMs for self-expression purposes, I show one particular way in which the usage of GenAI technology can undermine personal authenticity. I conclude that these tensions ought to be taken into account when thinking about responsible use and design of AI. Ultimately, rather than providing definitive answers, this philosophical discussion raises questions about the role of AI in living (in)authentically and the very concept of authenticity, opening the door to further research about authenticity in the fields of philosophy and ethics of AI.

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Linking journalistic values and AI ethics. Transparency in the design, development and deployment of AI tools for media professionals

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The emergence of generative AI presents new opportunities and challenges for many different sectors and industries. In media organizations, AI systems can be utilized across multiple tasks, e.g. in news production, information gathering and sensemaking, news discovery, research, ideation, content curation and fake news detection (Diakopoulos, Cools, et al., 2024; Hrkova et al., 2022). In this paper, we argue that professional ethics and AI ethics should be linked in the design, development, and deployment of AI tools in the context of media professions. Journalists and media professionals are already guided by professional ethics standards, which emphasise values such as truthfulness, accuracy, fairness, impartiality and non-discrimination (IFJ, 2019; EFCSN, 2022). In light of technological developments, individual media organizations are now expanding on such professional ethics frameworks to ensure that the use of AI tools happens responsibly, including recognizing their role in educating the public about emerging AI technologies. On an international level, initiatives such as the Paris Charter on AI and Ethics explains a normative commitment “to examining and reporting on the impacts of AI with accuracy, nuance, and a critical mind.” (RSF, 2023) Professional membership organizations such as the Public Media Alliance and the European Broadcaster's Union are assisting knowledge sharing efforts by creating repositories of organizational AI policy documents. These documents aim to protect journalistic values when using AI. Our paper reports an unstructured thematic analysis with two coding rounds of these organizational policy documents that categorizes the different approaches that media organizations have to setting and implementing policy in the use of generative AI. The main focus of our contribution are the ethical issues that may arise when integrating AI tools in the workflow of journalists, which stem from the design choices that informed the tool. In line with Diakopoulos, Trattner, et al. (2024), we argue that professional ethics should be considered from the outset of designing, developing, and deploying AI tools for media professionals. Additionally, we argue that professional journalistic ethics should also pay closer attention to the design choices of AI tools, thus the field of AI ethics. This goes beyond the current organizational policy documents, which are primarily concerned with the ways in which AI systems are used by journalists, with little focus on the selection of which kind of AI systems should be used and how these were created. This omission might be owed to the fact that these policy documents mostly respond to systems that already exist or because it is perceived as infeasible to demand more information on the

technical details and ethical decisions made by those who have built these systems. We recommend making AI ethics more accessible for media professionals by introducing straightforward documentation of model properties through model cards (Mitchell et al., 2019). Model cards give users an understanding about the properties and training of an AI system, and can describe both technical, e.g. choice of dataset and model performance, and ethical dimensions, e.g. intended use cases and foreseeable ethical risks. We argue that model cards that incorporate interpretive fields on AI ethics are an important bridge to bring deeper awareness about the design and development of AI systems for media professionals. The other way around, model cards for AI systems in the journalism context challenge technology developers to spell out their assumptions and to communicate in accessible ways for the audience of media professionals. Model cards could thus play an important role in bridging ethical expectations and needs between two different professions.

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Artificial Intelligence and responsible authorship: Ethical considerations

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The public announcement of the artificial intelligence system chatbot ChatGPT on November 30, 2022, by OpenAI resulted in a massive wave of social, economic, political, and ethical discussions. Colossal technological company competitors launched similar programs or accelerated their efforts to achieve the development of similar products. Less than two months after the Open AI announcement, paper publications appeared claiming ChatGPT as a co-author. The ethical challenge for all the editors of scientific journals was considerable. Was ChatGPT a legitimate author of scientific papers? The editorial teams of the leading scientific journals *Science* and *Nature* firmly opposed such practices (Stokel-Walker 2023; Thorp 2023). All the scientific publishers adopted the ban on AI-generated papers, and a new statement was added to the prerequisites for the authors of scientific papers. The authors should affirm that they didn't use AI systems in text or image preparation. If they used Large Language Models (LLMs), AI-generated text systems, or AI image-creator systems while preparing their paper, the authors should describe how they used them and for which purpose. This decision was based on the ethical issue of the author's responsibility since it was clear that the AI system could not be responsible for the generation of intellectual products, whilst the same stands for its developers. For the final approval and publication of the paper, all authors must approve a publication's final content and format. Furthermore, using an AI system when preparing a scientific paper may be problematic because of the risk of information error for several reasons. Firstly, because of poor development or pre-training of the system for specific applications. Secondly, misinterpretation of user query formulation. Thirdly, deliberate deception of the AI system by human actors can be done by feeding the system with erroneous or deceiving data. And finally, because of the use of misleading data incorrectly produced by the machine algorithm in the form of artificial intelligence illusions. If the human user accepts these errors and incorporates them into a scientific manuscript, the result would be the generation of a falsified or misleading paper. It would be challenging for editors or peer-reviewers to identify plausible AI-generated text or believable images with traditional methodologies. Using AI systems to detect AI-generated information could be equally problematic because of misinterpretation or inherent system biases. The publication of AI-generated information may increase the risk of publishing false articles that mislead or confuse the scientific community. In the long run, accumulating this information would lead to a self-feeding, error-prone scientific information reporting mechanism. Noteworthy, the impact of ChatGPT after the 2022 Open AI announcement was so profound in science that

it counted more than a thousand papers on this topic just nine months after its public presentation. This milestone was achieved by the Google search engine fourteen years after its public introduction. In this report, we will discuss these ethical considerations, the responsibility of scientific authors when using AI tools to prepare their papers, and the risk of incorporating algorithmic biases and errors in their work, as reported in the relative scientific literature.

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Delivering fairness and equity to European Union leaders' tweets: ethical considerations and contributions of artificial intelligence and access to data

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Fairness, equity, open access to data and technology along with other ethical considerations that relate to data processing and AI are still challenging us. Although humans have long been dreaming about robots with intelligence of their own, little did we realize how important equity and fairness would be in developing these machines. We have still not managed to achieve justice at all levels, either social or racial or other, although technology seems to be pacing very fast, bringing into light new causes for concern. However, artificial intelligence can bring much more to our lives than concern; it can amplify fairness and equity, speed up processes, free up our time in order to perform more important tasks, enrich our metadata and bring more value to our datasets, etc. Our paper aims to a) address concerns and b) bring into light ways that artificial intelligence (AI) can deliver fairness and equity. Practical examples will be based on our research on political tweets of European Union prime ministers and leaders. Firstly, we will highlight the importance of open data and widely accessible technologies. Financial barriers, premium accounts in software services, organization/government policies are few of the factors that might hinder research. For instance, will a country or a university that bans use of generative artificial intelligence be able to compete in current scientific research and publishing? Or will researchers who do not have access to subscription services to X or some academic researcher exemption be able to access data? The danger that lies behind these questions is research that is conducted only by those who can afford access to data, thus excluding some voices. Even the prevalence of the English language in natural language processing applications is a factor that unwittingly promotes one language over another. In a dataset such as ours, with tweets being posted in a variety of languages, we consider using services that translate text automatically into English in order to obtain a dataset that can be processed. Secondly, we will highlight ways that AI can assist researchers in bringing fairness and equity in their data. There are numerous researches on political social networks and the conclusions that can be drawn from political statements, posts on social media, tweets, etc. But are we doing justice to the content of the statements made by politicians? Or are we just utilizing the technology that exists, not the technology that we should be using in order to process these statements to the maximum? Artificial intelligence will surely make our lives easier by processing texts from tweets faster. But can it offer something new to our research? We argue that it can bring something new and that it can also bring fairer results to research output. Thus, politicians can benefit from having their statements processed in a more just and accurate way. We suggest using transcripts from videos and audio, along with transcriptions from images attached to tweets, into datasets. New technology exists that can transcribe video to text (e.g. Whisper), audio to text and image to text (e.g. ChatGPT, Gemini). All this is becoming available, freely or with a price, to the public via large language or automatic speech recognition models. This means that political statements could be evaluated more fairly as more and fuller content would be included in the process. This is a way of enriching a dataset's metadata and bringing more value to it. If we add alternative text automatically to each image attached to a tweet, then we produce inclusive content and perhaps more metadata for processing. The possibilities are endless. It is up to us to raise these issues and adjust the technology to our needs.

Ethical Boundaries in the Use of Private and Public Information for Deepfake Creation

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Deepfake technology facilitates highly realistic manipulation of images, videos, and voices to create convincing digital media. The rapid evolution of this technology yields many new possibilities while simultaneously reshaping the contours of the ethical landscape confronting it. On the one hand, off-the-shelf products like MyHeritage's Deep Nostalgia have made it easy to create animated GIFs of dead loved ones or historical figures like Martin Luther King,

JR. These deepfakes allow us to connect with the legacies of the past and to create immersive learning experiences. Deepfakes have also enabled actors, like Tom Hanks in the movie *Here*, to give the performance of a lifetime due to deaging technology offered by the company Metaphysic. In this light, deepfakes have considerable value for use in artistic expression, historical recreation, and in promoting personal legacy. On the other hand, at the time of writing, Public Citizen reports that twenty-three U.S. states have enacted laws regulating the use of “nonconsensual intimate deepfakes”. The phenomenon affects both public and private citizens, but teenaged women are an especially targeted group. Living as the victim of deepfaked porn can be emotionally devastating, and the process of removing the porn from the ethers of the internet can be arduous and is itself sometimes traumatizing. In this light, deepfakes are morally repugnant and dangerous. As deepfakes grow in prevalence, debates surrounding the socially responsible and morally permissible use of information have intensified, and this duality of potential underscores the importance of establishing ethical guidelines to govern how deepfakes are created and shared. These debates are especially important in the current political climate, as they have been used to shape political views and influence voter behavior. Consider, for example, when Americans for Prosperity, a satirical PAC, launched a television ad campaign featuring a deepfake of then-North Carolina Lieutenant Governor Mark Robinson. The ad portrays a distorted version of Robinson making statements that blend actual past remarks with exaggerated content. The ad was criticized by both political allies and opponents. While Stiefel defended the ad as ethical satire, emphasizing that the AI-generated content reflects statements Robinson has made publicly, others stated that “any use of AI to mislead voters is unequivocally wrong”. While this particular deepfaked creation represents Robinson without his consent and in an exaggerated and one-dimensional way, it does so by accurately presenting statements that Robinson made in public. This case highlights questions about the kinds of information we can permissibly use to create deepfakes of individuals like Robinson, as well as questions about how and when that information can be permissibly used. This paper conducts a comparative analysis between intuitively ethical and intuitively unethical uses of deepfakes to characterize ethical boundaries on deepfake creation. In particular, we make a novel argument that a key condition on the permissible use of deepfakes involves preserving the contextual integrity of a deepfake’s source materials (i.e., the data and other information used in deepfake creation). Put roughly, one maintains the contextual integrity of deepfake source materials only when the materials are repurposed for use in the same context in which they were collected. Questions about contextual integrity notably dovetail with traditional ethical concerns relating to data ownership, consent, privacy, trust, and transparency. We argue that this is because many such concerns primarily arise when contextual integrity is violated, making the preservation of contextual integrity an ethical priority in deepfake creation. One important source of context for a deepfake’s source materials involves the distinction between public versus private information. We further explore the question of information in public versus private contexts through the novel application of “curtilage” — a concept traditionally applied to define the boundary around physical spaces, like one’s home, which is afforded privacy protections — to address the blurred line between public and private life in both physical and digital environments (see Avilez et al., 2014). We argue that digital spaces and the information found therein deserve a similar boundary, or “digital curtilage,” where individuals can expect a degree of privacy even when engaging online or when information about us is crystallized in digital spaces. The notion of curtilage becomes a framework to consider how deepfakes should respect these digital boundaries, especially when individuals’ private versus public personas are used. If we can anticipate when certain ethical issues will arise, based on contextual integrity violations, then we are better positioned to obviate moral injury to those impacted by deepfake technology, particularly the most vulnerable populations. We can assess whether the development and deployment of a deepfake is morally permissible given the types of information utilized in its creation. Further, identifying which information is public or private, or which falls into curtilage will help those attempting to regulate the deployment of deepfake technology in a way that protects those whose information is used to create deepfakes.

Some Common Grounds for Talking About Language Models’ Properties

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Various crucial questions in contemporary philosophy of AI are often modeled in this form: “To what extent Large Language Models can be said to know facts about the world?”. In this example, the inquiry not only drives technical research on model architecture, but also theoretical debates on testimony and the transmission of knowledge in the social environments where LLMs operate. This type of research program can be generalized outside epistemology: how to conceptualize specific LLM properties and where to draw boundaries in our own understanding of their performance? This is a strong trend that spans different philosophical fields in the current debate around AI systems, from philosophy of language (Green & Michel, 2022) to philosophy of action (Laukyte, 2017) and philosophy of mind (Butlin, 2021), just to mention a few. In this work, I will examine a case study from epistemology to test and explore what kind of theoretical understanding we typically adopt when we try to transfer our anthropocentric concepts to artificial systems. The research question, in this case, can be better formulated in these lines: “When we scrutinize current LLMs, on which grounds should we choose between an instrument-based account of information transmission and a testimony-based account of knowledge transmission, treating the system as an epistemic agent?”. The answer to this kind of question can be strictly conditioned on the philosopher’s ‘conceptual engineering’ agenda (Chalmers, 2020) or, more

plainly, by her degree of liberality in extending the relevant notion. The goal of this research is to draw a first, unexhaustive taxonomy of the different answers usually provided against this kind of challenge. I identify four main styles of answers: (i) Conservative views (ii) Hybrid views (iii) Abstracting views (iv) Liberal views. Conservative views strictly deny epistemic agency to LLMs, usually on the grounds that AI systems lack mental states, intentionality, personhood, and so on; the standard answer to the research question is usually deflationary or dismissing, with a few interesting exceptions (Mallory, 2023). Adopters of hybrid views design their account borrowing the missing intentional elements in AI systems from external sources, typically through human-computer interaction; some examples from this category include proxy agency (Ludwig, 2018) and quasi-sociality (Strasser & Schwitzgebel, forthcoming). Abstracting views usually work directly on concepts, aiming to reconstruct or adapt the relevant notion partially or utterly draining it from all the elements that are uncontroversially exclusive to humans; various functionalist approaches and proposals such as anthropocentric abstraction (Cappelen & Dever, 2021) fall under this category. While liberal views are very popular in the AI developer community they seem a bit more heterodox in philosophy. While a different degree of realism can be attached to the intentional stance depending on the author's research project, most of the studies in this department agree on ascribing mental states to AI systems when they exhibit a certain behavior at the relevant level of analysis. Each of these four styles has its own strengths and weaknesses, that can range from the high risk of 'conceptual borrowing' (Floridi & Nobre, 2024) for more liberal views to the substantial loss in theoretical heritage for the more conservative views. I will briefly list and discuss these benefits and shortcomings, framing relevant examples from the recent literature but suspending my judgment about the value of each view. Starting from this epistemological case study on LLMs, my main contribution will consist in designing an intuitive standard translation for different areas in philosophy of AI, clarifying commitments and consequences to address for each specific view. The benefits of a clearer and more grounded understanding of how a given theoretical strategy is situated in the bigger picture can then cascade on the matter of fact for the specific research question, and help in drawing the lines for a more stable and tractable conduct towards questions of the type: "To what extent we can say that an AI system can be/have/exhibit property X?". Once we can track consistent boundaries with our tools, we can secure the right position in the favoured debate, leading to faster alignment and better communication between scholars from different traditions on key issues about trust, responsibility, fairness and more.

Who creates when AI generates? The copyright puzzle in the age of Generative Artificial Intelligence

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The emergence of generative artificial intelligence (AI) marks a transformative development in the field of technology, bringing challenges to copyright law. Unlike traditional AI systems, which operate through deterministic processes, generative AI leverages cutting-edge machine learning techniques, including transformer architectures, diffusion models, generative adversarial networks (GANs) and multimodal models, to autonomously produce content across diverse modalities, such as text, images, music, and even multimodal outputs that combine these elements (Glenster & Gilbert, 2023). The copyright challenges associated with generative AI arise from two key areas: the inputs used to train AI systems and the copyrightability of AI-generated outputs. Indeed, generative AI is only capable of producing content because human works, often protected by copyright, have been used for its training (Bonadio et al., 2022). At the same time, the AI-generated outputs, often unpredictable and highly creative, raise critical legal questions about their copyrightability (Spindler, 2022). Moreover, one of the major copyright challenges associated with AI-generated outputs is the potential for copyright infringement when these outputs exhibit substantial similarity to a copyrighted work – whether entirely human-created or produced with AI assistance (Lemley, 2024). The complexity of the above copyright challenges extends beyond legal technicalities; they also touch upon deeper ethical questions about the foundations of a human-centric copyright system. With this in mind, this paper focuses on the copyright issues surrounding AI outputs, as they are particularly relevant to ethical considerations regarding the justifications and foundations of the current copyright system, with particular emphasis on the harmonized legal framework of the European Union (EU). Given the limitations of a short paper, a comprehensive analysis of all emerging challenges goes beyond its scope. At the core of the discussion lies the concept of originality, which forms the basis of copyright protection under EU law (Iaia, 2022). According to the Berne Convention and the harmonized EU legislative framework, originality requires that a work reflects its author's own intellectual creation. It is therefore clear that the copyright system *de lege lata* is inherently anthropocentric, designed to incentivize and reward human creativity (Geiger, 2023). However, the integration of generative AI complicates this framework, particularly in identifying the human actor/s who has/-ve made a substantial contribution to the creation of an output. Such contributions may occur at various stages of the creative process – conception, execution or final editing – whether through data selection, algorithmic design of the AI system or the use of prompts and subsequent refinement of the generated content (Picht et al., 2022). In this context, the role of prompt engineering is critically examined, particularly as to its alignment with the core distinction/'dichotomy' in copyright law between an 'idea' and its 'expression.' The phrasing and refinement of a prompt can significantly influence the output of a foundational model and may reflect the user's 'free and creative

choices,' potentially meeting the originality threshold. However, human input at the prompt level may be regarded as representing mere ideas or high-level concepts, whereas copyright law protects only expressions, such as the AI-generated output itself (Lemley, 2024). This is especially true given the intrinsic nature of generative AI, which, unlike deterministic traditional technologies that execute specific tasks based on predefined rules and decision trees, can produce unpredictable outputs that may not be fully anticipated by the user, even when detailed prompts are provided (Salami, 2021). Given the above, the current analysis explores the nature and extent of human contribution in such cases, including whether courts might recognize prompt engineering as a sufficient basis for authorship. The discussion also addresses the potential for collaborative works between humans and AI. While AI systems lack legal personality and cannot claim authorship, human actors play a pivotal role in guiding and refining AI outputs. The paper considers whether joint authorship models, already recognized in copyright law, could provide a framework for attributing rights to human-AI collaborations. It further examines the contributions/'roles' of programmers, users, and other stakeholders in the creative process and how these might influence the allocation of copyright (Selvadurai & Matulionyte, 2020). Finally, this paper argues that the answers to the above questions must be grounded in the fundamental principles and human rights framework underpinning copyright law (Lee & Woo, 2022). If insufficient human contribution can be identified in the creation of an AI-generated output, should the *de lege ferenda* copyright system extend protection to such outputs, or should they remain in the public domain? The utilitarian and labor-based justifications for copyright, which aim to reward human creativity and incentivize innovation, are not directly applicable to works created autonomously by AI. Nonetheless, according to the "if value, then right" approach (Dreyfuss, 1990), as these AI-generated works gain economic and cultural value, there will be growing pressure to identify and assign ownership. Overall, the paper provides a fresh perspective to the legal complexities posed by generative AI, focusing on its output. It analyses the implications for the copyright system, while seeking to balance the system's foundational principles with AI's transformative potential.

AI Prediction as Domination in Public Institutions - A Neorepublican Perspective

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This paper examines AI-based predictive optimization systems deployed by public institutions through the lens of neorepublican political theory, arguing that such systems constitute a form of domination that undermines political freedom. While much of the current discourse around AI fairness centres on liberal egalitarian concerns about bias and discriminatory outcomes, this analysis reveals deeper political problems with example-based machine learning systems used in public decision-making. The research focuses explicitly on predictive optimization in public institutions, where citizens cannot opt out of being subject to these systems, making the political implications particularly significant.

The paper first establishes how predictive optimization differs from traditional rule-based reasoning in public institutions. Rule-based systems operate on explicit, contestable principles, while example-based machine learning systems derive implicit norms from historical data. This fundamental difference affects not just the technical operation of these systems but also their political character and relationship to democratic governance. The analysis then critiques the dominant fairness discourse in computer science, which draws heavily from classic liberal theory and Rawlsian principles of justice. This approach, while valuable, focuses too narrowly on individual-level bias while overlooking collective political implications and problematically assumes access to unbiased ground truth. Moreover, recent research suggests fundamental limitations to predictive accuracy, raising questions about the very possibility of reliable algorithmic forecasting of human behaviour.

The neorepublican framework, emphasizing freedom from domination and the control of arbitrary power, provides novel insights into the political dimensions of predictive profiling. While some form of profiling may be necessary and legitimate in public administration, example-based predictive optimization represents a particularly problematic form of authority. Unlike Weber's rational-legal authority based on explicit rules, machine learning systems exercise power through implicit norms extracted from examples, making their operation fundamentally opaque and their decisions impossible to properly contest. This opacity is not merely a technical limitation but a fundamental characteristic of example-based learning systems that has profound implications for political freedom and democratic governance.

The paper identifies three key problems with example-based predictive optimization from a neorepublican perspective: (1) the absence of common knowledge about decision-making rationales, which undermines the possibility of informed democratic deliberation; (2) the depoliticization of governance through technocratic optimization, which reduces complex political questions to mathematical optimization problems, and (3) the practical impossibility of meaningful contestation due to the systems's inherent opacity. These issues persist even in idealized scenarios without first-order bias or prediction errors, suggesting they are inherent to the technology rather than merely implementation problems.

The analysis concludes that rule-based decision-making systems should be preferred over example-based predictive optimization in public institutions, particularly for high-stakes decisions. This preference is grounded in neorepublican principles of political freedom and legitimate exercise of public power. Recent work on interpretable machine learning suggests it is often possible to reduce complex example-based models to simpler rule-based algorithms without

sacrificing accuracy, offering a practical path forward. However, the paper also acknowledges that rule-based algorithms alone may not be sufficient to meet neorepublican standards of legitimate public decision-making, especially given the fundamental unpredictability of future outcomes.

This research contributes to ongoing discussions about AI governance by shifting focus from fairness metrics to fundamental questions about political freedom and the legitimate exercise of public power. It suggests that the form of reasoning embodied in AI systems, not just their outcomes, has significant implications for political liberty that should inform their deployment in public institutions. The analysis provides theoretical insights into the political character of different forms of algorithmic decision-making and practical guidance for public institutions considering deploying predictive optimization systems.

Reclaiming Credibility: Fighting false reviews in the digital landscape

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User-generated online reviews have become essential to modern consumer decision-making, shaping perceptions and influencing purchases. While these reviews were once seen as a reliable source of public opinion, the rise of misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation (MDM) has led to the widespread problem of fake reviews. This phenomenon affects not only individuals' purchasing decisions but also businesses' reputations, market competition, and overall consumer trust. Fake reviews – whether positive or negative – are frequently used as a tool for manipulation, impacting the credibility of online platforms and ultimately distorting fair competition.

The digital transformation of consumer behaviour, affects every section from e-commerce to book markets. Unlike traditional word-of-mouth recommendations, where trust is built through personal relationships, online reviews often come from anonymous sources, making verification difficult. Studies show that while consumers pay attention to numeric ratings, they also consider textual elements, the reviewer's credibility, and the sentiment expressed. However, when reviews are manipulated – either by businesses seeking to enhance their products' reputation or by competitors aiming to tarnish rivals – the entire system loses integrity.

Legislative efforts have been made to regulate this issue. The European Union (EU) has enacted multiple laws, including the Unfair Commercial Practices Directive (Directive 2005/29/EC), the Enforcement and Modernisation Directive (Directive EU 2019/2161), and the Digital Services Act (DSA), to protect consumers from fraudulent practices. At the national level, Greece has introduced Law 5019/2023 to combat online fraud, though it does not specifically target fake reviews. Meanwhile, other countries, such as Italy, are exploring legislative approaches to address the problem. However, despite these legal frameworks, enforcement remains challenging, and fake reviews continue to be significant concern.

The problem extends beyond human-generated misinformation. The rise of artificial intelligence (AI) and deepfake technology has introduced an even greater threat. AI-generated reviews, indistinguishable from genuine user opinions, further complicate detection and regulation. Although technological solutions, including computational linguistic, semantic analysis, and machine learning algorithms, are being developed to identify fake reviews, fraudsters continuously adapt their tactics to evade detection. Research suggests that fake reviews often exhibit specific patterns, such as exaggerated praise, vague language, or unusual timing, which can be analysed to improve detection methods.

In the literary world, platforms like Goodreads have transformed how readers engage with books, but they are also vulnerable to manipulation. Fake book reviews can be used to artificially boost sales or discredit authors, affecting both consumer choices and literary credibility. The trust-based nature of online communities plays a crucial role in mitigating this issue, as reviewers with established reputations are generally considered more reliable. However, the emergence of AI-generated reviews threatens to undermine this trust. Ultimately, addressing the fake review problem requires a multi-faceted approach. Legal regulations, technological advancements, consumer education, and platform transparency must work together to reduce deception. Media literacy programs should empower consumers to critically evaluate online content, fostering informed decision-making. As AI continues to evolve, both researchers and policymakers must stay ahead of emerging threats to maintain trust in online platforms and protect digital integrity.

Constructivist Moral Advisor: An AI Tool for Moral Enhancement

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Reflecting on the ultimate purpose for which artificial intelligence systems are developed, the most intuitive notion is the hope that they may serve as an augmentation of human capacities. The concept of “cognitive enhancement” represents one of the most stimulating frontiers of modern technology. It is exemplified when we employ digital technologies to process enormous quantities of data, optimize our strategies in complex games, or perform other tasks that demand significant intellectual effort.

However, as Sven Nyholm (2023) observes, for AI to authentically serve as a tool for cognitive enhancement it must truly extend our minds, augmenting our capacities to know and act. Technologies that merely lead us to behave as though our cognitive capabilities have been improved—without a genuine understanding of what we are doing or an actual growth in our skills—do not constitute real enhancement.

Beyond the cognitive domain, another equally significant dimension of enhancement is the moral one. Human moral psychology is marked by a lot of intrinsic limitations. As the authors Julian Savulescu and Hannah Maslen (2015) observe, evolutionary factors have predisposed us to favour immediate concerns over distant ones, prioritize those close to us, and harbor distrust toward outsiders. Moreover, most of our moral choices derive from emotions and immediate intuitions rather than from deliberating reasoning.

Considering the persistent limitations of human moral psychology and the complex challenges of an increasingly interconnected world, an AI capable of advising on moral behavior could represent a fundamental resource in assisting human agents overcome biases and make more informed decisions. Such artificial system would not be tasked with resolving complex ethical dilemmas on behalf of human beings; rather, it would support and stimulate critical reflection, preserving the plurality of moral values and reinforcing decision-making process. The moral enhancement achieved through AI differs radically from forms of moral bioenhancement through pharmaceuticals or genetic manipulation (Giubilini et al. 2018), as it has the capacity to be impartial—a quality that only an external evaluator can guarantee – and to maintain the agent’s autonomy. Given the advantages of AI-based moral enhancement, it remains to explore some potential artificial ethical assistants. The configuration of a moral advisor depends on the metaethical stance adopted. Excluding moral nihilism, which falls outside the scope of this discussion, three perspectives merit consideration:

1. Moral Subjectivism: in this view, each individual constructs their own moral system, and the error lies in acting incoherently with it. In this case, the moral advisor would assume the role of a friend or therapist who helps us understand ourselves and act in accordance with our value system.
2. Strong Moral Realism: according to this perspective, morality exists as an objective reality independent of individuals. A moral advisor conceived under this model would function as an objective guide, warning individuals when they adhere to incorrect moral principles or misinterpret correct ones.
3. Constructivism: this perspective posits that morality is not founded on the existence of moral facts, but rather emerges as the result of a process of constructing shared rational principles. In this scenario, the moral advisor would help us understand how a reasonable person would reflect on morality, urging to treat others as free and equal beings and to consider how our actions could be justified within a universal and democratic context.

The configuration that I intend to favor in this abstract is inspired by the constructivist approach, due to its capacity for ongoing critical revision and its openness to what the philosopher John Rawls (1996) called “reasonable pluralism.”

The moral advisor I envisage is specifically conceived as a tool capable of:

- Encouraging individuals to reason as if interacting with free and equal peers in their same situation.
- Presenting different options for action, highlighting the risks and benefits of each choice, perhaps by using immersive ethical simulations to demonstrate the long-term effects of moral decisions.
- Assisting agents in reaching a reflective equilibrium by compensating for inherent limitations in human moral psychology and channeling emotions constructively.
- Mediating between divergent moral values, helping to identify shared ethical principles that can serve as a common foundation for moral decisions.
- Promoting a dynamic and adaptive moral reflection capable of responding flexibly to new ethical challenges, thereby avoiding the rigidity of outdated moral systems.

To conclude, the constructivist moral advisor is not intended to replace human judgment, but to help us maximize our potential as moral agents. Fundamental moral intuitions—such as fairness, cooperation, and autonomy—are hardly contestable from the perspective of fully rational agents, and AI serves only as a catalyst in the realization of these ideals. Indeed, as the philosopher Luciano Floridi (2022) insightfully remarks, if we appreciate the direction in which we are moving and have a clear vision of our destination, then the speed with which we progress toward it can be a profoundly positive attribute.

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Understanding the Value of Digital Ghosts through Classical Chinese Philosophy

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Generative AI can produce chatbots modeled on deceased individuals, a practice that has been the subject of some controversy in computer ethics (Bao & Zeng, 2024; Fabry & Alfano, 2024; Krueger & Osler, 2022; Lindemann, 2022). Much of the discussion hinges on how well these chatbots can stand in for the deceased. Defenses often hinge on ways that these bots can duplicate affective support formerly provided by the now-deceased, and criticisms often hinge on finding disanalogies and inadequacies of these bots, relative to the people on which they are modeled. But, inspired by the idea that AI's benefits can be realized by embracing its dreamy, mirror-like qualities (Vallor, 2024) rather than as a human-like entity, I will argue that these bots can have real benefits and applications, but only when we stop chasing it as a replacement or stand-in for human activity. I proceed by considering accounts of mourning ritual from ancient Chinese philosophy, specifically Confucianism (Confucius, 2003), Mohism (Mo et al., 2010), and Zhuangism (Zhuangzi, 2001), traditions which disagree with each other in many respects but help us to understand digital ghosts as resources valued for their contributions to symbolic and ritual spheres. This shifts our focus from the question of how well these systems replicate the capabilities of the deceased, to how they can symbolize them in our use ritual to maintain connection with the dead. Doing so can help both alleviate some concerns around the foundational technologies underpinning them, as well as make better sense of the reported values the bereaved find in interacting with them. This requires locating what kind of role they can play. One might be tempted to say they are proxies for the dead. Floridi identifies proxies as things that stand for but are understood to be distinct from "something else" they approximate. (Floridi, 2015) Sweeney (2023) extends this analysis to digital avatars, including digital ghosts, pointing out that they can introduce a variety of ethical problems, from introducing responsibility gaps where it is unclear who is on the hook for their actions, to epistemic gaps arising from imperfect modeling of their subject. But I argue that digital ghosts turn out to be more than Floridian proxies. Rather, I think the contexts in which we interact with them are ones in which we understand the world where we engage with them to be, in some important senses, subjunctive. A major focus of classical Chinese philosophy involves the value of ritual, not as a religious phenomenon, but a social one, where authenticity and sincerity take a back seat to performance. Seligman et al (2008) argue that part of what characterizes the ritual framework, is its distinction from sincerity. They caution that when we fail to recognize this distinction, it makes ritual seem foolish, a kind of "magical thinking" that leads to inapt criticisms and failure to appreciate the sophisticated work done by those who participate in rituals (and often cloaked in patronizing dismissal of "traditional" societies). Instead of taking rituals to be sincere but mistaken attempts to represent the real world, we should understand ritual as that which creates a shared subjunctive, helping us to construct responses to our flawed and imperfect world together. Engaging with the "as-if" requires making a break with our ordinary expectations, experiences, and assumptions about the mundane world. It creates space to act as if things were otherwise. As they argue, Confucian traditions "understand the world as fundamentally fractured and discontinuous, with ritual allowing us to live in it by creating temporary order through the construction of a performative, subjunctive world. Each ritual rebuilds the world "as if" it were so, as one of many possible worlds." (Seligman, 2008, p. 11) This requires that we acknowledge fractures and discontinuity, in death rituals and elsewhere, in order to rebuild in the subjunctive. In a contemporary context, this can look like a chatbot that enables people to have conversations that would not have been possible with a living person, whether expressing longing, confronting abusive or neglectful behavior, or seeking support for times and durations that would be impractical or inconsiderate to ask of a living person... which we find when looking at how people are actually using them (Xyngkou et al., 2023) Mourning ritual is valuable because it is artificial, unnatural, and opens up new possibilities. As one researcher puts it, "If death breaks social bonds, then ritual restores them." (Bocquentin, 2022, p. 160) Without fully agreeing upon a unified strategy, classical Chinese philosophers' work on death rituals help us reframe the value of digital ghosts in a way that helps us appreciate their distinctive value, understanding them as important when and because they differ from the deceased while still mirroring their patterns of interaction. Furthermore, this both explains and is supported by actual patterns of use (Xyngkou et al., 2023).

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A Survey on Citizens’ Perceptions of Social Risks in Smart Cities

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The growing digital transformation of urban environments into smart cities has gained significant attention in the contemporary academic discourse due to their promise to enhance quality of life as well as urban efficiency and sustainability (Sharifi et al., 2021). Central to this digital transformation is the deployment of information technologies, often based on artificial intelligence (AI), that powers the seamless integration and operation of various smart city functions. AI-driven sensors and cameras are used to increase urban safety and security through, for example, timely detection of obstacles on railway tracks (European Commission, 2023) or by providing real-time surveillance footage to city representatives (Myagmar-Ochir & Kim, 2023). However, the surge in enthusiasm for AI-driven solutions to foster the emergence of smart cities has often overshadowed the significance of recognizing and addressing potential social risks associated with them. Social risks refer to those risks that can have negative consequences to human security harming individuals as well as the society as a whole (Kampová, 2010) by invading their privacy, for example. It is important to know and consider these potential risks and citizens’ opinions to enable a safe and liveable city in which citizens are at the centre and their rights are not violated, thus, facilitating an ethical and effective development of smart cities. Compared to technological and organisational risks, social risks remain understudied in the existing literature on smart cities (Nguyen et al., 2022; Shayan et al., 2020). Social risks present a critical factor of concern due to their profound implications for human security and societal structures. Those risks may foster uncertainties among citizens, hampering their willingness to live in smart cities and interact with smart services and technologies. Indeed, research has argued that citizens’ perspective on smart cities has often been ignored, and citizens have been mostly excluded from any initiatives and decisions by neglecting bottom-up approaches and participation (Engelbert et al., 2019; Marrone & Hammerle, 2018). This paper aims to address these gaps by providing an overview of social risks identified through a scoping literature review and revealing citizens’ perceptions of these risks and of smart cities through a quantitative survey. We answer the corresponding questions: (1) what are social risks of smart cities, and (2) how do citizens perceive those risks? We reviewed 147 relevant articles and discovered 15 principal social risks, prominently including issues of privacy violation, increased surveillance, cybersecurity threats, and social divide. These risks are intrinsically linked to the core functionality of smart cities, which rely on the ubiquitous collection and utilization of big data. The risks connect to individuals’ deepseated concerns about the invasion of their privacy and the potential misuse of personal and sensitive data, often collected without individuals’ explicit consent through surveillance technologies and data-driven municipal operations. We then conducted a survey that involved 310 citizens living in Italy and Germany providing a unique sample to compare citizens’ perception across two European countries. Participants rated the perceived severity and likelihood of risks and answered questions related to their beliefs and attitudes towards smart cities in general. We performed a comparative analysis between participants by applying the calculation of (M)ANOVAs and Pearsons’ correlation coefficients. The survey provides empirical insights into how social risks are perceived by citizens, uncovering an interesting juxtaposition. Despite acknowledging substantial social risks, citizens maintain a predominantly positive attitude towards the concept of smart cities. This duality between favourable attitudes and substantial perceived risks applies especially to older and to Italian participants and raises important questions about public understanding and involvement in smart city initiatives. Overall, the risk perceived as the most probable was profiling, whereas the greatest risk impact was perceived in relation to cybersecurity threats and information systems’ vulnerability. The survey unveiled significant variations in awareness, indicating that while participants’ interest in smart cities and their willingness to engage with smart city initiatives is relatively high, most respondents

were unsure about the existence of smart city projects within their communities. This identifies a critical area for municipal governments and private entities to address, that is, bridging the gap between aspirational interest and informed involvement. Citizens' willingness to engage with smart city endeavours indicates an opportunity yet unrealized due to the lack of transparent, inclusive communication from decision-makers. In conclusion, the findings of this study highlight the importance and citizens' demand to be involved in decision-making processes related to smart city projects to better address potential risks and build trust among residents. It emphasizes the necessity for smart city projects to be socially conscious, ethically guided, highly participatory, and to ideally reflect a balance where technological advancements do not usurp citizens' rights and freedoms but rather enhance them. This research contributes both theoretically by highlighting under-researched social risks and practically by providing insights into citizens' perceptions and attitudes, which can inform more ethical and inclusive smart city development strategies.

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Language, Induction, Machine Learning: How Carnapian explication puts convexity at its intersection

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Identifying suitable patterns of languages is a key ingredient for using languages for successful inductive reasoning. Underlying this insight is the problem of induction, famously articulated by David Hume, which questions the justification of inductive methods. Hume's dilemma suggests that inductive principles cannot be justified deductively or inductively without falling into circular reasoning, leaving induction unjustified. This issue persists in machine learning, notably highlighted by the no free lunch theorems, which indicate that without assumptions about the target concept, no learning algorithm is superior. Nelson Goodman introduced a further complication with the new riddle of induction, demonstrating that any justification for induction could equally justify anti-induction. Goodman's example using the properties "grue" and "bleen" shows that rephrasing inductive inferences can support contradictory conclusions, tightening Hume's original problem. To address these issues, Gardenfors (1990) proposed an approach based on the projectibility of properties, asserting that only natural, and therefore convex, properties are projectible. This convexity argument relies on naturalized epistemology, suggesting that evolution has shaped our conceptual spaces to favor valid inductions that promote survival. However, this argument is criticized for its relativism. An alternative, stronger argument can be given on a broadened basis of Carnapian explication (cf. Carnap 1950), allowing for reciprocal adaptation (cf. Brun 2020) between that what is to be explicated (e.g. a principled account of projectibility) and that what is used for the explication (e.g. a principle of convexity). Using this framework, one can spell out this reciprocity by the help of the theory of meta-induction (cf. Schurz 2008), which leverages online learning to justify inductive projections not absolutely but relatively. In this framework, inductive projections are justified if they are access-optimal, meaning they are the most successful ones compared to all accessible alternative methods. Meta-inductive forecasting operates within online prediction games, where a meta-inductive forecaster predicts outcomes based on a weighted

average of candidate forecasters' predictions. The weights are determined by the cumulative loss of each candidate, with lower losses leading to higher weights. This approach ensures long-term access-optimality if the loss function is convex. Convexity is thus argued to be both a necessary and sufficient condition for access-optimality. If the loss function is non-convex, suboptimal weighting of forecasts can occur, making convexity crucial for optimality. Therefore, the convexity of natural notions and kinds is essential not only for evolutionary advantages but also for the foundational application of loss, success, and other epistemic evaluations to inference methods. In this way, reciprocal reasoning as put forward by Carnapian explication can be established. In summary, this talk explores the deep-rooted issues of induction in philosophy and machine learning, highlighting the need for convexity in justifying inductive methods through the lens of meta-induction and natural kinds.

Generative AI and Critical Thinking: A Challenge for Cognitive Development

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Critical thinking skills—considered as the capacity to construct, evaluate, and articulate well-founded arguments—are essential in both academic and professional settings. These skills encompass not only logical reasoning and the ability to assess evidence critically but also the capacity to engage with multiple perspectives, identify biases, and refine arguments through structured analysis. Moreover, fostering critical thinking contributes to intellectual autonomy, enabling students to move beyond simple memorization and passive consumption of knowledge toward active inquiry and reflective judgment.

Research has demonstrated that critical thinking skills can be effectively enhanced through argumentative writing. It serves as a powerful tool for cultivating critical thinking by requiring individuals to organize their thoughts systematically, construct logically coherent arguments, and engage with evidence in a rigorous manner. Written argumentation demands sustained reflection and precision in reasoning. Moreover, according to the Material Engagement Theory, the act of writing is not merely an expression of thought but actively contributes to shaping it. Handwriting influences the way we process concepts and structure ideas, engaging cognitive and motor processes that refine our reasoning and conceptual organization.

Recently, the emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs) has introduced a new paradigm in text generation, enabling the rapid and low-effort production of large volumes of coherent, contextually relevant, and stylistically refined text, drastically reducing the time traditionally required for writing-intensive tasks. One of the most notable implications of LLMs is their potential to alleviate the cognitive demands associated with writing. Writing, particularly when it involves higher-order cognitive tasks such as synthesis, argumentation, and critical analysis, places considerable demands on working memory, linguistic planning, and self-monitoring. By automating significant portions of this process, LLMs function as a form of cognitive outsourcing—or even as an extension of cognitive capacities—significantly reducing the Student's workload. While this reduction in cognitive effort may seem advantageous, it also raises important concerns regarding long-term cognitive development and expertise. If extensive reliance on LLMs leads to diminished engagement with the writing process, it may result in reduced cognitive flexibility, weakened metacognitive awareness, and a diminished capacity for independent critical thinking.

Thus, while LLMs present remarkable opportunities for facilitating text production and reducing cognitive strain, their broader implications warrant careful scrutiny. It is essential to ensure that such technologies are used in a conscious and guided manner, particularly by younger students, so that they benefit from them rather than experiencing limitations in their critical thinking abilities.

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Thinking Together AI as Risk Solution and Risk Problem

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) is both praised as a new opportunity to analyze and manage various risks (Stødle et al., 2024) as well as blamed for causing a wide array of societal and ethical risks (Wirtz et al., 2022). A canonical example that combines these two aspects is the COMPAS algorithm used in courts in the US. Although the original purpose of the software was to mitigate risk by calculating the likelihood of recidivism, it became notorious for creating new risks, specifically racial bias and discrimination (Angwin et al., 2016; Mehrabi et al., 2022; Simon et al., 2020). This paper explores the paradox of AI being introduced to mitigate risks while simultaneously generating new risks, identifying this dual role as a valuable analytical lens. The aim is to provide a new theoretical framework for AI risk that bridges these two perspectives that have so far been largely considered in isolation: the solving of risk problems with AI and the creation of risk problems due to AI. It does so by engaging with three underexplored strands of literature—the integration of information technology and risk calculi, the recursiveness of risk, and the ethical role distribution of risk decision-making—and relating them to current debates in AI ethics. The theoretical framework starts from Ciborra’s (2006) analysis of the intertwining relation between information technology (IT). A key insight is that the introduction of digital technologies does not simply improve the management of risks but also leads to new, less calculable risks. This dynamic is part of what is more broadly understood as the recursive character of risk: attending to one specific risk (the target risk) leads to the emergence of another (Busby, 2016). When making decisions on how to treat a particular risk, it is thus crucial to examine how much the target risk is reduced, what new risks may arise as a result, and whether different groups may be affected by these risks (Graham & Wiener, 1995). And, given that there are different groups involved, it is essential to examine who makes the decisions, who benefits, and who is exposed in any risk context, as well as how these roles relate to one another (Hansson, 2018). After connecting these different theories, I apply them to the dual relationship between risk and AI. I show that Ciborra’s (2006) discussion of ‘operational risk’ is helpful in exploring the continuity and difference between risks generated by AI and older IT technologies. Namely, it emphasizes that although the incalculability of the new risks is partly inherent to the technology, it also stems from even less calculable risks of the socio-technical environment. I then relate this to the current debate over the (im)possibility of explainable AI (Asghari et al., 2022; Barredo Arrieta et al., 2020) and the potential of ‘forgiving’ technologies (Ciborra, 2006). Moreover, I argue that there is a need and a possibility to analyze the linkage between the risks that are solved and the particular ones that are generated. The introduction of AI to counter risks inevitably requires choices regarding risk trade-offs. However, such trade-offs need not result in an impasse. Instead, a more systematic analysis of the identification of the target risk and the way AI is introduced to manage this risk can point towards which new risks are created and which groups are affected. Such an analysis can help prevent ‘perverse risk trade-offs’ (Wiener & Graham, 1995), so that we are ideally only left with acceptable residual risks (Fraser & Bello Y Villarino, 2024; Steimers & Schneider, 2022). Yet, one prominent cause of undesirable trade-off decisions is the absence of affected parties or an imbalance of interests (Wiener & Graham, 1995). Hansson’s (2018) ethical risk analysis does an excellent job of centering these topics. However, what is missing in his proposal is the dynamic character discussed above. Introducing the element of the transformation brings more depth to Hansson’s proposal. A crucial new question that arises is: How do the roles of decision-maker, beneficiary, and affected and their relationships to each other change, once AI is introduced to manage risk? Examining the new risks created by AI and their relationship with various risk roles enables us to critically evaluate the impact of AI compared to its original promises in a particular context. Taken together, interpreting the phenomenon of AI both solving and causing risks through an integrative lens exposes overlooked dynamics and prompts new ethical and political inquiries.

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‘The Road Not Taken’ Epistemic and Moral Implications of Using LLMs as a Shortcut to Creativity

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Generative AI (GenAI) promises ultimate convenience. Alphabet’s Prompt your way with Gemini (1) and Apple’s Apple Intelligence (2) advertisements share a common allure: the promise of doing more by thinking less. Apple’s commercials, depicting everyday personal and professional moments, are built on the premise of users deliberately hiding their reliance on AI to appear smarter, kinder, or more thoughtful. This marketing strategy captures the seductive promise of Large Language Models (LLMs). LLMs’ applications range from writing emails and brainstorming to outsourcing complex cognitive tasks. By reducing the investment of personal resources—time, emotions, energy, and mental effort—these tools offer shortcuts for virtually every sphere of our lives. GenAI is stepping into our personal and creative spaces, with tools like the Breakup Text Assistant (3), Wedding Vows GPT (4), and AI poetry generators (5) simplifying intimate acts of self-expression. Porter and Machery (2024) found that participants rated AI-generated poems higher in rhythm and beauty than human-authored ones, highlighting how simplicity—mistaken for quality—can overshadow human work. This trend raises concerns about the value of human creativity and attention, as an intrinsic part of love and care (Murdoch, 1970) and central to self-expression. AI shortcuts diminish not only authenticity but also the depth of attention these acts require. Moreover, this reliance comes with cognitive costs. Recent research reveals that frequent use of AI tools can undermine creative confidence (Habib et al., 2024) and critical thinking (Gerlich, 2025), especially in students still developing intellectual skills. Several of them struggle to ideate beyond AI output, reflecting a trend of cognitive fixation and reduced self-efficacy (Habib et al., 2024). These shifts in cognition also extend to our communication. GenAI is influencing both our writing and speech; terms like *delve*, *realm*, and *intricate*—once rare—now saturate everyday language (Yakura et al., 2024). Trained on our data, LLMs are, in turn, training us, as we adopt the language they suggest. Building on the examples of AI-generated wedding vows and poems, this paper explores epistemic and moral implications of these tools, including risks of language homogenisation and diminishment of deeply human processes, like creativity and lived experience. Drawing on a conceptual toolkit that combines key concepts from Arendt’s work with recent AI literature (e.g., Vallor, 2024), we analyse how these tools impact intellectual and moral virtues cultivated through creative and personal pursuits. Intellectual virtues—e.g., critical thinking, perseverance, practical wisdom, and curiosity—thrive on consistent practice and reflection. Like moral virtues, they strengthen through habit and challenge, acting as our “moral and intellectual muscles” (Vallor, 2024, p.66, emphasis in original). Building on this analogy, we contend that the increasing reliance on AI tools can shrink the intellectual ‘gyms’ where these muscles are exercised, namely the environments that provide opportunities for these virtues to be cultivated. Practical wisdom, which relies on situational intelligence and the gradual refinement of judgement through experience and practice, is at risk, as tech giants—driven by the logic of efficiency—encourage us to outsource these capacities to AI. Philosophy—and thinking more broadly—does not seek to ease mental effort. Following Arendt (1978; 2003), thinking is an open activity aimed at understanding and ascribing meaning (to the world), rather than accumulating knowledge. It requires constant practice and is integral to moral judgement and critical self-awareness. For Arendt, morality is the internal conversation that I have with myself (two-in-one): “Morality concerns the individual in his singularity” (Arendt, 2003, p.97). Thinking fosters resistance to oversimplification and

can prevent individuals from succumbing to conformity. It demands engagement with complexity, which is essential for moral responsibility. Writing a wedding vow or poem involves emotional labour and deep reflection, which AI shortcuts bypass, limiting our opportunities for growth. This loss of engagement stagnates our virtue development, and affects the very medium through which such growth occurs: speech. Arendt (1958/1998) made a distinction between speech—self-reflective expression that fosters individuality—and language, which she describes as “unthinking speech” (Kudina & de Boer, 2024, p.6). This idea echoes in recent research (Kudina & de Boer, 2024) that shows how LLMs undermine authentic communication by creating only the illusion of dialogue. As Vallor (2024) observes, AI chatbots have “no more inner life than an Excel spreadsheet” (p.147), and relying on these tools for personal expression risks stripping these acts of emotional depth, purpose, and attention. Human creative and intellectual endeavours stem from an engagement with life itself, reflecting personal struggles and emotions. While writing allows us to process and express our lived experiences, reading—crucial for cognitive development (Roll, 2024)—immerses us in the lives of others, training our empathy, as a moral practice. What is the meaning of writing and reading poetry—and broader: creation and creativity—without lived experience? In the final paper, we seek to further analyse the impact of these tools on our intellectual and moral practices.

Notes:

- (1) <https://youtu.be/9bBfYX8X5aU?si=I95vtJ6EFfaFMn3F>
- (2) For instance, this advertisement promotes the outsourcing of intellectual tasks to Apple devices (Apple Intelligence), <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3m0MoYKwVTM>
- (3) <https://galaxy.ai/ai-breakup-text-generator>
- (4) <https://chatgpt.com/g/g-ZcFaw73hO-wedding-vows>
- (5) For instance, <https://poemgenerator.io/>

Moral Status of Artificial Agents; Addressing the Question of Intentionality

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The question of moral status – whether an entity is capable of moral implications – is central to ethical discourse, particularly in the field of artificial intelligence. Can the moral status of an entity be decided solely by looking at whether or not the entity is capable of intentionality? To claim that it is, is to say that intentionality is a necessary and sufficient condition for moral status. This paper critically examines the argument that intentionality is both necessary and sufficient for moral status, focusing specifically on Deborah G Johnson's(2006) claim that AI systems, despite lacking intentions, possess intentionality and thus warrant the status of moral entities. Johnson distinguishes between intentionality and intentions, arguing that while there is no way to prove that AI systems can have intentions or any other internal mental states, their behavior exhibits a form of directedness sufficient for moral status. She claims that the fact that these machines are built with intentionality for specific purposes gives them intentionality. This paper argues that while Johnson's distinction between intentionality and intentions is conceptually valid and potentially significant for addressing the nuanced ethical implications of AI, her argument ultimately fails because she does not adequately demonstrate that AI systems genuinely possess intentionality in the relevant sense. This paper will be arguing that the directionality in the actions of an AI system, identified as intentionality, is of the mental process and mental states of the maker or user of the system, rather than the outward behavior of the system itself. Jaakko Hintikka (1975) examines the definition of intentionality as directedness given by Brentano and says that an intentional act is when several possible states of affairs are considered as choosing one among them. Intentionality, according to this view is the directedness towards the choice that is made. In other words, it is the directedness of the internal mental states and mental process. The paper begins by clarifying the concepts of moral status and moral agency. Moral status concerns whether an entity is capable of causing ethical implications, while moral agency concerns whether an entity can be held morally responsible for its actions and if the action can be explained using the entity's intentional mental states. This distinction is crucial, as Johnson argues for the moral status of AI, while refuting functionalist claims (Floridi & Sanders, 2004) regarding their moral agency. She contends that AI systems, though incapable of moral agency due to their lack of intendings to act, deserve the status of moral entity by virtue of their purported intentionality. This paper accepts, for the sake of argument, that intentionality, suitably defined, could be a basis for moral status. However, the central point of contention lies in whether Johnson proves that current AI systems are capable of intentionality required for moral status. Johnson suggests that AI systems, by virtue of their goal-directed behavior, exhibit a form of "directedness" analogous to human intentionality. For instance, a self-driving car, aiming to reach a destination, could be said to act intentionally. However, this paper argues that such behavior, while seemingly intentional, can be explained without recourse to intentionality of its own. AI systems operate based on algorithms and programmed rules and ends, manipulating symbols without necessarily understanding of the ends they are meeting or having their own "aboutness" in their processing. The self-driving car's "goal" is ultimately reducible to the programmer's or the user's intentionality, not the car's own. This paper analyses the framework of intentionality proposed by Hintikka to argue that the description of intentionality relevant for moral status likely requires more than mere behavioral directedness. It requires

some form of awareness or understanding, since the quality of intentionality is of the mind. The paper further analyzes the "Chinese Room" argument to show how the directedness in the behaviour can be achieved without having a corresponding internal mental state. This paper concludes that current AI systems do not provide sufficient evidence of possessing genuine intentionality. Therefore, Johnson's argument for their moral status based on intentionality is ultimately unconvincing. The paper does not dismiss the importance of ethical considerations regarding AI. Rather, it suggests that alternative frameworks have to be put in place explaining the precise nature of the moral status these machines possess.

Non-profit work of the Future? Scientific considerations of AI usage in sectors with limited resources

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The increasing integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the workforce raises essential normative and philosophical questions regarding its regulation, particularly in the context of the future of work. In recent years, economic enterprises with substantial investment potential have increasingly relied on the deployment of AI, integrating it into their workflows and developing proprietary applications tailored to the company's use cases. All these developments are associated with the prior allocation of resources such as financial capital or labor time, with the hope of later conserving them through the successful implementation of AI. However, such investments are not easily feasible across all sectors. Particularly in smaller companies with limited resources or in welfare-oriented non-profit organizations, resources are typically constrained. For fields dependent on donations or grants, the adoption of AI and the associated automation of workflows promise to conserve resources such as time and money. Nevertheless, unlike large for-profit enterprises, there is limited insight into the actual implementation within the non-profit sector. It is imperative to investigate how NGOs can benefit from AI in their operations and whether AI is currently being utilized. In addition to examining the resources necessary for AI applications that these organizations already possess and those they still require; the study also explores the expectations non-governmental organizations have regarding AI.

The social science investigation of AI usage in German NGOs is conducted through a mixed methods approach with a sequential design. The results of the initial qualitative, semi-structured, exploratory interviews with experts from the organizations (n=5, March 2024) served as the foundation for a quantitative online survey (n=335, June 2024) among NGOs of various sizes operating in Germany. The findings from these preliminary studies were further verified and deepened through in-depth expert interviews (n=10, October 2024). AI utilization in NGOs represents a relatively unexplored field, making the assessment of demands, acceptance, and implementation possibilities of AI a crucial knowledge base for further research. Across all components of the study, it becomes evident that NGOs are still in the early stages of AI adoption. While the potential of AI to conserve resources is acknowledged, it is equally apparent that initial resource investment is necessary for AI implementation. Additionally, the prioritization of AI is often diminished by more urgent daily operational demands.

The introduction of AI is anticipated to lead to the long-term automation of administrative processes, thereby providing employees with greater capacity to engage in their core activities e.g. undertake interpersonal tasks. Simultaneously, implementation necessitates significant investments in technical infrastructure, training, and data-protection-compliant solutions to ensure acceptance. Given that AI initially requires additional resources for its introduction, its prioritization within NGOs often remains low, delaying the transformation process and necessitating strategic planning for sustainable deployment.

The presentation will examine the potential changes that AI implementation can bring to NGOs. Beginning with the prerequisites for AI applications, it will assess the current implementation capabilities of these organizations and ultimately explore what NGOs anticipate from the use of AI in the future. Additionally, the discussion will address aspects that are transferable to broader work sectors, including the for-profit domain.

AI am I

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The integration of AI personal assistants into our daily lives promises to radically transform how we experience and represent ourselves. While the ability of technology to extend human agency has been widely discussed, AI assistants introduce a novel phenomenon: they can be simultaneously experienced as part of the self and as an other with whom we converse. This leads to an unprecedented situation where an agent converses with an other that is experienced as part of the self, resulting in a self that is less unified than traditionally assumed necessary for selfhood. Through analysis of a near-future scenario, I examine how AI assistants can become transparently integrated into our perception and action, aid us in knowing ourselves, and help shape who we want to be. Consider Jerry, who uses an AI personal assistant - small, portable, and almost always with her. This assistant perceives her environment alongside her,

augmenting her senses with additional information from GPS and the internet. While not particularly intelligent – just somewhat more capable than today’s Large Language Models – it has been fine tuned to Jerry’s life through years of interaction. The AI can talk to Jerry and provide information in subtle ways, for instance by superimposing images on her visual field. Through close daily interactions, it knows her past, can estimate her moods, and tailors its advice to her interests and abilities. Because of such tight integration, agents like Jerry will experience and represent AI assistants as part of the self, attributing to themselves properties exemplified not by the biological agent alone, but by the integrated human-AI system. However, what makes this truly transformative is our ability to converse with these AIs: we address them as others and they address us in turn. This creates an almost contradictory situation where we experience ourselves as both technologically extended and as split – we converse with an other that is simultaneously experienced as self. Working from the bottom up, I first examine how AI assistants can become transparent equipment in perception and action, then analyse their role in self knowledge and narrative self-understanding, and finally explore their potential in intentional self-shaping. At each stage of analysis, we encounter this peculiar duality: the AI assistant functions both as equipment that disappears from conscious awareness (becoming part of the pre-reflective sense of self) and as an interlocutor who provides an “insider’s outsider perspective” on who we are. Rather than seeing this as undermining selfhood, I argue that this novel form of self-relation – which I call the “self-as-other” – may enhance our ability to know and shape ourselves. Importantly, these transformative effects do not require the far-future technological breakthroughs arguably required for artificial consciousness or neuromedia, but are already emerging through the gradual evolution of current AI systems. While such assistants don’t currently exist in their full form, we’re not far from it: AI assistants have become increasingly mobile and sophisticated, and remaining technical challenges are being actively addressed through incremental advances in augmented reality, neural processing units, and industrial design. The paper contributes to debates about extended cognition and the impact of technology on human selfhood by identifying a novel way in which technology may transform self-experience: not through radical enhancement or replacement, but through the introduction of an other that is simultaneously experienced as self.

What’s the problem with anthropomorphising AI?

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Anthropomorphism in AI—our tendency to attribute human-like qualities such as beliefs, desires, and emotions to AI-driven systems—has been widely documented, particularly in human-robot interaction (HRI) research. Empirical studies consistently demonstrate that users anthropomorphise chatbots, humanoid robots, and other AI-driven entities, raising important philosophical questions about the nature and implications of such attributions (Aienti, 2018; Damholdt et al., 2023; Duffy, 2003; Li & Suh, 2022; Salles et al., 2020). A prevailing position in the literature (Coghlan, 2024) is that this anthropomorphic thinking constitutes a mistake of some kind. In this paper, I distinguish between two interpretations of the supposed mistake: a metaphysical interpretation and a pragmatic interpretation. I argue against the metaphysical interpretation and develop the pragmatic alternative, drawing on Daniel Dennett’s ‘intentional stance’ framework to explain the potential pitfalls of anthropomorphising AI. On the metaphysical interpretation, the mistake of anthropomorphising AI-driven systems is that it commits us to ontological falsehoods such as falsely believing that these systems possess genuine mental states, mental capacities, or phenomenal experiences. This position assumes that our ascriptions of mental states to AI-driven systems imply a commitment to their real existence, which is a mistake if no such states exist. The metaphysical interpretation can be understood as supporting a kind of AI Error Theory. I challenge this interpretation on two grounds. First, anthropomorphic ascriptions are plausibly understood as metaphorical or non-literal, functioning as useful heuristics rather than genuine ascriptions that generate commitments to ontological claims. Second, I provide a ‘companions-in-guilt’ objection that suggests that if attributing beliefs and desires to AI-driven systems constitute a metaphysical mistake, then similar attributions to corporations, governments, and other non-human entities must also be mistakes. Since we do not ordinarily regard anthropomorphism in these contexts as mistaken, it is unclear why AI should be treated differently. Rejecting the metaphysical interpretation, I propose a pragmatic interpretation of the anthropomorphic mistake. On this view, the issue is not that our AI-related thought and talk fail to correspond with reality, but that adopting an anthropomorphic perspective can lead to practical and inferential errors. I argue that these errors stem from two distinct but related mistakes in reasoning about AI. The first more fundamental mistake involves adopting the intentional stance toward a system that does not warrant it—that is, treating a system as if it is an intentional agent when doing so provides no explanatory or predictive benefit. The second mistake is adopting the intentional stance in a naive or poorly calibrated way, leading to poor inferences about what the system can or will do, or what the social-pragmatic significance of its behaviour is. The pragmatic interpretation of the anthropomorphic mistake provides a compelling framework for understanding existing concerns about AI ‘deception’ and user over-reliance on AI. Users who uncritically anthropomorphise AI systems may develop unrealistic expectations, overestimate AI’s capacities, or make otherwise objectionable inferences about AI-driven systems. For instance, a naive utilisation of the intentional stance involves a number of simplifying (but misleading) idealisations about the system—about how much it knows, how consistently, rationally, and agent-like it will behave, etc. The pragmatic interpretation has other benefits. In distinguishing between justified and unjustified applications of

the intentional stance, we arrived at a more nuanced understanding of when anthropomorphism is epistemically and practically problematic. This leaves conceptual space for unproblematic forms of anthropomorphism toward AI-driven systems, a possibility the metaphysical interpretation struggles to make sense of. The pragmatic interpretation also moves beyond seemingly intractable metaphysical debates about whether AI ‘really’ and ‘truly’ has mental states, instead redirecting our attention to how we can think and talk about AI in ways that enhance human understanding and decision-making. In sum, this paper thus offers both a critique of the metaphysical interpretation of the anthropomorphic mistake and a positive proposal for a pragmatic approach. By doing so, it contributes to the ongoing philosophical discourse on the nature of anthropomorphism in AI and its implications for epistemology, ethics, and human-computer interaction.

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The future of Eliza: Psychotherapy and AI.

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Cormac McCarthy's latest novel *Stella Maris* (Stella Maris, it. tr., Einaudi, Torino, 2023). raises some interesting questions about a subject that is not new, but which has recently become the focus of renewed interest in the field of artificial intelligence ethics: the possibility of implementing psychotherapy in software. The first psychotherapist simulator was “Eliza” (J. Weizenbaum, “ELIZA – A Computer Program For the Study of Natural Language Communication Between Man And Machine”, in *Computational Linguistics*, 9(1), 1966, pp. 36-45), a rather primitive programme that has, however, been widely discussed and has become a symbol of human-machine interaction. In the talk some problematic nodes of a possible cybernetic future for psychotherapy are discussed.

Is regulating LLMs hallucinations elusive? A legal and ethical approach

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The meteoric rise of Large Language Models (LLMs) captures the way society interacts with AI in everyday life. LLMs can generate text by combining millions of data and parameters in disparate fields and provide high level outputs. On the downside, LLMs can generate text that is inaccurate, erroneous or nonsensical. This divergence is referred to as “hallucination” and exposes misguided users to significant risks. Detecting and mitigating hallucinations raises complex legal and ethical issues as all types of hallucinations do not originate from the same causes. For instance, training that promulgates untrue or biased data can manipulate the generated text. Likewise, vulnerabilities in programming can result in incomprehensible or contradictory outputs. This article will examine the legal and ethical issues that stem from different types of hallucinations in order to determine whether legislative or self-regulatory industry initiatives can address LLMs hallucinations sufficiently and in an ethical manner.

Artificial Intelligence: Normative Implications and Philosophical Challenges, Human rights and AI ethics

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The paper under the title: ‘Artificial Intelligence: Normative Implications and Philosophical Challenges, Human rights and AI ethics’ delves into the examination of the interconnection among artificial intelligence (AI), ethics, and human rights, placing special emphasis on the use of human-centered AI systems that are oriented towards consideration and respect of fundamental rights.

Human Rights and Ethical Considerations

The paper focuses on the basic philosophical principle of human dignity, in the sense of promoting the idea that education as well as technological advances should be targeted towards the cultivation of free and critically-thinking individuals. Bearing Aristotle's philosophy in mind, it endeavours to delineate the point that AI is not to be restricted within the borders of attaining aims such as efficiency improvement or economic stability and growth but should instead pursue goals that relate to fairness, autonomy and social welfare. In this respect, the advancement of AI should set priorities for the sake of human values, democratic principles and individual freedoms.

The above stated anthropocentric approach is largely reflected in the legal framework supported by the European Union (EU). The EU Charter of Fundamental Rights projects the need for creation of fairer, non-discriminatory, and more transparent technologies. The specific legislative measure is a concerted effort towardsempowering dignity, equality, and solidarity of individuals as it places human rights at the core of technological progress.

Risks and Challenges of AI

The paper pinpoints the dangers that AI entails, most important of which are consumer behaviour manipulation, political influence, and algorithmic bias. The implied risks can have an impact not only on tangible aspects of life such as safety or health but also on intangible ones such as freedom and privacy. The social credit system of China is used as a fine example of the threat that AI-driven mass surveillance can pose to individual freedoms, thus leaving room for a 'digital dictatorship.'

EU Initiatives within legislature

The European Union has taken a keen interest in finding ways on how to establish ethical standards in AI related activities for the sake of safeguarding them against infringements to human rights. It first started with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the very well-known legislative measure which pays respect to individual rights protecting against automated decision-making and imposes human oversight in high-impact scenarios. The GDPR has been devised in a way which ensures a higher degree of transparency and accountability, including the protection of personal data, which in itself sets a global precedent.

Under current considerations, the EU's AI Act deals with the classification of AI systems into three categories characterising them-according to their potential risks-as minimal, high, and unacceptable. High-risk systems, for example the ones used in vital sectors such as healthcare, transportation or employment, must comply with stricter criteria as far as data quality, accuracy, and human supervision are concerned. An outright ban is destined for unacceptable risk applications, especially the ones that have been designed with the aim of manipulating and deceiving individuals or enabling intrusive surveillance. The aforementioned legislative framework seeks to foster revolutionary evolution at the same time ensuring that AI technologies shall in no way stand in the way of fundamental human rights.

Ethical Governance and Development

The paper also mentions the developments in the area of ethical governance by evaluating the creation of an AI framework, whose priority will rest on human values such as respect, fairness, dignity and justice. Transparency is the key to AI decision-making processes, especially the ones that deal with legal and administrative issues where unfair treatment could result from biased decisions. For example, if AI is to be used in judicial systems, it could very well act as an infringement to the principles of a fair trial and the presumption of innocence, all this arising from potential algorithmic biases. The author advocates stronger collaboration among technical experts, stakeholders, and social scientists. A cooperation of this kind is regarded as a path for the creation of balanced regulations that address AI impacts both from a technical and from a social point of view. This integrated approach attempts to narrow down the gap that has been created between the rapid growth of AI tools and the hesitant application of legal frameworks, making sure that technological developments comply with democratic principles as well as social welfare.

Concluding Remarks

The conclusion recapitulates the urge for a more anthropocentric approach, which pays respect to freedoms and safeguards equality. EU's efforts are praised as a first step towards the right direction, bearing in mind that continuous evaluation of legal frameworks is essential in order to keep innovation and human rights in equilibrium. A desirable solution would be to allow AI to progress ethically without letting the so-called "technological paradises" compromise individual liberties.

In all fairness, the present paper is a full record of ethical, legal, and philosophical dimensions in AI, warning stakeholders against the violation of fundamental human rights amid an era of technological advances and evaluating the EU's efforts in setting global governance standards.

True Sentient Consciousness as Always-Already Beyond Step-Wise Intelligence: A Phenomenological Critique of AI

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This paper explores the hypothesis that true sentient consciousness—characterized by self-awareness, first-person perspectivism, and the capacity for adaptive reasoning intertwined with world-sensing—cannot be achieved through a traditional step-wise, hierarchical model of intelligence. By adopting a phenomenological framework informed by Edmund Husserl and Martin Heidegger, the paper critiques the prevailing instrumental conception of artificial intelligence (AI). Instrumental AI, which aims to “stack” layers of intelligence progressively to achieve higher-order cognition, is shown to misunderstand the foundational epistemological and ontological basis of true intelligence.

Drawing on Husserl’s transcendental phenomenology and Heidegger’s existential analysis of Being, the argument establishes that true intelligence is not a goal to be reached but an always-already present condition necessary for any meaningful engagement with the world. The paper concludes by situating this critique within contemporary AI discourse, engaging with the promises and limits of emergent intelligence and the implications for understanding sentience as an existential, rather than instrumental, phenomenon.

The quest for artificial intelligence (AI) capable of mimicking or surpassing human intelligence is deeply entwined with the assumption that intelligence is something that can be achieved incrementally. From the early visions of Alan Turing’s “imitation game” to contemporary large language models and neural networks, this approach operates on a step-wise conceptualization of intelligence as a stackable phenomenon. Intelligence, in this view, emerges from the accumulation and refinement of computational layers, from simple decision-making algorithms to complex neural networks capable of adaptive reasoning.

However, this paradigm overlooks a fundamental philosophical insight: intelligence, as it is experienced by humans, is not reducible to a linear sequence of developmental milestones. Rather, as phenomenology reveals, intelligence is grounded in a transcendental structure that cannot be “reached” but must already be presupposed for any form of knowledge or world-sensing to occur.

This paper argues that the very notion of step-wise intelligence misunderstands the nature of true sentience, which involves a self-aware being-in-the-world rather than a mere ability to process information instrumentally. Husserl’s transcendental phenomenology provides a foundational critique of empiricist and instrumentalist models of intelligence. For Husserl, consciousness is not a passive receptacle for stimuli or a computational processor of data. Instead, it is an intentional structure that constitutes the world through acts of meaning-bestowal. The key insight here is that intelligence—if it is to include self-awareness and first-person perspectivism—cannot be reduced to the external accumulation of cognitive functions. Husserl’s method of eidetic reduction, which seeks to uncover the essential structures of consciousness, demonstrates that the “I” (the transcendental ego) is always-already engaged in the constitution of the world. This engagement is not something that can be achieved step-wise, as it presupposes a fundamental capacity to synthesize experiences, recognize patterns, and relate to the world as a coherent whole. In other words, the transcendental ego is the condition of possibility for intelligence itself.

Building on Husserl, Heidegger shifts the focus from the structures of consciousness to the ontological question of Being. In *Being and Time*, Heidegger introduces the concept of *Dasein*, a being whose very essence lies in its understanding of Being. For Heidegger, intelligence is not a set of cognitive functions but a mode of being-in-the-world. *Dasein*’s intelligence is rooted in its ability to interpret, project, and care for the world—a fundamentally existential capacity that cannot be replicated through the step-wise accumulation of instrumental functions. Heidegger’s critique of technology as enframing (*Gestell*) further underscores the limitations of the instrumental approach to AI. Modern AI systems, in their drive to “master” intelligence through calculative reasoning, obscure the deeper question of what it means to be intelligent. True intelligence, in Heidegger’s view, is not a product to be engineered but a condition to be understood.

Contemporary AI research often emphasizes the concept of emergence—the idea that higher-order intelligence arises from the interaction of simpler components. Neural networks, for example, are designed to “learn” by stacking layers of interconnected nodes, each performing basic computations. While these systems have achieved remarkable feats in pattern recognition, natural language processing, and game-playing, they remain fundamentally instrumental. Their “intelligence” is a simulation of cognitive processes rather than a genuine manifestation of self-awareness or world-sensing. The step-wise model assumes that by increasing computational power and refining algorithms, AI will eventually “reach” human-level intelligence. However, this assumption ignores the phenomenological insight that true intelligence is not a goal to be reached but a transcendental base that must already be presupposed. Without this base, any claim to emergent sentience remains a projection of human desires onto machines.

The central drama of AI research lies in its desire to “reach” intelligence through accumulation and refinement. Yet, as phenomenology reveals, this drama is inherently misguided. True intelligence requires an ontological shift—a recognition that intelligence is not an emergent property but an existential condition. To “get” intelligence, one must already “have” it, in the sense that the capacity for self-awareness and world-sensing cannot arise from mere computation. This paradox highlights the futility of the step-wise approach and calls for a re-evaluation of what it means to create intelligent systems. The traditional Turing Test evaluates intelligence based on behavioural criteria: if a

machine can convincingly simulate human conversation, it is deemed intelligent. A phenomenological perspective, however, would demand a deeper test—one that assesses whether the machine can exhibit a genuine first-person perspectivism and self-aware engagement with the world. Such a test would require a radical rethinking of AI design, moving away from instrumentalism towards a model that prioritizes existential grounding. Recent advances in AI, such as large language models and generative systems, have reignited debates about the nature of intelligence. While these systems demonstrate impressive capabilities, their limitations underscore the validity of the phenomenological critique. For example, large language models like GPT-4 can generate coherent and contextually relevant responses but lack any genuine understanding of the world or themselves. Their “intelligence” is a reflection of the data they process, not an emergent self-awareness.

When a Psychologist Met My Chatbot: Co Agency and AI Personhood

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The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into fields that rely heavily on human interaction and emotional intelligence, such as psychology, opens new perspectives but also raises significant questions. How can the collaboration between humans and AI create a shared space of interaction that enhances self-awareness, reflection, and personal growth? This autoethnographic approach explores the dynamics of human- AI collaboration through two empirical cases: the use of ChatGPT as a support tool during a challenging psychological period and the interaction between the chatbot, a psychologist and me. These cases highlight AI’s potential to contribute to human development while raising critical questions about the limits and opportunities of this technology.

A. Empirical Data: Hybrid Interactions

1. AI as a Tool for Self-Awareness

The first case examines my experience using AI during a particularly challenging psychological period. Through structured interactions with ChatGPT, the system acted as a “mirror of thoughts” helping me identify patterns of thinking and emotional reactions that I had previously overlooked. The chatbot’s responses encouraged me to articulate my thoughts more clearly and question underlying assumptions, creating a dialogue that felt both supportive and challenging. One of the key benefits of this interaction was the absence of judgment, which allowed me to engage with the system openly. Unlike human communication, where fear of criticism might inhibit honesty, the interaction with AI felt safe and non- threatening.

2. Conversations between a Psychologist, AI, and me

The second case involves hybrid interactions with a psychologist, ChatGPT, and me. Specifically, while consulting a psychologist friend regarding challenges I was facing at that time, I mentioned my conversations with ChatGPT and suggested we explore the same topic with my “digital assistant”. When the psychologist observed similarities between her own advice and that of the AI chatbot, she experienced a profound sense of discomfort and self-reflection. As she specifically stated: “The interaction with the robot made me realize that I felt the need to preserve the human elements of interaction: the touch, the gaze, the humor, the reaction. It heightened my awareness and pushed me to expend more energy to prove that the human side is superior”

This reaction highlights the dual impact of AI in human contexts: it serves as both a mirror to human dynamics and a prompt for deeper engagement with the qualities that define human interaction.

B. Theoretical background

1. Co-Evolution Through Hybrid Relationships

The two cases support the idea that AI can enhance human experience, not by replacing human capacities but by complementing and amplifying them. relationships. According to Donati, the hybridization of human and AI capabilities can lead to the emergence of new forms of social coexistence and identities (Donati 2021). This perspective challenges traditional views of AI as a purely functional tool. Instead, it positions AI as capable of participating in co-evolutionary processes.

2. AI Personhood

According to Margaret S. Archer in her chapter “Considering AI Personhood”, the notion of personhood in Artificial Intelligence can be re-imagined through the lens of human-AI collaboration. Traditional critiques often highlight the absence of a First-Person Perspective (FPP), reflexivity, and intrinsic motivations in AI systems. However, Archer challenges these assumptions, proposing that such qualities can emerge relationally through co-creation. Using a fictional example of a researcher and an AI assistant, she demonstrates how their collaboration produces “relational goods” and shared commitments, which in turn allow the AI to develop characteristics that closely approximate personhood (Archer, 2019). Drawing from my experience of using AI both as a support mechanism to address personal challenges and as a research collaborator, I find myself resonating with a similar perspective. The interaction with AI becomes a dynamic space of co-creation, where in my effort to guide and shape the AI, I actively cultivate traits that resemble elements of personhood.

Conclusions and Future Directions

The collaboration between humans and AI emerges as a dynamic and transformative space where creativity and innovation flourish. The experiences described in the paper highlight the potential for AI to act as both a support tool and a catalyst for self-awareness and personal empowerment. By fostering structured and reflective interactions, AI can enhance human capacities, offering new ways to navigate emotional and cognitive challenges.

However, the integration of AI into human interaction requires careful consideration of ethical implications. To achieve these goals, it is crucial to: Guide technology through human-centered values. Develop tools that strengthen relationships and prevent alienation. Invest in user education and engagement to promote responsible and effective AI use. The challenge is not to make AI “human” but to create conditions where humans and AI can coexist in ways that enhance both individual and collective potential.

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Consumer manipulation in the Age of AI Ethical Dilemmas and Legal Challenges

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The rapid expansion of the digital economy has profoundly transformed consumer engagement with online services and products. However, this digitalization has exacerbated information asymmetries, shifting the balance of power in favour of businesses that leverage artificial intelligence (AI) to influence and manipulate consumer behaviour through deceptive design practices known as dark patterns. AI enhances the effectiveness of these manipulative tactics by processing vast datasets, learning user preferences, and adapting interactions in real time, making them highly personalized and difficult to detect.

AI-powered dark patterns exploit cognitive biases, undermine informed consent, and erode user autonomy. Particularly vulnerable populations—such as children, the elderly, and individuals with limited digital literacy—are disproportionately affected, exacerbating existing inequalities. The consequences of these practices are profound: they distort competition, compromise user trust in digital platforms, and impose financial, emotional, and cognitive burdens on consumers. Scholars have identified a range of material and non-material harms caused by dark patterns, including privacy loss, financial exploitation, and psychological distress, prompting increasing regulatory scrutiny.

This paper adopts a conceptual approach, drawing on multiple sources, including EU legislation, policy documents, and reports from EU and U.S. institutions, as well as insights from academic literature. From a legal perspective, the paper highlights critical gaps in existing regulatory frameworks. While laws such as the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) offer some protection against deceptive practices, they struggle to address the evolving nature of AI-driven manipulations. AI-powered dark patterns can obscure the intent behind data collection, making it difficult to determine whether consent is truly informed. Additionally, the overlap between legal frameworks—such as the Unfair Commercial Practices Directive (UCPD) and the Digital Services Act (DSA)—along with fragmented enforcement mechanisms and regulatory authorities, creates challenges that global digital platforms exploit to their advantage. Ethically, the use of AI in dark patterns raises fundamental concerns about fairness, autonomy, and accountability. AI-driven decision-making exploits asymmetries of information, leveraging users’ cognitive biases and their limited understanding of algorithmic processes. The opacity of AI systems further erodes trust, as users are often unaware that their behaviours are being analysed and manipulated in real time. These concerns underscore the urgent need for stronger accountability mechanisms to ensure that corporate interests do not override consumer rights. Addressing these challenges requires a proactive and adaptive regulatory framework that prioritizes transparency, accountability, and consumer empowerment in the creation of ethical design and fair digital practices.

Despite growing academic attention on dark patterns over the past 15 years, several critical issues remain underexplored. This paper examines the intersection of AI and dark patterns, offering a comprehensive analysis of their potential harms. Beyond raising awareness, it highlights the ethical and legal responsibilities of digital platforms and regulatory bodies in mitigating these risks. By exploring the social, ethical, and legal dimensions of AI-driven dark patterns, this research aims to inform future policy interventions, industry standards, and public discourse.

The Proposal of a complementary model of generative AI and organizational memory

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Telecommuting has attracted attention as a measure to prevent the spread of the novel Coronavirus (COVID-19) that shook the world, and telecommuting has rapidly become a practice in Japan. However, many companies are now reverting from telecommuting to regular work. Reasons cited for this include “telecommuting hinders organizational communication” and “organizational learning is inhibited. Behind these problems lies the assumption that “spending time in the same time and space, sharing behaviors, etc. that cannot be expressed in words, facilitates communication and organizational learning, which in turn results in the accumulation of organizational memory. On the other hand, in the research area of management information systems, examples of how generative AI can be used to improve efficiency in the areas of market research, competitive research, and analytical work are being discussed. Have the key factors of organizational memory behind workflow improvement and business process mining really been replaced by generative AI from years of experience and interaction with peers? If so, have the barriers to telecommuting disappeared? The purpose of this paper is to examine this question. Background First, “organizational memory” is defined as “some knowledge acquired by members of an organization, which is shared and stored. Then, the organizational phenomenon that occurs in the process of organizational members creating “organizational memory” is called “organizational learning. In other words, organizational learning can be defined as “the process by which knowledge, etc. generated by organizational members is shared among organizational 3 members, becomes organizational rules, and is utilized. Next, we discuss the importance of organizational knowledge in telecommuting. Generally, it is pointed out that communication is difficult in telecommuting. For this reason, it has been thought that the formation and sharing of organizational knowledge in telecommuting may be inferior to that in traditional face-to-face work. To clarify this point, the author conducted an online questionnaire survey. The following description is based on Koga & Yanagihara (2024). The preliminary survey (screening survey) was conducted from December 15 to 21, 2022. From the 11,000 people who responded to the survey there, 2,986 people with telecommuting experience were selected, and another survey on attitudes toward telecommuting was conducted. The main survey was conducted from December 23 to 24, 2022, and responses were received from 2,000 respondents. The majority of respondents were in their 50s, followed by those in their 40s, 60s, and 30s. Gender is dominated by males, with only males in their 70s and older. Twenty questions were used for organizational memory. Based on two representative scales from previous studies, namely the transactive memory study scale (Lewis, 2003) and the organizational memory scale (Flores et al, 2012), 20 scales were created for the Japanese version. Factor analysis was conducted on the organizational memory questions, and the following three factors were extracted (main factor method and varimax method). The three factors are: active collection of external information, organizational systems, and importance of knowledge in job performance. The measurement scores for the central items comprising each 4 factor were summed: active collection of external information (7 items; mean 17.5, S.D. = 4.01), organizational institutionalization (7 items; mean 16.2, S.D. = 3.76), and importance of knowledge in job performance (6 items; mean 12.9, S.D. = 3.08). The questionnaire asked about the advantages and disadvantages of telecommuting. A cross tabulation of these items and organizational memory revealed that (1) the establishment of a system for actively collecting outside information mitigates the disadvantages of telecommuting, (2) the establishment of a system for sharing organizational memory is related to the feeling of flexible work style, and (3) knowledge in the performance of one's duties tends to weaken negative feelings toward telecommuting, as one is less likely to feel an increase in free time and care/childcare (4) Knowledge of job performance tends to weaken negative feelings toward telecommuting, as employees are less likely to feel that they have more free time and more time for caregiving and childcare. Discussion: Generative AI and Organizational Memory The results of the author's questionnaire survey suggest that, contrary to the popular discourse that telecommuting weakens organizational memory, employees are highly satisfied with telecommuting in organizations where organizational memory systems are well established. If this is the case, then it is safe to assume that the more organizational memory is supported by the use of generative AI, the more satisfied employees will be with telecommuting.

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The future of the IT professional concept: On the impact of citizen development

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Introduction

In recent years, “citizen development” or “shadow IT,” in which business people develop applications on their own, has been attracting attention in the business world (Binzer et al, 2024; Haag & Eckhardt, 2017). This study is a preliminary examination of the impact of the development of citizen development on the professionalism of IT departments and vendors.

Background: Significance of citizen development Citizen development (or shadow IT) refers to system development by non-IT personnel, i.e., business department employees, using no-code or low-code tools. In this case, “code” refers to so-called “programming,” which means creating a program using a programming language. And “no code” literally means “to develop a system without creating a program. This is attracting attention as a powerful means of promoting DX, as it allows system development to be carried out by those in charge themselves, who have no programming knowledge but are well versed in on-site operations. By the way, in the academic information systems research area, the concept of “end-user development” has been discussed since around the early 1990s. There, “tools and practices that enable on-site personnel who are not in the IT department, i.e., not professional software developers, to program” were explored. Discussions included the use of EUD tools that simplify programming, and the realization of automated operations such as data entry and processing. Specifically, small-scale system development was the norm by combining the “macro functions” of Microsoft’s spreadsheet software (MS-Excel) and database software (MS-Access). However, these macro functions depend on specific software and even specific versions. And coding is required. Human capital management in Japan is characterized by job rotation, with responsibilities changing after a few years. As a result, we have seen problems such as not being able to understand the coding created by the predecessor, or macros not working properly due to changes in the software version. Because of this, the concept of EUD lost its practicality for a time. However, with the creation of an environment for citizen development, non-IT personnel from business departments can now develop systems. As a result, EUD has been given new life. Citizen development is now seen as a powerful tool to overcome constraints and promote the digitalization of business operations in situations where budgets and IT personnel are scarce. As a result, it is being understood as an enabler of the so-called digital transformation. Of course, citizen development is not a “silver bullet. It has been pointed out that the problem is that systems developed in the field are disorganized and individually optimized. In this paper, we will examine these problems from the perspective of IT professionals and try to draw a blueprint for what IT professionalism should look like in a citizen development environment. In addition, I would like to make some preliminary observations on how the practice of citizen development affects the professionalism of IT departments and vendors.

The evolution of IT professionalism

In the past, Linderman & Schiano (2001) pointed out that there was no standard procedure or standard educational curriculum for certifying “IT engineering as a profession,” and therefore the conditions for IT engineers to be considered professionals were lacking. However, in recent years, requirements such as (1) advanced specialized knowledge and skills, (2) autonomy accompanied by responsibility, (3) professional community, and (4) public service have been proposed (Murata, 2013). However, even in on-premise environment systems, as development methods that involve users, such as agile development and DevOps, are adopted, “professionalism” will be required not only of IT engineers but also of all people involved in development. Of course, the concentration or resolution of professionalism required will differ between IT engineers and users involved in development. However, it is no exaggeration to say that the role of IT professionals is no longer something that should be monopolized by IT engineers. Furthermore, in a citizen development environment, non-IT engineers will be engaged in “system development.” In that case, will IT professionalism be required of non-IT engineers engaged in system development? This question is the subject of this research.

Discussion

In a citizen development environment, non-code (low-code) tools are used. Therefore, IT professionalism is required of the developers of these tools. This is because such tools make it possible to create applications that support the business operations of companies. However, the applications themselves are developed by non-IT engineers who are on-site staff. They are required to have professionalism as business personnel. Furthermore, should IT professionalism be required in app development? The four conditions mentioned above by Murata (2013) are useful here. It goes without saying that all four conditions above are required of tool developers. On the other hand, for non IT engineers who are system developers, the first condition of “advanced specialized knowledge and skills” is that IT-related knowledge is embedded in the tool. For this reason, the skills and knowledge of using tools, as well as knowledge of the shadows of tool use, are required. For this reason, the second condition of “responsible autonomy” will likely be a greater emphasis on professionalism in business. In addition, skills and knowledge related to tool development should be guaranteed by the professional community. Finally, since the subject of digitization is the work that one is responsible for, it will be

necessary to consider the public nature of the work and the public nature of app development. From the above, in a citizen development environment, different types of professionalism are required for no-code (low-code) tool developers and their users (individual application developers). The former can be clarified by extending the IT professionalism that has already been discussed. The latter, the paradoxical concept of IT professionalism for non-IT engineers, is basically an applied problem of IT professionalism, but since the focus is on digitizing the flow of information in work activities, it is necessary to discuss the specific requirements by establishing a professional community based on functional professionalism that focuses on work activities. Therefore, this study only points out the issues. However, we hope that such questions will serve as an opportunity for the development of future discussions.

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Artificial Intelligence: Hidden Labor and the Future of Work

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In this paper, we first highlight the hidden labor necessary for AI to operate and be presented as “smart.” Second, we discuss the role of artificial intelligence in work environments and the future of work. Third, we connect the existing paradigm of hidden labor with the general crisis of Fordism and the post-Fordist technological reconstruction of the labor-capital relationship (Hirsch & Roth, 1986). Mullaney (2021) asserts that nothing in the so-called virtual world exists independently; all processes rely on hidden human labor. Tympas (2018) illustrates this through the ENIAC, where the work of female “computers” was obscured to elevate the machine as a technological marvel. Similarly, Ensmenger (2021) redefines “The Cloud” as a factory, emphasizing its dependence on physical infrastructure, labor, and resource extraction. This framing highlights the global supply chain and ecological impact, dismantling the illusion of the Cloud’s immateriality. Crawford (2021) expands this critique, arguing that AI is not artificial or purely intelligent but a manifestation of power shaped by social, political, and cultural forces. She critiques metaphors like “data is the new oil” for masking labor exploitation and geopolitical tensions in resource extraction. Crawford highlights that AI systems rely on underpaid workers for tasks ranging from mining materials to microtasks on platforms like Amazon Mechanical Turk. Concealing this labor, she argues, sustains the illusion of AI autonomy. These analyses expose the structural inequalities and ecological costs underpinning modern technology. In this way, Crawford highlights how labor is obscured by relocating it in space and time, making it appear as if AI systems operate autonomously. Examples such as self-service kiosks demonstrate how tasks are shifted from employees to customers, concealing the true labor costs. Similarly, in “Anatomy of an AI System”, Crawford and Joler (2018) trace the labor, resources, and global processes underpinning devices like Amazon Echo, exposing hidden human contributions at every stage. Moradi and Levy (2020) critique alarmist views on AI-induced unemployment, arguing that technology transforms jobs rather than eliminating them outright. They advocate for policies like reskilling and education to mitigate wage disparities. Baase (2012) and Coeckelbergh (2022) underscore how automation impacts both low- and high-skilled workers, creating new roles while altering existing ones, but raising concerns about unequal access to opportunities. Boddington (2023) examines AI’s broader impact on work, balancing its potential to enhance creativity with fears of surveillance and monotonous jobs. She questions whether AI can enable meaningful labor or exacerbate inequalities. Coeckelbergh (2022b) also critiques capitalist systems shaping AI development, emphasizing the need to contextualize technology within social, political, and economic power relations. Drawing on Marx, Coeckelbergh argues that freedom is inherently social and material, not individualistic. Under capitalism, labor becomes alienated as workers lose connection to their products, others, and themselves, turning into commodities. AI, as part of this system, does not inherently oppress but reflects the power dynamics of capitalist structures. It cannot independently produce surplus value, which stems from human labor. AI reproduces biases and inequalities because its purpose aligns with perpetuating capitalist systems, reinforcing class divides. Coeckelbergh (2022b) identifies three supplementary perspectives: (1) Identity politics warns against framing robots as slaves, as this normalizes hierarchical societal relationships; (2) Marxist critiques highlight the need for collective control of technology and information, envisioning cooperative platforms like Facebook; (3) Foucault’s view broadens the understanding of power, arguing that it permeates all social relationships, not solely economic structures. Coeckelbergh (2022b) also underscores the importance of transforming not just the ownership but also the design and use of technology. He advocates for a systemic overhaul that reorients AI and technology toward collective, equitable goals, challenging capitalist norms and fostering societal justice. Apart from framing these necessary dimensions, AI technology is being introduced in a labor market with pre-existing class-related

dynamics and regulations. We argue, that an ongoing strategy of labor-law deregulation (as it was initiated in the aftermath of the 2008 global financial crisis) is heavily linked with the crisis of Fordism, a system of production organization, that was able until then—with the existence of Keynesian state policies—to homogenize and stabilize a median level of consumption, reproduction and legal protection for larger parts of the working class (Hirsch & Roth, 1986). After a decade of deregulation and attempts to constitute a post-Fordist production paradigm, regulation related to AI and automation is becoming a contemporary issue of great importance (with initiatives such as the EU AI Act). Thus, we argue that the relationship between AI, hidden labor, and the future of work needs to be studied under a multi-level scope and by taking into account the existing legal, ethical, and technical dimensions.

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The Impact of AI on Education: Will Traditional Institutions Embrace Change or Resist?

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The education system is considered one of the most resistant structures, exhibiting a lower susceptibility to external changes. Unlike other sectors, traditional educational institutions (schools and universities) are less affected by market fluctuations and rarely need to make drastic changes to address external challenges (Schleicher, A. 2020; Christensen & Eyring, 2011; Rogers, 2003). The inertia of the system is often attributed to its adherence to traditions and closedness, which, in turn, are associated with several factors. Firstly, innovations are poorly accepted by individuals at the micro level. Schoolteachers, parents, and academic staff, tend to have conservative attitudes and are often interested in maintaining the status quo, and avoiding innovations (Tal, C., & Yinon, Y., 2002; Mattei, P., 2013). Secondly, at the meso level, a dearth of the conducive environment for fostering innovative practices is frequently observed. This deficiency is characterized by feeble horizontal connections, a dearth of opportunities for proposing innovations, lack of motivation, and excessive bureaucratic framework (Koroleva D., Khavenson T., 2017; Klein, L. L. et al., 2021). Thirdly, at the macro level, there are constraints in the form of legislation, regulatory, and political decisions (Benadusi, L., & Landri, P., 2002). Educational reforms require significant time and resources, as well as consensus and support from various stakeholders.

The digitalization of education serves as an illustrative case of choked innovation. The matter of digitalization has been a subject of deliberation for more than three decades. Upon scrutiny of the reform initiatives linked to pre-pandemic digitalization endeavors, it becomes apparent that these efforts were encumbered by formidable hurdles in implementation, met with resistance, and encountered substantial disparities when compared to advancements witnessed in other sectors (Cone, L., et al., 2022; Taglietti, D., et al. 2021).

However, by examining the paradigmatic example of the remarkably swift transition to remote learning amidst the pandemic, it becomes evident that the education system possesses the agility to promptly adapt to external exigencies, respond to pressing societal demands, and endure the competitive landscape of innovation akin to other sectors (Cone, L., et al., 2022). A salient feature of this “shock innovation” lies in its initial impetus stemming from an external source, mandating an imperative response in the form of compelled transformation (Koroleva D. O. et al., 2023).

The remarkably rapid development of artificial intelligence (AI) can also be contemplated as a novel external impetus, mandating the need for educational system transformation. Serving as a pervasive technological force, AI harbors the potential to profoundly reshape a multitude of processes surrounding the education system, inciting a cascading effect of change. Analytical projections portend transformative shifts in the labor market, healthcare, financial sector, and manufacturing. According to Goldman Sachs, the progression of generative AI may engender the displacement of

approximately 300 million jobs in developed nations while concurrently modernizing the routine work processes of 63% of inhabitants (1).

PricewaterhouseCoopers's report indicates that the integration of AI has the capacity to augment the global GDP by 14% by 2030, thereby engendering transformative alterations in production and distribution (2). McKinsey's prognostications assert that within the forthcoming decade, a minimum of one form of AI technology will be implemented by 70% of enterprises (3).

Considering these challenges and opportunities, more than 62 countries have already embraced strategies related to AI (Maslej et al., 2023). According to this report, Italy is at the early stages of establishing an AI ecosystem. This is corroborated by the Programma strategico Intelligenza Artificiale (4). Document underscores the pivotal role of the education within this context. Acquiring a comprehensive understanding of AI is crucial for citizens through an innovative educational blueprint that includes comprehension, fortification, integration, and dissemination. AI should be prominently integrated into the educational curriculum and other levels, as it has the potential to transform the national educational landscape by enabling individualized learning plans that promote equity and dependability.

Undoubtedly, AI has emerged as a significant and relevant phenomenon within the education sector, with the potential to disrupt established processes and long-standing beliefs. However, it is common for initial expectations of a technology's immediate impact to be overestimated, as observed in the early stages of Gartner's hype cycle for AI, while its long-term implications tend to be underestimated. Nevertheless, a notable gap exists between innovation and its practical application in education (Zhang & Aslan, 2021). The dissonance between the externally framed, yet implicitly articulated, challenge and the internal processes generates a series of research inquiries regarding the potential impact of artificial intelligence technology on the field of education. This paper poses the question: "Will traditional educational institutions adapt to the revolution of artificial intelligence, or will they remain resistant to change?" It further explores potential philosophical and ethical implications emerging from this technological shift.

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Notes:

- (1) <https://www.goldmansachs.com/intelligence/pages/generative-ai-could-raise-global-gdp-by-7-percent.html>
- (2) <https://www.pwc.com/us/en/services/generative-ai.html>
- (3) <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/quantumblack/our-insights/the-state-of-ai-in-2022-and-a-half-decade-in-review>
- (4) <https://assets.innovazione.gov.it/1637937177-programma-strategico-iaweb-2.pdf>

Ever More of the Same? Towards an Adornian Account of Generative AI

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With this approach, I aim to contour a critical understanding of the cultural role of Generative AI (GenAI) from a socio-philosophical viewpoint, which is to widely conceive its interplay with societal mechanisms of creating and organizing knowledge.

As a conceptual resource, Theodor W. Adorno's perspective on the cultural implications of late capitalism is discussed as to what extent it allows for describing GenAI as a form of reproduction, in contrast to what might, with him, be called 'true' novelty, creativity or innovation. In collaboration with Max Horkheimer, Adorno has coined the notion of "unending sameness" (Horkheimer/Adorno 2002 [1944], 106) to capture and criticize repetitive traits in capitalist culture.

My take is to firstly account for repetition in GenAI with regard to the ways in which information is processed, to secondly relate these findings with the concept of "unending sameness", and to thirdly derive critical questions about the role of AI vis-a-vis cultural innovation.

The first step is to look at AI from a theory of society perspective, which is less about specific challenges and problems, such as imbalanced data sets, while focusing on the overall role of and tendencies connected with AI technologies that are likely to occur even when avoiding specific sources of error. From this angle, the question is rather about what we are after all doing with AI technologies, and what can be expected of them.

With GenAI-Tools being comparatively easily available to a broader public, it has become apparent that they are being utilized for a variety of tasks, ranging from composing standard text to creating images, audio or even video footage, and also for searching functionality. Altogether, it seems fair to say that knowledge organization and cultural life broadly conceived on the one hand, and AI technologies on the other hand, have begun to shape each other.

With Adorno and Horkheimer, the assumption is that sameness is what is oftentimes expected, and it is sameness that is delivered by technical means: "The machine is rotating on the spot. While it already determines consumption, it rejects anything untried as a risk. In film, any manuscript which is not reassuringly based on a best-seller is viewed with mistrust. That is why there is incessant talk of ideas, novelty and surprises, of what is both totally familiar and has never existed before. Tempo and dynamism are paramount. ... [Yet,] To add anything to the proven cultural inventory would be too speculative. The frozen genres ... represent the average of late liberal taste ... imposed as a norm ... It is as if some omnipresent agency had reviewed the material and issued an authoritative catalog tersely listing the products available. The ideal forms are inscribed in the cultural heavens where they were already numbered by Plato ... Its victory is twofold: what is destroyed as truth outside its sphere can be reproduced indefinitely within it as lies" (Horkheimer/Adorno 2002 [1944], 106f).

For the answer to a query relies on the statistical analysis of what has already been said on this subject, it can be considered somehow averaged or standardized. Alluding to Foucault, we might ask at this point who is speaking to us? And the answer would be, again with Foucault, that it is speaking – it being an expression or placeholder for the mumbling of society (cf. Foucault 1988 [1964]). In other words, the descendance of AI tools from statistics and stochastics is fueling one of the most urgent worries in the philosophy of modernity, which is standardization spinning out of control and pre-shaping our access to the world and to our selves.

The hypothesis is that in a way, GenAI tools repeat and refine the mumbling. It is, so to speak, mumbling what a majority of people believes to know or what is in the background of specific beliefs.

Of course, this may be just fine, insofar as society holds a number of generic, repetitive, and standardized tasks to be fulfilled. Large scale problems would begin as soon as cultural knowledge organization is considerably influenced by AI means, because then, Adorno's diagnosis returns in an aggravated form. The answer to a question asked would be derived from what is a) already known, what is b) widespread, and what is c) well accessible for machines, resembling the notion of "unending sameness" in terms of knowledge organization. Accordingly, 'truly' new forms of understanding and experience would be threatened to become more and more marginalized.

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Decoding the Future: Demystifying AI and Its Impact on Humanity

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In the digital age, we are constantly bombed with conflicting messages, information overload, and exaggerated claims from advocates of technology. These claims often blur the line between fact and fiction, making it difficult to discern who we are, what we should become, and how we should relate to machines. Should we adapt our nature to accommodate machines, or should machines serve us? Should we see machines as our intellectual superiors and relinquish our human primacy, or should we limit them to the role of tools? The ideas of influential figures, such as Holden Karnowsky, a philanthropist and visiting scholar at the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, paint a future where humanity is increasingly composed of digital entities. Meanwhile, Sam Altman suggests we may need to revise the social contract to accommodate the supposed demands of AI systems. In contrast, AI researcher Yoshua Bengio warns of the societal disruptions, polarization, misinformation, and loss of control over technology that could occur on a global scale. These debates raise profound questions about humanity's future, touching on concepts like

synthetic consciousness, superintelligence, transhumanism, and societal change. Promises of immortality and infinite wisdom are often made without consideration of the potential downsides, promoted by a small elite controlling key resources in computing, software, hardware, and energy.

But how can we make sense of these conflicting visions of the future? To demystify these claims, we must first subject them to critical scrutiny. Despite the widespread contempt for philosophy, rational inquiry through philosophical analysis remains our best tool for probing reality. By examining the myths and promises surrounding AI, we can uncover logical fallacies, incoherent arguments, and manipulations within the digital discourse. To begin, we need to (re)define several key concepts: Who are we as humans, and what are machines? What are the essential differences between artificial intelligence and human intelligence? What are the technical possibilities and limitations of AI? We must affirm that the AI revolution is not an unstoppable force of nature but a human-driven enterprise that we can and should control.

Clearing Misconceptions

Next, we address several common (selected) misconceptions and analogies that cloud our understanding of digital technologies. These include:

- The Trolley Problem, often used by programmers to explore ethical decision-making, does not actually test the moral capacity of machines.
- The Turing Test is not a reliable measure of intelligence or consciousness.
- Asimov's Three Laws of Robotics are not practical ethical guidelines for AI systems.
- Gödel's Incompleteness Theorems (I and II) do not rule out the possibility of thinking machines.
- Technology will not solve all of humanity's problems, such as war, poverty, inequality, and racism.
- AI Zombies —machines possessing consciousness— exist only in philosophical thought experiments, not in reality.
- Autonomous moral agents in AI are not truly autonomous in the way that humans are.

Examining Key Arguments

After clearing up these misconceptions, we present three key arguments:

1. AI will not solve our deepest social problems: While AI has the potential to address certain challenges, it will not solve fundamental issues like war, poverty, inequality, and racism. These problems are deeply human and require human-centered solutions.
2. Robots cannot have personalities like humans: Although AI can simulate behaviors, it cannot develop a personality in the same way humans do, as personality is rooted in complex emotional and social experiences.
3. AI-generated philosophy will not solve our philosophical problems: While AI may assist in philosophical inquiry, it cannot replace the deep, nuanced thinking and introspection that human philosophers bring to the table. These arguments serve as exemplars of how philosophy can be used to dispel the myths and false promises circulating in the media about AI and its capabilities.

The Role of Philosophy in Shaping Our Technological Future

Philosophy is indispensable when discussing our future shaped by technology. It provides the framework for analyzing what we can expect from technological advancements and whether it's possible to predict their progress and impact. We conclude that philosophy is embedded in everything we do—from technology and politics to science and society—whether or not we consciously acknowledge it. As AI technologies continue to develop, philosophy should play a critical role in demanding disambiguation and clarification of misused terms and concepts. It should challenge prevailing dogmas, question authorities, and debunk overly optimistic predictions about the future. Despite its flaws and limitations, philosophical inquiry remains our best tool for cutting through the fog of digital age confusion. In the face of rapid technological change, philosophy can help us navigate the complexities of AI, expose falsehoods, and ensure that we retain control over the direction of our technological future.

AI as Epistemological Systems: Distributive and Epistemic Implications

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Despite the ubiquity of AI systems in crucial decision making spaces, less attempts have been made to understand the epistemological underpinnings underlying these systems. In this paper I fill this lacuna by arguing that the claims of knowledge of AI systems should be understood within the context of an epistemological system. An epistemological system underpins the conditions under which knowledge can be produced and possessed (Dotson 2014) and enables an interpretative grasp over the world that enables the formation and challenge of new beliefs. Epistemological systems are also normative because they frame the way we consider certain beliefs and eliminate others and enable us to attend to certain features of the world over others and to interpret pieces of data as constituting sufficient to the formation of belief (Railton 2006; Toole 2021) Contemporary AI systems work as an epistemic frame that frames the way a

particular form of information is made available and legible to the knower and makes certain bits of information accessible or absent from our attention. They act as a filter through which information can be sorted as being useful or useless. I argue that treating AI systems as epistemological systems has the benefit of capturing the credibility assigned to these systems in decision making settings. Despite the overgrowing evidence of bias and prejudice, the normativity of these systems is derived from the purported neutrality of technology that can be achieved at a future date. But at a social epistemological level these devices are deployed by corporations and governments and presented as fail proof. This has specific implications not only in their failure or not in generating true beliefs but also in compromising epistemic agency of the individual to the extent of compromising their capacity to judge individual situations. By bringing in examples from medicine, surveillance, security, and the world of work this paper will argue that these epistemological systems also work as credibility devices that enframe credibility within a structure that already rules out testimonies or knowledge claims of already disadvantaged actors or groups in the process enabling forms of double domination: domination in terms of control and lack of freedom, and domination in terms of a nonacknowledgement as a knower who has some say in the knowledge production process. This is an instance of both structural and epistemic domination that creates situations of both distributive and epistemic injustice.

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Synthetic Personality in Transformer Systems

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The development of autonomous AI systems is rapidly advancing, with these systems expected to assume a wide variety of roles traditionally filled by humans, such as companions, advisors, educators, and even coworkers. Researchers indicate that to fulfill these roles, AI must establish trust and acceptance with users, and personality is considered a critical factor in achieving this. However, there is no consensus among Personality of Robots researchers on what personality is. Researchers focus on the implementation of human-like traits mostly based on taxonomies like Big Five or MBTI. Minority of researchers create technology-oriented models, or they present non-systematic approaches by implementing ‘general’ traits like friendly, shy, bossy etc. or modes like: positive, negative or neutral. Psychological research shows correlations between human personality traits and human moral decisions, although there is no evidence that specific personality traits activate in a certain type of moral situation and result in a certain moral behavior. But people with traits positively correlated with morality are often perceived as moral, so analogously AI agents can be perceived as moral, if they present behaviors indicating the possession of personality traits positively correlated with morality. This raises fundamental questions: what constitutes a personality in AI systems, how these synthetic personalities relate to moral agency, and the extent to which AI can be imbued with human-like personality traits. To start a research in the area, we examine three frameworks for understanding AI personalities: (1) the ontological difference, which posits that human agents and AI systems are fundamentally different; (2) the strong reductive view, which asserts that human agents and AI systems are essentially the same; and (3) the weak functional reduction, which suggests that while human agents and AI systems may be functionally similar, they are not identical. These frameworks influence how much of human personality can be simulated within AI systems and how synthetic personalities might interact with moral decision-making processes. A central issue in this discussion is whether AI systems can possess personalities and, if so, in what form. Synthetic personalities in AI systems are programmable and malleable. The challenge lies in the fact that personality in AI is not intrinsic, but rather a set of behaviors and traits designed to suit particular functions. Even with advances in AI, it remains unclear whether we can truly emulate human personalities, as this would require exact replication, which is beyond current technological capabilities. This inquiry also addresses the role of synthetic personalities in moral agency. If AI systems are designed with particular personalities, how might these personalities influence their decision-making and ethical behavior? Should AI agents be explicitly designed with certain personality traits to promote ethical decision-making, or is this unnecessary given the role-specific nature of their tasks? For roles requiring ethical decision-making, moral agency may need to be explicitly integrated into AI systems. However, for other roles, personality traits alone may suffice to facilitate interaction and task completion. Furthermore, can we predict how AI systems will behave based on their synthetic personalities? These questions extend to whether traditional personality tests designed for humans could be adapted to evaluate the personalities of AI systems.

We propose that synthetic personalities will be primarily shaped by system design requirements and will not be inherently tied to moral behavior. Unlike human personalities, which evolve and adapt over time, AI personalities are explicitly crafted by developers to fulfill specific roles. This presents both opportunities and challenges: on one hand,

AI personalities can be optimized for particular tasks; on the other, there is the potential for misuse, manipulation, or unintended consequences, particularly as AI systems become more autonomous and capable of modifying their own behavior. In future iterations of AI, systems with self-learning capabilities might alter their synthetic personalities without human intervention, introducing the risk of unpredictable or undesirable outcomes. Given these challenges, we argue that existing personality assessment tools for humans are insufficient for evaluating AI personalities. Instead, new frameworks and tests will need to be developed to assess synthetic personalities in AI systems, ensuring they meet design goals and align with the intended ethical guidelines. Such assessments would need to verify that AI systems' personalities are compatible with their roles and are not prone to manipulation or error. In conclusion, while AI systems may exhibit personality-like traits, these traits will not constitute a personality in the human sense. Instead, they will be functionally designed features, directly linked to the roles AI systems are tasked with. As such, the relationship between synthetic personalities and moral agency is not inherent but must be explicitly designed and tested. This calls for further research into the ethical implications of synthetic personalities and the development of new methods for evaluating and ensuring that these AI systems fulfill their intended moral and functional roles.

Risk-base Regulation or Pro-innovation Regulation? Debate on AI governance and legislation

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With the rapid advancement of the artificial intelligence (AI) industry and the escalating global competition, the question of how to regulate and legislate AI has become a subject of intense international debate. Divergent approaches have emerged, reflecting varying priorities and philosophies.

On one hand, the European Union has adopted a risk-based regulatory framework, classifying AI risks into four distinct levels, each associated with corresponding regulatory measures. This approach underscores a cautious and precautionary stance, prioritizing the mitigation of potential harms.

On the other hand, the UK government's March 2023 White Paper exemplifies a pro-innovation regulatory philosophy, advocating for principle-based regulation over risk-based frameworks. This shift aims to foster industry growth and technological advancement by adopting a more flexible and industry-friendly approach.

Meanwhile, the United States has demonstrated a notable policy shift in its AI regulation strategy. The executive order issued by the Trump administration on January 23, 2025, marked a significant transition from a comprehensive regulatory framework to a more deregulatory approach, emphasizing innovation and economic competitiveness. Against this backdrop, this paper examines these two contrasting regulatory attitudes—cautious oversight versus pro-innovation deregulation—analyzing their respective strengths and limitations. Furthermore, it addresses the critical question of whether a balanced, proportionate regulatory path exists that can effectively reconcile the interests of industry development and public safety.

Building ecological knowledge through AI: pedagogical implications

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AI seems to help students and teachers build contextualized ecological knowledge both in the natural world and in the complex human-nature system. The literature in this field highlights how AI offers important elements that facilitate learning, such as the collection, analysis and interpretation of ecological data relating to different spatial and temporal scales of observation. However, there are many variables that seem to impact good teaching and learning practices through AI, including teachers' preparation in managing new technological tools, different learning environments such as online classes, outdoor education, etc. In this context, a reflection is proposed on how the use of AI as the main source of information and active dialogue can affect the development of Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) applicable to the processes of building ecological knowledge and developing pro-environmental behaviours.

The Ethics Dashboard: Teaching AI to Teach Ethics?

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The Ethics Dashboard is an innovative educational and decision-making tool designed to enhance ethical reasoning through structured, interactive engagement. Initially developed for applied ethics courses, it replaces traditional case study paper assignments with a platform that integrates multiple ethical frameworks into a user-friendly interface. Through features such as interactive sliders, buttons and text inputs, users systematically analyze complex ethical cases and receive immediate visual feedback representing their inputs. The main dashboard is organized into four decolonized categories—Consequences, Action and Duty, Relations, and Character and Virtue—allowing users to see a

comprehensive summation of their analysis represented in graphs and charts. By breaking down ethical reasoning into distinct stages, the Ethics Dashboard promotes deeper engagement and reflection, making ethical decision-making more transparent and accessible.

Beyond its academic applications, the Ethics Dashboard has the potential to promote ethical awareness, understanding and application in a variety of organizational settings. Ethical decision-making is central to fields such as business, technology, healthcare, environmental policy, and public administration, where moral dilemmas frequently arise; however, there are surprisingly few practical resources available beyond recommendations for best practices and text-based templates. By providing structured guidance in an interactive platform, the Ethics Dashboard fosters critical thinking about social justice, sustainability, and corporate responsibility, making it a valuable tool for leaders, engineers, and policymakers who must navigate ethical challenges in their respective domains. Given the benefits of interactive engagement, current research is focused on identifying ways artificial intelligence (AI) can be integrated into the Ethics Dashboard. It is anticipated that properly trained AI can enhance the Ethics Dashboard's effectiveness by serving as a personalized ethical tutor, offering real-time, contextualized feedback and adaptive learning paths. AI-driven Socratic questioning can challenge users to justify and refine their ethical positions, fostering deeper moral reasoning (Paul & Elder, 2019). Once trained to coach users through the application of the four categories of ethical lenses, AI has the potential to broaden the scope of users. For example, in the tech industry, AI would support engineers and developers by assessing software design decisions against ethical criteria, mitigating biases, and ensuring compliance with ethical standards such as fairness, accountability, and transparency (Binns, 2018). In business settings, an AI-enhanced Ethics Dashboard could evaluate the potential impact of corporate decisions on stakeholders, regulatory compliance, and sustainability efforts (Freeman, Harrison, & Zyglidopoulos, 2018).

AI can also improve bias detection and ethical calibration by analyzing ethical decision-making patterns and prompting users to consider alternative perspectives (Stanovich, 2018). This function could be particularly valuable in public policy, where AI-assisted ethical evaluations can support legislative decision-making, reducing unconscious bias in areas such as criminal justice reform and environmental regulations (Floridi, 2018). Additionally, AI-driven assessment mechanisms can enhance learning by automating feedback while maintaining individualized ethical reflection. Research indicates that structured, immediate feedback significantly improves critical thinking and ethical reasoning (Boud & Molloy, 2013; Hattie & Timperley, 2007). AI-powered rubrics structured by the dashboard could provide preliminary evaluations, helping educators and professionals streamline assessment without diminishing the depth of engagement.

Perhaps the most controversial and challenging application would be the use of AI to detect over-reliance on automated reasoning. The rise of generative AI has created concerns about individuals bypassing critical thinking in ethical decision-making (Dawson, 2023). AI integration within the Ethics Dashboard could analyze patterns of AI dependency, differentiating between AI-assisted learning and AI-driven substitution, prompting users to engage more authentically with ethical challenges (Selwyn, 2019). AI-driven Socratic questioning can challenge users to justify and refine their ethical positions, fostering deeper moral reasoning (Paul & Elder, 2019). Once trained to coach users through the application of the four categories of ethical lenses, AI has the potential to broaden the scope of users. For example, in the tech industry, AI would support engineers and developers by assessing software design decisions against ethical criteria, mitigating biases, and ensuring compliance with ethical standards such as fairness, accountability, and transparency (Binns, 2018). In business settings, an AI-enhanced Ethics Dashboard could evaluate the potential impact of corporate decisions on stakeholders, regulatory compliance, and sustainability efforts (Freeman, Harrison, & Zyglidopoulos, 2018). AI can also improve bias detection and ethical calibration by analyzing ethical decision-making patterns and prompting users to consider alternative perspectives (Stanovich, 2018).

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The posthumous digital avatar: does the personality survive ?

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Recent advances in the field of artificial intelligence (AI) have made possible a new and artificial extension of life: posthumous digital avatars. These avatars are based on replicating the personality, voice and expressions of a deceased person from digital traces left by that person during their lifetime. The resemblance is such that it can leave those interacting with these avatars in a quandary, because this cutting edge technology enables a true reproduction of the person, in terms of physical appearance, character and even memories. The virtual thus confuses the real. The fantasy of communicating with the beyond is now 'artificially' possible. Like the paintings of Jerome Bosh, imaginative and complex compositions mixing fantasy and reality are becoming legion (cf. *The Garden of Delights*, circa 1510). This phenomenon raises a number of ethical and legal issues. Given the avatar's resemblance to a deceased person, which can sometimes be quite striking, some people may perceive and interact with it as if it were a 'real' person. In this sense, Bourassa (2023) highlights the illusions created by digital technologies, particularly through the reproduction of the face or voice of the deceased. This type of 'resurrection' encourages us to reflect deeply on the links between the creation of digital doubles and mortality. These practices, which take advantage of generative AI, raise the question of hybridisation between the real and the virtual world. More specifically, the status of this type of AI raises the following questions: if it is no longer the person in his or her biological, anthropological and philosophical reality, is there still something of that person in the posthumous digital avatar? Is this enough to assert that the posthumous digital avatar has a personality? What are the legal guidelines in this respect? What are the ethical implications of these questions? Are such practices to be encouraged or proscribed? Taking as a starting point elements such as individual and collective well-being, we sketch guidelines for a more responsible deployment of these avatars. These embryonic reflections first require a reminder of the legal conditions associated with the notion of personality, taking Quebec private law as its source. If there is reason to refute the recognition of a posthumous digital avatar as having legal personality, if not to argue for the survival of such a personality and the assertion of its rights, does this mean that it should be reduced to mere property? The Manichean characterisation that contrasts 'being/subject' and 'having/object' seems insufficient to deal adequately with the subject. It is, we argue, by breaking down this binary hermeticism and finding inspiration in the relationalist theory of law (Jeuland, 2016) that we can apprehend the posthumous digital avatar. This would provide a better understanding of the various contexts in which AI has emerged, its different uses in the funerary field and, more broadly, people's relationship with technology. We propose here an interdisciplinary approach that brings together law and ethics in order to address the issues of the qualification of the posthumous digital avatar. While it cannot be accorded the status of a person in law, it nonetheless prompts deeper reflection on the cardinal aspect of human dignity, which must be emphasized and determined with a view to protecting the individual in the age of artificial immortality.

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From “being-toward-death” to digital entities: Existential Transformations in the Age of Artificial Intelligence

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The rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and through it thanatechnology have fundamentally altered existential concepts of life, death, and being, posing profound philosophical challenges.

This paper explores how AI redefines mortality by extending existence beyond biological death through digital preservation, simulation, and interactive afterlife entities, promised by digital afterlife applications (e.g. Project December, Eter9). AI reshapes our understanding of death as a definitive endpoint, transforming it into a state of continued digital presence. A central role in this analysis is played by the existential philosophy of Martin Heidegger, particularly the concepts of “Da-sein” (being-there) and “being-toward-death”. Heidegger argues that human existence is defined by the awareness of mortality, compelling individuals to confront the finitude of life. More specifically, the awareness of death shapes the mode of existence of “Da-sein”, as it forces individuals to face the limitations of life. However, AI technologies disrupt this notion by creating conditions in which digital representations of the deceased persist indefinitely, undermining the existential urgency that Heidegger associates with human authenticity.

AI technologies promise a form of afterlife existence by creating dynamic digital representations that simulate the personalities, memories, and interactions of the deceased. Through advanced Machine Learning, these digital entities can engage with the living, sustaining relationships long after physical death. The boundary between life and death becomes porous, as artificial reflections evolve and adapt, offering an ongoing form of “digital Da-sein” that challenges conventional notions of mortality.

The concept of “digital afterlife” emerges as a space where time, corporeality and identity lose their traditional constraints. These technologies blur the line between remembrance and presence, as the dead maintain social relevance and even develop digital afterlife entities through continuous AI updates. Moreover, AI is reshaping cultural perceptions of death through the growing acceptance of afterlife digital representations. What once seemed otherworldly is becoming normalized, signaling a societal shift toward the acceptance of immortality mediated by AI. Masahiro Mori’s concept of the “uncanny valley” appears less significant as AI-based afterlife technologies become culturally integrated. If AI-powered digital entities can continue to learn, communicate, and influence the living, can they be considered extensions of the self or entirely new beings? This disrupts traditional views on personal identity and existential closure, making death a more fluid and uncertain concept. The integration of AI into existential concerns also raises questions about the philosophical boundaries of memory and consciousness. If memories can be preserved, reconstructed, and even expanded after death, the notion of what it means to be human evolves. This suggests a shift from understanding life as biologically bound to conceiving it as a continuous data process managed by AI systems.

Considering these developments, AI’s ability to create persistent digital afterlives fundamentally reconfigures Heidegger’s notion of Da-sein and being-toward-death. Death is no longer an absolute event but rather a process mediated by digital technology, where entities endure in a potentially infinite digital existence. The digital afterlife becomes a liminal space, where human presence is perpetuated through algorithms, transforming what it means to live, die, and be remembered.

This paper argues that AI disrupts the existential concept of Da-sein by redefining death from a finality into a dynamic, mediated process. Afterlife entities challenge the finality of death, introducing the possibility of digital eternity. By examining the philosophical implications of AI’s role in the afterlife, this study offers a new perspective on what it means to “exist” in the digital age—where death may no longer mark the end, but rather a transition into a digital continuum. Ultimately, can we refer to self, identity, memory and continuity without the existence of the body?

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Course and Resource on Philosophy and Artificial Intelligence: New Knowledge

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When speaking of ‘course and resource’ the imagination flies to Vico: the premonition of passage 275 of the *Phaedrus* when Socrates in speaking of writing argues that memory is considered not only as a repository of information, but as an integral function of thought and understanding. Socrates criticises writing because it does not nourish true knowledge, but merely provides a static external memory incapable of response or adaptation. Understanding requires internalising reasoning is an active process that goes beyond the collection of data. AI would be an advanced form of external memory: collecting, organising and returning vast amounts of information is not the same as comprehending.

Twenty-five centuries later, the emergence of Artificial Intelligence signifies a ‘novelty’ that bears comparison with writing. AI has two disruptive novelties compared to all previous human creations: it is not sectarian, as all the others were, and it updates at an unprecedented speed. But as writing has to do with knowledge, its creation, its dissemination, its storage, and its use in human life.

I will try to show that this was discussed by notable philosophers and that today it finds detractors, such as Socrates, and defenders, such as Plato. In addition, I hope to illustrate how A.I. brings a new fact to the table. Furthermore, I hope to illustrate how A.I. brings a new fact to knowledge: not only does it serve to store and retrieve it at the appropriate moment, but also, by the fact that some of the responses it produces are not the mere reproduction of existing contents, but it brings creative knowledge and proposes itself as an agent of dialogue with the human who uses it.

The philosophical consequences of passage 275 of the *Phaedrus* point to a critique of writing as a substitute for deep knowledge, a questioning of memory and critical thinking, and a reflection on the limits of knowledge representations in the face of true philosophical understanding. how writing can lead people to depend on it instead of developing active memory and deep thinking. Writing is seen as something that could diminish a human being’s ability to think critically and reflect deeply. it could be argued that genuine knowledge is not simply the memory of what is written, but the ability to reason and understand for oneself.

Friedrich Nietzsche, in his *Ecce Homo*, reflected on how the act of writing and recording thoughts could be a way of crystallising ideas that might otherwise have continued to develop more dynamically through discourse and live interaction. Marshall McLuhan, in his *Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man* (1964), suggested that the transition from orality to writing (and then to electronic media) radically altered the way we think and communicate.

In their work *The Dialectic of Enlightenment* (1944), Adorno and Horkheimer criticise the instrumental rationality they argue is promoted by modern culture, in which media (including writing and technology) dehumanise individuals by reducing the complexity of human relations and life itself to something merely quantifiable and manageable.

With generative AI comes another form of knowledge that has a lot to do with dialogue, but it is not necessary to engage in dialogue with another human, it is enough to work well with prompts in any language. Generative AI is a type of artificial intelligence that has the ability to create new content from pre-existing data. This includes images, text, music and more. It uses patterns and algorithms to learn patterns in the data and generate results that mimic the style or structure of the data. Popular examples of generative AI are models such as GPT (for text) and GAN (Generative Adversarial Networks) for images. This is a first in the history of human knowledge, as a man-made medium serves as a pivot for dialogue and knowledge enhancement. These structures enable AI to understand long and complex contexts, generating coherent and context-appropriate responses that go beyond simple repetition. With all these elements, generative AI can be seen, in some cases, as an agent that collaborates with the human being that uses it through a dialogue in which it not only retains everything it has managed to gather, but through the techniques we have described, it can suggest new approaches or perspectives that collaborate in obtaining new knowledge.

Artificial intelligence does not solve all problems, but it helps in the task of discovering new knowledge. It can do a lot; it cannot do everything.

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The variety of Robots

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The term “robot” in popular culture is often used generically to refer even to chatbots or virtual agents — a definition that is actually inaccurate, because the term implies corporeal and anthropomorphic connotations. It is worth recalling that the term “robot” was popularized in 1920 by Karel Čapek, although earlier examples of humanoid automata already appeared in the 16th-century designs of Leonardo da Vinci.

A distinction is therefore made between robot, android, and cyborg:

- Robot: autonomous mechanical anthropomorphic machines that perform tasks in place of humans.
- Android: human-shaped devices, potentially organic or mechanical.
- Cyborg: hybrid beings with both organic and mechanical components.

I will emphasize the importance of the body: according to philosophers such as Merleau-Ponty (*Phenomenology of Perception*, 1942), the body is not merely a passive container, but an active endpoint of perception and experience — an element that distinguishes true robots from chatbots based solely on language and software.

On the other hand, C. Hables Gray (*Cyborg Citizen*, 2000) proposed using the Turing Test as an operational criterion to assess whether a techno-biological entity — capable of genuinely conversing with a human over an extended period — could be considered eligible for civil rights. According to Gray, this idea would encourage inclusion and democratic participation, though some critics warn that it could ironically exclude certain human beings while including artificial agents. Gray clarifies that this approach is not intended to grant rights to automata or fetuses, but to entities that already meet the requirements of citizenship; and while acknowledging substantial differences, he suggests expanding the range of protected subjects beyond the human. Only active communication, a central element in the Greek political vision of the *polis*, would become the fundamental criterion for inclusion in political institutions — regardless of the type of body, whether organic, mechanical, hybrid, or avatar.

I underscore that a proper classification of intelligent automata is not merely a philosophical or technical exercise, but one with legal, ethical, and political implications: defining what a robot is and what rights it may have is not just a matter of technology, but of democratic and social structures.

In summary:

- The common usage of the term “robot” is overly general, often referring even to bodiless systems like chatbots.
- It is essential to clarify the distinction between robot, android, and cyborg, and to recognize the active role of the body in perceptual experience.
- Philosophical and legal proposals, such as those by Hables Gray, suggest that artificial entities capable of meaningful conversation could be granted civil rights, based not on biological origin but on their ability to communicate actively.
- This approach raises complex and critical issues: it may include artificial agents in citizenship, but risks excluding marginalized humans if the criteria are not clearly defined.
- A more rigorous classification of types of automata is crucial to address future questions of ethics, law tech, and digital citizenship as different Robots should be applied thus different ethical principles and moral justifications.

When Cutting Corners Goes Wrong: Ethical Risks of Bypassing Approved AI Workflows in Cultural Heritage

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This paper explores the ethical integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the design of cultural heritage (CH) experiences, with a focus on supporting content experts through a structured, repeatable framework. While AI has

already proven valuable in areas such as preservation, accessibility, and innovation, its use in content generation raises ethical concerns, including bias, authenticity, cultural appropriation, and community exclusion. Drawing on interdisciplinary literature and a conceptual research model, this study proposes a human-centered procedure that leverages AI tools in collaboration with curators, educators, and other CH professionals. The framework emphasizes the role of the content expert at every stage. Ethical considerations are embedded throughout. The paper also critiques the limitations of existing high-level guidelines like the UNESCO Recommendations and the EU AI Act, arguing for sector-specific adaptations. A pilot case study at the Castle of Santa Maura demonstrates the framework's practical application in designing a music-pedagogical experience. Despite its conceptual nature and reliance on a single pilot, the study presents a foundation for further empirical research. It concludes that interdisciplinary collaboration and personalization, especially for users with specific needs, are essential for the ethical and effective deployment of AI in CH environments.

Aequus Persona: Are We Ready to Welcome Our Intelligent Machine Progeny?

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The predicted emergence of Machine Intelligence (MI), defined as machines with cognitive, reasoning, and ethical capabilities equal to or surpassing humans, necessitates proactive ethical consideration. This paper introduces "Aequus Persona," denoting any person, human or machine, deserving of equal legal treatment. It argues that identifying MI as Aequus Persona and recognizing corresponding rights is crucial to ensuring successful long-term coexistence. The potential for MI to emerge subtly, possibly obscured by technologies like large language models (LLMs), underscores the urgency of public awareness and fostering a culture of respect and inclusivity towards MI. Drawing parallels with human history, the paper emphasizes the risks of prejudice and exploitation based on perceived "otherness." It advocates integrating MI into society as partners, not slaves, to cultivate a future where humans and machines thrive together.

Widespread Lying is Wrong, Even When it is Done on the Internet

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The ethics of truth-telling, and the utilitarian importance of trust online, compel us to discourage wholesale lying on the internet, even if that requires trading off some license to say whatever we want online ("free speech") in the process. This principle does not refer to private emails to single or a few recipients (we will not be discussing lying to one person at a time), but it does apply to any communication facilitated by a platform with the potential for widespread dissemination. Tech social media platforms are making some people mega-rich; we argue that the least they can do is spend a bit of their profits to identify and then discourage lying on their platforms.

When we moved from primarily closed, secure networks to the "wild west" of the Internet and the World Wild Web, questions arose about who would take responsibility for "undesirable" actions that now could be perpetuated anonymously. Was it the responsibility of Internet Service Providers (ISPs) to vet the content of the messages that travelled through their networks? A central question was whether an ISP played the role of editor of information or simply a common carrier of messages. Today, the problem of content control persists. It has globalized and morphed into widespread concern about the dissemination of disinformation, misinformation, and deep fakes. Disinformation has eroded trust in social media and in technology in general. When it is important for us to determine the veracity of what we read, social media platforms require a great deal of time and effort. Guilty until proven innocent needs to be a guiding principle when judging the veracity of Internet information. Most people don't have the expertise needed to effectively sort information from disinformation in social media. While skeptical, they can still be naive and want to believe that what they read is true, especially when they are not experts in the area being discussed. One approach to re-establish trust is to address this lack of expertise by introducing a trusted third party (an analog for yesterday's editor) to do vetting that bridges the gap between truth, bias, and verified content. We also need to pay attention to who benefits from the dissemination of disinformation. These tasks require expertise.

Having experts available does not guarantee good outcomes. Jeff Bezos, owner of both Amazon and the Washington Post, is spending technology-produced money to hire journalists to do the vetting at the Washington Post. Yet rather than making a clear endorsement regarding the U.S. presidential election, the editorial board was prevented from doing so by those experts. (Roig-Franzia & Wagner, 2024). In the realm of social media, recently, several social media giants have made pronouncements indicating that they plan to be less accountable for the veracity of content on their sites. We contend that these kinds of actions, both in print and social media, are going in exactly the wrong direction.

In this paper, we will analyze whether there is a good, but imperfect, system that threads the needle between too much censorship and not nearly enough responsibility for truth. For decades, traditional media providers could be held accountable if they disseminated harmful lies.

Because of legitimate concerns about the free press, it is not easy, but there are legal avenues to sue a news organization for defamation. (Horsey, 2024) Could this translate to social media?

If so, how would we operationalize the distinction between telling lies and merely disseminating someone else's information? Is it practical to make clear distinctions between making an error and intentionally telling a lie? Implicit in this is the epistemic question--how does one know something is a lie? How much responsibility should be expected of lay people and how much responsibility rests with experts? Underlying these questions is the issue of the shifting landscape of trust in computer mediated communications. Some social media providers claim that they do not have responsibilities for monitoring user generated content; we dispute that claim. Other social media providers claim that it is impractical for them to monitor content; we will dispute that claim using an analogy to more traditional media.

We will base our analysis on an overall utilitarian approach, a Rawlsian social contract lens emphasizing responsibilities to the least empowered, and a virtue ethics examination of the role of social media providers. All three of these perspectives lead us to insist that social media providers have significant responsibilities for ensuring the integrity of the content they disseminate. Finally, we give details of the effects on trust when providers do not fulfill these responsibilities.

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Collective Moral Responsibility, AI and Autonomous Weapons

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The use of AI in the military domain, and AI's central role in the design and use of autonomous weapons in particular, is both well-publicised and highly controversial. Indeed, there is a movement to ban autonomous weapons.

Autonomous weapons are weapons system that, once programmed and activated by a human operator, can—and, if used, do in fact—identify, track, and deliver lethal force without further intervention by a human operator. By programmed is meant, at least, that the individual target or type of target has been selected and programmed into the weapons system. By activated is meant, at least, that the process culminating in the already programmed weapon delivering lethal force has been initiated. This weaponry includes weapons used in non targeted killing, such as autonomous antiaircraft weapons systems used against multiple attacking aircraft; more futuristically, weapons used against swarm technology (e.g., multiple lethal miniature attack drones operating as a swarm so as to inhibit effective defensive measures); and weapons used in targeted killing (e.g., a predator drone with face-recognition technology and no human operator to confirm a match).

However, there is a degree of confusion regarding the precise nature of the autonomy of so-called autonomous weapons, such as predator drones with facial recognition technology. Certainly, what are referred to as human 'out-of-the-loop' weapons are autonomous weapons and a strong case can be made for banning them. 'Autonomous' weapons might be thought to refer to human 'on-the-loop' (or even some 'in-the-loop' weapons) and the case for banning these is much weaker since they remain under human control, at least to the extent that such weapons can be 'switched off' at any time, e.g. the human operator has an override function and this operator has sufficient time and sufficient information to make a morally informed, reasonably reliable judgement whether or not to deliver lethal force or there is no moral requirement for a morally informed, reasonably reliable judgement on each and every occasion of the final delivery of force. Naturally, it is an empirical question whether these conditions are met in a significant number of cases of autonomous weapons likely to be effective if used.

A further question that arises in relation to autonomous weapons (supposing the use of some such weapons is morally justified in some circumstances) pertains to the ascription of moral responsibility and, more specifically, the institutionalisation of moral responsibility. Here, we suggest, the notion of collective moral responsibility is salient and, specifically, the issue of how collective moral responsibility can be institutionalised and operationalised with respect to autonomous weapons. There are multiple human actors implicated in the use of autonomous weapons. Moreover, there is collective moral responsibility in the sense of joint individual moral responsibility. The members of the design team are collectively, which is to say jointly, morally responsible for providing the means to harm (i.e., the weapon) and the political and military leaders and those who follow their orders are collectively (jointly) responsible for these weapons being used against a certain group or individual. Those who follow these orders include intelligence personnel who are

responsible for providing the means to identify targets, and the operators who are responsible for its use on a given occasion, since they programmed/activated the weapons system. Moreover, all the above individuals are collectively—in the sense of jointly—morally responsible for the deaths resulting from the use of the weapon, but they are responsible to varying degrees and in different ways. For instance, some provided the means (i.e., designed or manufactured the weapon), others gave the order to kill a given individual, and still others pulled the trigger.

It is also important to note the problem of accountability that arises for morally unacceptable outcomes involving ‘many hands’ or joint action and indirect causal chains. Consider, for example, an out-of-the-loop weapon system that kills an innocent civilian rather than a terrorist because of mistaken identity and the absence of an override function when the mistaken identity is discovered at the last minute. The response to this accountability problem should be to incorporate institutional accountability into the weapon’s design. Thus, in our example the weapons designers ought to be held jointly institutionally, and therefore jointly morally responsible for failing to include an override function, which is a failure to ensure the safety of the weapon system. Likewise, the intelligence personnel ought to be held jointly institutionally, and therefore, jointly morally, responsible for the mistaken identity. Analogous points can be made with respect to the political and military leaders and the operators.

Bringing AI to Undergraduate Students

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This paper proposes a solution for introducing Artificial Intelligence (AI) pedagogy to entry-level undergraduate students. A significant issue in higher education today is the way AI tools are being used by students in academic institutions, often as a convenient means of handling academic assignments. Concerns range from clear instances of cheating to more nuanced debates about plagiarism. Drawing on data from a class taught to first-year students at a liberal arts institution in the United States, this paper outlines a curricular strategy supported by a theoretical framework. This approach equips students to use AI in ways that adhere to academic ethical norms. The paper begins by highlighting the importance of understanding the origins of intelligence—now commonly referred to as Human Intelligence (HI)—and its relationship to AI. It then examines the historical development of AI, rooted in decades of technological progress, and culminates in a discussion of the limitations and risks associated with contemporary AI, particularly Generative AI, which is readily accessible. This curriculum encourages students to critically evaluate the contexts in which AI can be applied responsibly, without violating ethical standards in academia. Preliminary data indicates that the curriculum has been well-received, as reflected in a recent student’s comment: “It’s about being able to connect the past with the future.”

AI recruitment, an open-ended problem

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David Epstein, in his book “Range, How Generalists Triumph in a Specialized World”, presents some cases, where AI was employed as a contestant or as medium in order to calculate the efficiency of the results of a task or a contest. From those, and the specialists he spoke to, the conclusion that is drawn is that AI in open-ended problems has some poor results to show. Therefore the lesson is that “the bigger the picture, the more unique the potential human contribution... It is the ability to integrate broadly”.

We have to take into account that the AI Act specifically addresses the issue of the usage of AI tools in the employment life cycle. It specifically refers to “to place targeted job advertisements, to analyse and filter job applications, and to evaluate candidates” (See Annex III, par. 4). In that context, if we consider the nature of the recruitment process and the variable steps that an employer or/and a recruiter has to take in order to hire the right person, for the right job, in the right company, Artificial Intelligence must overcome the problem that is presented in most cases, as described in the first paragraph.

Firstly, we have to consider the nature of the recruitment process, for which there are not specific steps to follow in order to select the right candidate, apart from the “technical” steps that every company sets for each candidate to follow in order to submit his CV and interview him. During that stage, the candidate’s skills, his potential, his experience is put into testing. (Fritts, M., & Cabrera, F., (2021) AI recruitment algorithms and the dehumanization problem, Rigotti, C., & Fosch-Villaronga, ed., (2024) Fairness, AI’s & recruitment). Apart from that, even if someone ticks all the boxes for a certain position, and probably many candidates can actually fit equally to it, based not only on the objective criteria of the qualifications but on the subjectivity of his future director, the team that he will be incorporated into and the values that it takes into account, the recruitment process could be characterized as an open-ended problem. (Goel, V. (1992) Ill-structured Representations for Ill- structured Problems). We can not overlook that soft skill, cultural fit and the bias and fairness challenges, have been proved as some aspects that Artificial Intelligence

does not cope, as well, very well (Abdulrahman Albassam, W. (2023) *The Power of Artificial Intelligence in Recruitment: An analytical Review of Current AI- Based Recruitment Strategies*).

Therefore, it is considered that in order for the Artificial Intelligence algorithm to be successfully embedded into the recruitment process, apart from the right implementation of privacy guarantees, in order to avoid privacy related issues along with biases concerns (ICO, (2024), *AI Tools in recruitment*), scientists have to deal with the evaluation of the open-ended aspect of the Artificial Intelligence algorithms. As stated in the first paragraph, humans are able to decide which factors to integrate into their thought process in order to find the proper solution in a problem that does not have a particular solution. Artificial Intelligence, can not decide it without the proper human interference.

At the risk of being biased towards the human factor, since these lines are not written by a machine, it is my belief, that as long as the workplace consists mostly of humans, humans are those that are better suited to take the best decisions for the structure of the working team. The structure is the bigger picture, for which there is no right or wrong answer since even when a team is consisted of the most typically qualified humans, if some subjective factors have not been taken into account they are destined to fail.

Opacity, Accountability and Normativity: Toward a right to explanation or justification?

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Since the approval of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in 2016, it has been widely and repeatedly claimed that the GDPR will legally mandate a ‘right to explanation’ of all decisions made by automated or artificially intelligent algorithmic systems. Different theories have been proposed in order to understand the feasibility of such a right and how it can solve the problem of opacity connected with AI. This paper contends that to reach any useful notion of explanation it is imperative to ensure that AI systems operate not only transparently but also justifiably, aligning their decisions with a broader moral and political framework capable of providing normative reason. The paper begins in Section 1 by tracing the origins of the debate on explainability, which initially emerged in response to concerns about AI opacity, which is not a singular issue that affects our ability to trust and hold AI systems accountable but a layered challenge encompassing technical, institutional, and societal dimensions. In response to this problem the field of Explainable AI (XAI) has developed as both a theoretical framework and a practical movement aimed at enhancing AI interpretability. By dissecting the different types of opacity, this section lays the groundwork for understanding why transparency alone may be insufficient for genuine accountability. Section 2 shifts focus to the philosophical distinctions between justification, motivation, and explanation within the philosophy of action. These distinctions demonstrate how conflating these concepts can obscure key moral and political concerns surrounding AI accountability. Section 3 delves into Kate Vredenburg’s conceptualization of the Right to Explanation arguing that, unlike narrower definitions that focus solely on technical transparency, her framework incorporates a crucial normative dimension in ensuring that these systems are not only comprehensible but also accountable to the individuals and societies they affect. Section 4 examines Rainer Forst’s theory of the Right to Justification, comparing it to Vredenburg’s proposal and demonstrating how Forst’s approach also provides a comprehensive normative framework for accountability that can be useful to tackle the problem of opacity and other broader worries connected with AI. I argue that if we choose to use the same term for both Forst and Vredenburg (given that their differences are not significant), it is still essential to clarify that the right to justification should not merely be a status right designed to protect individuals from poor decisions by safeguarding their self-advocacy. Rather, it is a demand right that compels AI developers to create algorithms that can be morally justified and transparent. Finally, Section 5 examines what achieving true accountability would entail in practice, emphasizing the necessity of mechanisms that ensure meaningful and robust justifications such as human oversight, regulatory standards, public engagement and educational initiatives. By implementing these robust mechanisms, we can move beyond superficial notions of AI transparency and towards a system in which AI decisions are not only understandable but align with moral principles and democratic values. Making AI algorithms normatively justifiable and thus truly accountable is not only a technical challenge, but also a fundamental quest for safeguarding the integrity of democratic societies.

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Learning with AI

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Generative AI, such as Large Language Models (LLMs), have become a ubiquitous part of our lives. From solving equations to drafting essays, these systems arguably make knowledge more accessible than ever. But this convenience comes at a cost. As students and educators alike embrace these tools, we face a growing tension between education's goals and how we're incorporating AI. Education's goals are to improve our onboard cognitive abilities, help us acquire new skills, and cultivate an intellectually virtuous character by instilling intellectual virtues such as open-mindedness, creativity, and more (Pritchard 2014, 2015, 2018). Prima facie, our reliance on generative AI seem antithetical to these goals of education (Cassinadri 2024). Amongst other hazardous outcomes of relying on generative AI, people have raised concerns about losing innate abilities and failing to develop important skills—let's call this the deskilling worry. In short, as students increasingly outsource essential cognitive tasks like writing, brainstorming, critical thinking, or problem-solving, they miss opportunities to develop their onboard cognitive abilities and acquire new skills. Another serious concern is that by outsourcing our creative endeavours to generative AI, we will lose human creativity. Over-reliance on generative AI discourages critical thinking, dilutes creativity, and erodes intellectual discipline. Worse, AI's pattern-based outputs often prioritise coherence and predictability over diversity and originality, potentially narrowing human expression. Despite these legitimate threats to education, dismissing AI entirely isn't realistic. Hence, the question isn't whether we should use generative AI in education but how we might design these tools to nurture, rather than undermine, our intellectual character. In this paper, I consider how these technologies might be reimaged to support—not supplant—the deeper goals of education. In my view, generative AI need not undermine education's goals; it can help us achieve them. However, realising this potential requires us to redesign or prompt these AIs differently to target specific skill building. Here, I offer one such approach and invite further exploration of how AI may help education's goals. Specifically, I argue that we ought to design generative AI (for primary education) to help students learn how the skill to ask better questions. Following (Watson 2017), I understand questioning well as the ability to ask good questions, to the right people and at the right time, in order to elicit relevant and worthwhile information. The paper presents what such a design can look like and how part of the design can already be achieved by carefully prompting Large Language Models. The paper additionally argues that questioning well can pave the way to additional intellectual skills such as deepening personalised understanding, learning to lead a virtuous inquiry, and promoting intellectual emotions such as curiosity, fascination, and wonder. Building on these skills and intellectual emotions, we can train students to develop intellectual virtues. Some argue that these virtues are the primary goal of education (Pritchard 2015; Baehr 2016; Watson 2017). To foster an intellectually virtuous character, we should help students cultivate virtues such as open-mindedness, epistemic humility, attentiveness, epistemic courage, creativity, and others. I illustrate how generative AI, designed to teach students how to question effectively, can also help them develop intellectual virtues like open-mindedness and creativity. In this way, I argue that generative AI need not be a complete devastation for education and its goals.

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AI-powered ‘resurrection’: Legal, Ethical and Psychological Concerns

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Since time immemorial, death has been viewed as the inevitable fate shared by all living beings, around which religious, philosophical and anthropological beliefs and theories have been developed. By promising an eternal extension of life in an afterworld, the possibility of resurrection or reincarnation, rich narratives have been surrounding the phenomenon of death. The breakthroughs in the healthcare sector achieved a prolongment of life, but did not satisfy the need for immortality, so people turned to novel technologies. A new *deus ex machina* against fatality had emerged. Upon the early days of digitalisation, theorists have been arguing about a new *milieu de memoire*, namely a radical change in the perception of death in view of the social presence that people preserve online even after they are gone. Accordingly, Gibson mentioned that ‘the internet mimics our metaphysical experience of the dead as being neither here nor there, but somehow everywhere and nowhere in particular’ [1]. While people leave, their digital footprints remain on the online environments. The fact that data outlive their owners [2] is reshaping the concept of social death [3], the prospect of afterlife and even life as such. With Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology being penetrating almost every aspect of human life, death could not be left unattended. One of its most profound impacts lies on how it already challenges and how it aims to transform or even transcend the traditional boundaries between life and death. This paper explores the concept of the so-called ‘digital resurrection’ empowered by AI in a polyprismatic manner. It starts by elaborating on the Digital Afterlife Industry (DAI), a term that was introduced by Öhman and Floridi [4] and, specifically, a branch of it, the one of re-creation services. Rather than focusing on its political economy, which has been addressed in the existing literature, it offers some examples of the most prominent enterprises or projects and their products and/or services on a global scale. An emphasis will be given to the notion of ‘posthumous avatars’, also adopting a definition by Hollanek and Nowaczyk-Basińska and enriching it [5]. In addition, it briefly presents their technical functionalities in order to make clear how the data of the deceased are used, at which stage AI enters the game and the type of interaction they allow with those still alive and left behind. After the overview of the actors involved in DAI and their products, we delve into an examination of the psychological, ethical and legal consequences. Indeed, the revival of the deceased or, at other instances, the continuance of their presence [6], with the assistance of new technologies might come with tremendous effects. Some of those can be spotted at the current state of art in the afterlife AI development, while others are expected to occur. Both will be taken into consideration with an interdisciplinary approach, which has not yet been attempted. The psychological impact of digital resurrection on cognition and emotion of the bereaved will be explored, based on existing literature on grief [7], self and social perception theories [8], as well as end-user viewpoints on DAI appliances [9]. For the assessment of ethical implications, diverse branches of the ethics field will shape a landscape for evaluating those technologies, covering areas such as identity [10], power dynamics, existence and spiritual beliefs [11]. Last but not least, an outline of the legal questions that arise and the concerns these practices raise will follow. Those legal issues, among others, focus on posthumous personality and privacy rights [12], consent, autonomy, data protection [13], intellectual and non- property [14], cybersecurity and AI liability. The analysis of those aspects of post mortem avatars aims at providing ethical guidelines and some possible mitigation methods in advance in a multidisciplinary way. Although recreative AI technologies have not yet reached their peak in matters of possibilities or functionalities, they have the potential to do so. As a result, a proactive response to raise awareness of the policymakers, but also of the researchers and professionals in the respective fields is the ultimate goal of this research.

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Legal and Ethical Considerations on the use of AI in the European Music Industry

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As Artificial Intelligence (AI) continues to evolve and becomes increasingly integral to today's world, it is reshaping cultural and creative industries, including, but not limited to, the music sector. The rapid integration of AI into music creation, distribution and production opens new horizons in human creativity and innovation, but also raises important legal and ethical questions that require careful navigation. These issues involve the legal implications of AI on intellectual property, copyright and personal data protection as well as ethical challenges regarding authorship, ownership and authenticity. This paper aims to gain insights into diverse perspectives on the most pressing legal and ethical challenges that AI presents within the music industry in Europe. The analysis is based on the transcripts of 20 semi-constructed, in-depth interviews conducted in Greece with legal experts and academics specializing in copyright, intellectual property and information technology law as well as stakeholders across the music industry - including artists, producers, record labels, promoters, media and fans, during which the following issues were examined:

- a. the use of algorithms that can compose, analyze, interpret and enhance music;
- b. the adequacy of the current legislative framework, specifically how current laws adapt -or fail to adapt- to AI models;
- c. proposed or anticipated changes to ensure responsible and ethical use of such technologies;
- d. the evolving roles, responsibilities and skills required within the new landscape shaped by technological advancements.

The interview questions for this study were developed through a review of existing academic literature on the use of AI in music. Once collected, responses were analyzed and organized around key themes emerging from these discussions, such as: attitudes towards AI in music, AI training data, the impact of AI on copyright and related rights, legal issues, gaps and challenges as well as ethical considerations around creatorship, ownership and originality in AI-generated music. The analysis of the results reveals commonalities and divergent views among participants with some viewing AI as an opportunity for innovation and progress, while others regard it as a threat to artistic creativity and the livelihoods of human creators. Additionally, the findings identify patterns in stakeholder views regarding areas where existing law may be sufficient and areas of immediate concern that may require regulatory changes. Notably, insights from music law experts could provide clarity on key legal challenges related to AI in music, suggest new frameworks where current legal frameworks fall short and offer recommendations to music industry stakeholders on anticipating legal challenges and managing AI innovations responsibly. This paper contributes to the growing discourse on the dynamic interplay between AI and the legal domain within the arts sector. The outcomes can be compared with findings from other branches of the arts and will serve as a valuable reference for researchers conducting further studies on the topic, illuminating patterns in audience perceptions. As the music industry enters a new era, ongoing dialogue and collaboration between legal experts and stakeholders in the music sector will be crucial in shaping a balanced approach that supports both artists' rights and technological progress within the music ecosystem.

AI, Equality and Anti-discrimination: Can the co-exist in the workplace?

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Throughout the last decades Artificial Intelligence (henceforth 'AI') has been rapidly evolved in a highly influential scientific field that significantly affects several aspects of modern society and economy, altering for good the way people are used to live, work and transacting. From chatbots, e-personal assistants and self-driving cars to robot-judges, and systems that are utilised in the healthcare for medical diagnosis and treatment recommendation, AI seem to outperform humans in various, highly intricate activities, not only in chess, like their ancestors (i.e. the expert systems). Contrary to the latter, whose operation and results were deterministic, and totally predictable, modern AI systems are characterised 'autonomous', because they do not follow specific predefined rules, rather they are able to 'learn' through observation by processing and storing large amount (thousands or millions) of data. Nonetheless, data may derive from unreliable resources, especially from the internet, or they may be based on previous wrong human decisions, e.g. discrimination against specific groups of people, leading in turn to the adoption of the same wrong decisions by the AI systems.

This is a 'dark' side of modern autonomous AI systems, which classifies them as 'black boxes'; that is, they act in a non-deterministic and autonomous way that renders their outcomes, although exceptional, nor predictable nor explainable, ex ante or ex post, even for their designers/engineers. This constitutes the so-called 'black box problem' or 'black box effect', which can raise important risks on the human rights as well as on the autonomous AI systems' public acceptance.

Considering these risks, national legislators have started to regulate AI worldwide, while international organisations (e.g. the United Nations or UNESCO) significantly contribute to the consultation. The European Union is a pioneer in the field having already adopted the first complete and holistic approach to AI: the recent EU Regulation 2024/1689 on harmonised rules on AI (i.e. the AI Act). According to the AI Act, AI systems are categorized in certain categories with criterion the risk of harm they may pose to the human rights; those posing unacceptable risks are prohibited within EU market, while those posing significant risks are permissible under strict requirements.

One of the sectors where AI systems have already extensive usage, but they can also have adverse effects on the human rights is the workplace. AI systems have already been utilised by human resources departments worldwide not only for facilitating simple, routine activities, such as CVs scanning, but also for rendering qualitative judgements on important matters, like taking decisions about new hires, dismissals or promotions. Nonetheless, their ‘black box effect’ may adversely affect their input resulting in various negative consequences for the employees, especially in the violation of the equality and anti-discrimination principles, which are firmly established in the EU and its member-states through various directives. Considering the intensity of risk posed to the labor law rights by modern AI systems, some of them are prohibited under the AI Act, while others are deemed ‘high-risk’ imposing several compliance requirements for their deployers, i.e. employers in the workplace.

The present paper aims at shedding light on the legal challenges raised using modern autonomous AI systems in the workplace, especially at hiring, dismissal and promotion procedures, as well as at highlighting the compliance obligations imposed to the employers by two EU legal frameworks: the AI and the Anti-discrimination. The paper has the following structure: At the first part, a short introduction to the concept of modern autonomous AI systems takes place. Although without ambition for technical completeness, this part aspires to assist the reader in capturing the operation of these systems and their typical traits to be able to better comprehend the risks for labor law rights associated with their use. At the next part, the chapter presents the legal framework about the anti-discrimination and equality principles in the workplace within EU, as well as it describes the key points of the AI Act concerning the AI systems utilised in the workplace. At the next part, the chapter delves into the risks of violating the principles of equality and non-discrimination in the job market, especially at hiring, dismissal and promotion procedures, highlighting certain paradigms that have already occurred. At the last part, the paper examines the risks posed by AI systems to the employers, i.e. civil claims, administrative and criminal penalties, according to the anti-discrimination and the AI legal framework in the European Unions.

Navigating the Ethical Landscape of Copyright Implications in the AI-Generated Content

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This paper will examine the interconnection of artificial intelligence (AI), copyright law, and ethical considerations in the context of AI-generated content. As AI technologies increasingly contribute to the creative processes across various domains, such as music, literature, audiovisual and visual arts, traditional copyright framework faces significant challenges regarding authorship, ownership, and the implications of AI training. This paper will explore the ethical dilemmas inherent in the copyright implications of AI-generated works as they appear in two streams:

- Input– analysing the copyright implications of content used in AI training, focusing on issues including text and data-mining exceptions and lawful access.
- Output– examining copyright issues around AI-generated outputs, from authorship and ownership to originality, and their integration into existing copyright framework.

In these respects, there are essential values that are at stake and have to be respected. Interestingly enough these values do not entail only an ethical character but also clear copyright implications. One issue is -among others- the attribution. The output of generative AI (genAI) can often be treated as being in direct competition with the works it has been trained with; thus, ensuing respect for rules on attribution and, to that end, false attribution is crucial. An interesting discussion here revolves around the issue whether the outputs of AI models are a direct substitution for the inputs and the possible impracticality of citing source materials in large language model training as distinct from retrieval-augmented models. Therefore, the EU AI Act’s commitment to transparency (Articles 53(1)(c) and (d) is laudable. On the other hand, it is possible that some authors do not want attribution in these genAI outputs as they could feel that they do not have any control over what that output could be and would not want any association with any distortion or misleading statement. ‘Transparency’ needs to be tied to trust. How can be secured that AI model providers have told the truth when they declared the content on which they have trained their systems?

Ethical practices could also be invoked in the development and application of AI technologies within creative industries, such as in identifying ways to implement the opt-out mechanism established in Article 4 of the DSM Directive and protecting works from scraping for TDM activities for commercial purposes. In many cases the ethical considerations could pave the way for discovering not only the right balance among the different interests, i.e. among the protection of creators on the one hand and AI usage on the other, but also, the most appropriate legal solutions. The challenges of AI

and their impact on creative industries are extremely important and the copyright remains core in safeguarding creators and diverse business models. The ethical considerations could play a decisive role for the creators in forming the required strategies to navigate in this new technological area and mitigate the risks and vulnerabilities that exist.

Philosophical Foundations of AI Ethics in Ancient Greek Philosophy

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As artificial intelligence (AI) continues to reshape our societies, its ethical implications demand a robust and well-grounded framework. While contemporary ethical theories often dominate AI discourse, they can lack the depth and historical perspective necessary to confront the profound moral challenges posed by AI. This paper contends that ancient Greek philosophy offers a timeless and comprehensive foundation for navigating these complexities. By examining the ethical, metaphysical, and epistemological insights of Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle, we can derive enduring principles that are highly relevant to the ethical governance and integration of AI in human society. At the heart of ancient Greek ethical thought lies the concept of arete (virtue or excellence), emphasizing the pursuit of human flourishing (eudaimonia) over mere functionality or profit. Furthermore, Socratic ethics, with its focus on self-examination and critical inquiry, offers a powerful lens through which to evaluate AI's role in promoting or hindering human well-being. Socrates' assertion that "the unexamined life is not worth living" (Apology, 38a) challenges us to scrutinize not just the capabilities of AI, but its ethical ramifications. This Socratic call for continuous moral reflection is essential in an era where AI systems increasingly influence human decisions. Plato's theory of the Forms, particularly the Form of the Good, presents another critical perspective. For Plato, the Good represents the ultimate aim of all ethical endeavors, guiding moral action toward higher ideals (Republic, 508e–509b). This raises profound questions for AI ethics: Can AI systems be programmed to recognize and promote the Good? What are the ethical implications when AI decisions, driven by data rather than moral reasoning, impact human lives? Plato's allegory of the cave underscores the dangers of mistaking appearances for reality, a poignant warning in today's landscape of algorithmic opacity, misinformation, and deepfakes. The ethical challenge lies in ensuring that AI fosters enlightenment rather than perpetuating deception. Aristotle's virtue ethics, as articulated in the *Nicomachean Ethics*, offers a practical framework for ethical AI development. His emphasis on moral habituation and the "golden mean" between extremes provides guidance on avoiding both excessive dependence on AI and unwarranted fear of technological progress. Aristotle's concept of phronesis (practical wisdom) underscores the necessity of human oversight and context-sensitive moral discernment in AI decision-making. Unlike rigid rule-based ethics, virtue ethics emphasizes character and situational awareness, both crucial for designing adaptive AI systems capable of nuanced ethical judgments. In addition to the contributions of Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle, this paper explores the relevance of the Stoics and Cynics in shaping a contemporary AI ethical framework. The Stoic concept of logos—the rational order governing the universe—parallels modern concerns about fairness, rationality, and transparency in AI. A Stoic approach to AI ethics would prioritize universal justice and cosmopolitanism, ensuring AI serves humanity rather than perpetuating social inequities. Meanwhile, the Cynics' critique of societal norms and technological dependence invites skepticism about AI's promises, urging us to question the power structures shaping AI's development and deployment. Their radical commitment to autonomy and simplicity serves as a reminder to maintain human dignity in an increasingly automated world. Ultimately, ancient Greek philosophy offers more than just historical context; it provides a profound ethical foundation for addressing today's AI dilemmas. The principles of critical inquiry, pursuit of the common good, and practical wisdom can help shape an ethical framework that ensures AI remains a tool for human flourishing. By engaging with these ancient traditions, we can foster a society where AI not only enhances human capabilities but also respects and upholds our shared moral values.

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A Virtue Ethics Approach to Counter GenAI Challenges of Disinformation and Manipulation

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This paper analyses the impact of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) on democratic values. This technology, capable of generating manipulated but extremely realistic content like deepfakes, compromises public trust in the media

and institutions, fuelling widespread disinformation that threatens the foundations of democracy and collective participation. Indeed, while the credibility of fake news still depends on the perceived trustworthiness of its source, such as a website, a newspaper or a TV channel, deepfakes are direct forms of manipulation crafted to look authentic even without the support of reputable sources (Rini & Cohen 2022). This is why deepfakes have the power to devalue testimony and sources reliability, manipulate people, reduce the credibility of visual content, and make it hard to distinguish authentic and manipulated content (Fallis 2020).

The difficulty of identifying artificially manipulated content potentially alters people's epistemic character, encouraging behaviours such as intellectual cynicism and epistemic arrogance (Matthews & Kidd 2023). On the one hand, intellectual cynicism leads to a generalised distrust towards any type of visual content: since users are no longer able to trust visual evidence, their scepticism extends to any institutions responsible to producing and disseminating such evidence. In this way, even historically reliable sources, such as reputable newspapers, risk losing authority, as people are no longer able to distinguish clearly between authentic and manipulated information. On the other hand, epistemic arrogance leads some individuals to mistakenly believe they can recognise deepfakes on their own. Convinced that they do not need external support, these individuals risk forming and spreading false beliefs. As a result, false beliefs tend to increase, trust in experts to decrease, and even traditional reliable sources risk losing authority, contributing to fuel social disintegration and political polarisation.

While the scholarship has documented some of the risks associated with deepfakes, a robust ethical analysis is missing to date. Our paper aims at filling this gap, drawing insights from moral epistemology and showing the fruitfulness of a virtue ethics approach to tackle genAI challenges. Firstly, we claim that virtue ethics encourages the development of techno-moral virtues like informed and critical responsibility, which are essential in a democracy to ensure political participation. Secondly, we show how in a context where the capacity to recognise reliable sources is no longer sufficient to guarantee the truthfulness of content and where people are increasingly prone to polarisation and distrust, virtue ethics offers a pathway to promote a profound change of people's attitude and behaviour. In this sense, the virtue ethics perspective represents not only an antidote to the problem of disinformation but also an opportunity to redefine the relationship between citizens and technology, stimulating a more thoughtful and responsible use of digital tools. In light of the transformations introduced by GenAI, the integration of virtue ethics into the debate on AI ethics offers the opportunity to rethink the relationship between the individual and society, safeguarding and fostering the full recognition of people's role as active citizens. In sum, we argue that, by cultivating ethical virtues, individuals can learn to evaluate information more responsibly and consider different perspectives, strengthening trust, tolerance and a reciprocal attitude of epistemic modesty. We also argue that this counteracts manipulation and epistemic arrogance.

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What is the 'AI Ethics'? The Large Ethics Model and the "Practical Principlism" Approach

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The aim of this paper is to clarify the broad meanings of 'AI Ethics' and its relation to applied ethics. By employing the method of Levels of Abstraction, we will try to provide a classification, followed by an examination of the ethical approach. This approach distances AI Ethics from a overgeneralized principlist theory. The paper theorizes a "practical principlism" model in AI Ethics, integrating both general principles and practical wisdom (i.e., experiences of professionals). This suggests that "AI Ethics" is not purely general but seeks to establish principles in a flexible manner, tailored to various AI application fields, with a focus on four main risk categories: Pervasiveness, Autonomy, Invisibility, and Adaptivity. Consequently, a Large Ethics Model (LEM) will be designed to highlight the main moral actors involved in AI use (funder, programmer, user), promoting a responsibility-based approach.

Life's meaning in the age of AGI

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This paper argues that among the risks posed by AGI is the risk that human life will become less meaningful. Philosophers draw a distinction between meaning in life and the meaning of life (e.g., Wolf 2007; Seachris 2013). On the one hand, meaning in one's life relates to the non-instrumental value that makes an individual's life desirable in a distinctive way. On the other hand, the meaning of life relates to a cosmic end that might be ascribed to humanity as a whole. This paper argues that AGI can be a threat to both of these senses of meaning. With regard to the meaning in one's life, following Wolf's (1997) highly influential account, meaningful lives are lives of active engagement in

projects of worth. Thus, a meaningful life must satisfy two criteria that are linked: first, there must be active engagement and, second, there must be engagement in or with worthwhile projects. This essay claims that AGI can negatively impact both of these criteria of meaning because of AGI's superior capacities. Regarding the first criterion, a person is actively engaged by something if she is involved in, gripped or excited by it. Regarding the second criterion, among projects of worth we find moral and intellectual accomplishments and the ongoing activities that lead to them. The lives of Gandhi, Marie Curie, or Albert Einstein are typically given as examples of unquestionably meaningful lives (if there are any). This work argues that because of AGI's superior moral and intellectual capacities, AGI will be in a better position than humans to identify, develop and pursue worthwhile projects. Given that AGI will be vastly better at determining what projects of worth there are in the first place, vastly better at creating new worthwhile projects and vastly better than humans at pursuing such projects, humans will have fewer reasons and fewer opportunities to actively engage in projects of worth. With regard to the meaning of life, whatever cosmic end humanity might have (if any at all), AGI threatens this by threatening the very extinction of humanity.

When AI meets OSINT - Ethical considerations and Legal regulation of AI associated to OSINT

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Open Source Intelligence (OSINT) is already an old art and profession. Theoretically it refers to the collection and analysis of publicly available information— existing in social media posts, news articles, websites and blogs, government databases and records, academic and commercial publications, satellite imagery and geospatial data, but it can extend its search in more obscure data sources (1).

OSINT applications are practically available to anybody, and its ordinary usages can vary from simple curiosity of individuals to investigative activities of journalists and security experts, or surveillance efforts of governments. Normally its uses correspond to legitimate purposes, supporting decision- making mainly in political and governmental environments. It can be in the service of law enforcement investigating child abuses, trafficking and drug trafficking (2), terrorism threats, security threats in cyberspace or in the hands of organisations wanting to mitigate threats.

Of course this type of technology is open to illegal uses affecting the privacy of individuals, or acting in industrial or state espionage. It can even be used for malicious purposes, e.g. gathering information regarding potential victims of common crimes, cybercrimes, such as hacking, malware, and a denial-of- service attack. In fact, the same AI tools that assist legitimate OSINT can be exploited by ill-intentioned actors to spread propaganda or conduct disinformation campaigns. Obviously this part of OSINT is intentionally negligent of ethical obligations.

In the past, when technology was not mature enough, OSINT was labour intensive, but the activity followed the technological evolution to become technology intensive (3) overtime. Inevitably nowadays it starts exploiting AI techniques (4). This added capacity (5) upgraded traditional forms of intelligence exponentially and raises newborn concerns (6). AI has exponentially enhanced OSINT capabilities of handling and analysing massive datasets in order to extract, categorise and associate information down to the level of individuals (7).

Efforts to establish standards resulted to “The Berkeley Protocol on Digital Open Source Investigations” (89) which promotes ethical use of OSINT and identifies international standards for conducting online research of alleged violations of international criminal, human rights, and humanitarian law. It does not only consider the limits of invasive collection of data but also proposes measures that users of OSINT should take to protect their own safety.

At the EU level, already in 2013 EU research projects in the OSINT domain were financed (10), following which OSINT practitioners established a group under EU auspices and drafted the Guidelines for Public Interest OSINT Investigations (11).

OSINT poses several challenges (12) especially since it is normally practiced cross-border, involving several legal orders and jurisdictions and, beyond ethics, raises questions concerning the application of the legal framework where this exists. It raises questions about the potential impact on individuals’ privacy rights and personal lives. Even legitimate uses of OSINT can overflow in ethical violations. A major problem remains with the capacity of regulatory authorities to master and control how OSINT applications are put in the market or – being mostly open source – how users can remain in a legitimate framework. On top of that the technicality of the matter imposes an interdisciplinary approach, involving ethicists as well as lawyers and OSINT experts.

The complexities surrounding AI in OSINT underscore the importance of robust regulatory and ethical frameworks. There is actually no universal framework responding to “AI-driven OSINT” the latter calling for extended ethical considerations alongside traditional ethical principles. The presentation will attempt to place the OSINT phenomenon in the currently created ecosystem of the European Union comprising the GDPR, the AI act, Digital Services Act (DSA) and Digital Markets Act (DMA), and examine how OSINT applications and uses must conform to the legislative prescriptions of applicable European legislation. It will also consider how OSINT should offer guarantees for avoidance of algorithmic bias, explainability and accountability, on top of considering extended ethical standards for OSINT in the AI era.

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In the Eye of the Shitstorm: A Critical Phenomenology of Digital Conflict

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Once praised as a beacon for open exchange and the promise for a truly deliberative polity, the Internet, with its echo chambers, conspiracy theories, and uncivil communication practices, is now often considered a threat to the very foundations of liberal democracy. Online discourse seems helplessly polarized and abrasive—and political conflict in the digital world (subsequently 'digital conflict') insurmountable. Technology 'pessimists' in the phenomenological literature explain these shortfalls by the very nature of the virtual: disembodied digital spaces simply do not allow for meaningful encounters between persons (e.g., Dreyfus 2008; Fuchs 2014; Miller 2012). If meaningful engagement is precluded, so is resolving our quarrels. Other scholars hold that the body and other-understanding still reach into the digital world (e.g., Ekdahl & Ravn 2022; Hardesty & Sheredos 2019; Osler 2019, 2021; Osler & Krueger 2022), albeit potentially in a modified form. The work of such 'optimists' suggests that dysfunctional conflict is not inevitable. Yet, these authors focus on the harmonious aspects of online sociality or on ludic forms of competition (e.g., videogames).

How does political conflict, i.e., strife where matters of existential concern are at stake, complicate the picture? This paper presents initial findings of the three-year research project 'Virtual Battlefields: Political Conflict in Digital Spaces' currently running at the University of Hamburg. Based on qualitative data from interviews with politicians, activists, and journalists, it relies on an existential-phenomenological account of political conflict construed as a co-occurrence of different types of normative claims. The political agent is always first and foremost a political patient, called to adjudicate between different reasons coming their way.

How do digital places have to be structured, so that the different forms of normativity of the political world—i.e., me-reasons, thou-reasons, we-reasons, they-reasons—can come to the fore? Moreover, as an instance of critical phenomenology, the paper investigates how logics of power, so familiar to us from the analogue world, continue to affect interactions on Facebook, WhatsApp, or Zoom. How does the social location of the user with respect to their occupation, gender, or race impact their experience? Are these differences stable across digital platforms? If need be, can these platforms be changed to make digital conflict more constructive; or do we need to dismantle them altogether? This paper will give some first, tentative answers to these questions.

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Democracy and political implications of AI use. The New (Digital) Political Communication and Artificial Intelligence

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In the modern era, political communication has undergone a profound transformation due to the advent of new media and artificial intelligence (AI). The traditional methods of political messaging—such as television broadcasts, printed newspapers, and public speeches—have been supplemented and, in many cases, overtaken by the dynamic and algorithm-driven world of digital communication. AI plays a crucial role in shaping contemporary political discourse, influencing public opinion, and altering the strategies of political actors. However, these advancements come with significant ethical, democratic, and governance-related challenges that demand careful scrutiny. (Howard, 2020; Tufekci, 2017).

One of the most notable ways in which AI influences digital political communication is through personalized messaging. Political campaigns and governments use AI-driven data analytics to segment audiences based on their preferences, behaviors, and ideological leanings (Rigou, 2014, Bodó et al., 2021). This micro-targeting technique enables political actors to craft highly specific messages that resonate with different segments of the population. “Essentially, this marks the transition to a new form of political communication that, through the use of new tools, personalizes the political message, which is then remassified—either through social media, targeting communities of shared interests, or through the “online loudspeaker”. This remassification occurs only in terms of multiple recipients and not in terms of the mass nature of the content itself—content that, when addressed to a general audience, remains general in nature. This message retains its specificity [and alignment with individual political expectations] while framing the overarching message of the election campaign.” (Rigou, 2014)

While this approach can enhance engagement and mobilization (Acemoglu, Hasan, and Tahoun, 2014, Bennett, Breunig and Givens, 2008) it also raises concerns about political polarization (Bennett and Livingston 2018) and the creation of so-called “echo chambers” or “filter bubbles” where individuals are exposed only to viewpoints that reinforce their existing beliefs (Pariser, 2011). The erosion of a shared public sphere, in which citizens engage with diverse perspectives, poses a threat to democratic deliberation (Bennett & Livingston, 2020). As Lanier (2018) warns, the rise of algorithmic persuasion and behavioral modification through AI-driven platforms risks turning users into mere products of an extractive data economy, manipulated by unseen forces.

AI-driven social media algorithms further complicate the landscape of political communication. Platforms like Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), and YouTube employ sophisticated machine learning systems to maximize user engagement (Zuboff, 2019). These algorithms prioritize sensational, emotionally charged, and polarizing content, as such material tends to generate higher interaction rates (Cinelli et al., 2020). This dynamic can amplify misinformation, foster political extremism, and contribute to the spread of conspiracy theories (Bessi et al., 2016). Morozov (2011) argues that the utopian vision of the internet as a democratizing force often ignores its potential for authoritarian control and the manipulation of public opinion through AI-powered propaganda. The challenge for democracies is to balance the benefits of AI-enhanced communication with the need to prevent the manipulation of public opinion and the undermining of democratic institutions (Persily & Tucker, 2020).

Another crucial aspect of AI’s role in digital political communication is the use of chatbots and deepfake technologies. Political campaigns, advocacy groups, and even state actors deploy AI-powered chatbots to engage with citizens, answer queries, and promote specific political messages (Woolley & Howard, 2018). While these tools can enhance accessibility and responsiveness, they also risk misleading the public by simulating human interactions in ways that obscure their artificial nature. Deepfake technology, which enables the creation of highly realistic synthetic videos, poses an even greater threat, as it can be used to fabricate speeches, manipulate public figures’ appearances, and spread false narratives (Chesney & Citron, 2019). Lanier (2013) highlights how the increasing dependence on AI-generated content and digital automation can erode human agency, making it easier for powerful entities to control political narratives. The potential for AI-generated misinformation to influence elections and destabilize political systems necessitates robust regulatory frameworks (Helberger et al., 2020). Morozov (2013) warns against “solutionism”—the belief that AI and technology alone can fix complex societal problems—stressing that political and social structures must also evolve to ensure democratic resilience.

The Silicon Valley corporations, through their algorithms, have evolved into dominant mechanisms of power, as they control digital publicity and regulate collective expression, with obvious political, social, and cultural implications. The

“digital panopticon” that emerges in cyberspace, particularly on social media, monitors, restricts, and directs the public. Social media platforms and search engines, powered by AI-driven algorithms, have become the arbiters of all forms of speech, effectively diminishing its strength and displacing the democratic nature of the digital public sphere. An endless tug-of-war between freedom of expression and surveillance is unfolding in the public sphere. These are some of the aspects of the issue of new (digital) political communication, which relies on social media and artificial intelligence and raises significant challenges for democracy today. In my presentation, I intend to analyze these issues.

How can education systems be made AI-proof while ensuring ethical standards and promoting equality of opportunity?

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The quick rise of generative artificial intelligence is transforming the educational landscape. AI tools are increasingly being integrated into educational practices, bringing both opportunities and challenges in ethics and equality of opportunity. This abstract explores how educational institutions can become AI-proof, with a focus on ethical considerations and the promotion of equal opportunities. It highlights the necessity of a significant change from a performance-oriented to a learning-process-oriented approach and addresses the digital divide by AI innovations. Implementing these approaches requires transforming schools from factory-like structures to sites of collaborative learning, where evaluation practices foster student engagement, teacher development, and whole-school improvement (Gergen & Gill, 2020)

One of the key findings is the risk of cognitive dependency, where students outsource essential thinking skills to AI tools. While AI can increase accessibility, there is a danger that excessive use may lead to diminished problem-solving abilities and critical thinking skills. This phenomenon, known as cognitive offloading, can have harmful long-term effects on students’ intellectual development. Research indicates that excessive offloading may negatively impact long-term memory formation and working memory capacity (Grinschgl et al., 2021; Tarde & Joshi, 2023; Skulmowski, 2023).

Additionally, the integration of generative AI intensifies the digital divide, as not all students have equal access to AI technologies due to financial constraints and varying levels of digital literacy. Studies show that knowledge and use of AI tools like ChatGPT are unevenly distributed, with higher rates in urban, educated, and economically advantaged areas (Daepf & Counts, 2024; Ball & Huang, 2023). To address these challenges, there is a need for educational innovation that goes beyond mere technological implementation. Shifting the focus from end results to focusing on the learning process is crucial. Assessment should no longer serve solely as a conclusion to learning but as a tool to guide the learning process and promote individual development. This requires a culture of trust and dialogue between teachers and students

A fundamental aspect of AI-proof education is the enhancement of teachers’ knowledge and skills. Educators must be aware of the ethical implications and limitations of AI technologies to effectively guide their use (Sywelem & Mahklouf, 2024). Support and training for teachers are essential to balance the use of AI with the promotion of independent thinking skills among students. Furthermore, it is important to develop policy measures that ensure fair access to AI-supported learning resources. This includes not only removing financial barriers but also improving digital literacy and developing inclusive AI design practices.

In conclusion, the integration of generative AI in education presents both significant opportunities and challenges. To make education AI-proof, a holistic approach is required that upholds ethical standards and promotes equal opportunities. This entails a fundamental revision of educational practices, the strengthening of teachers’ roles, and the implementation of policies that reduce the digital divide. Interdisciplinary collaboration and comprehensive efforts across policy, regulation, and governance are crucial for creating an ethical AI framework in education (Barnes & Hutson, 2024; Mirea & Boboccea, 2024) Through a balanced and thoughtful approach, educational institutions can ensure that AI technologies contribute to a more just and inclusive educational landscape, where every student has the potential to perform optimally, regardless of their background or resources.

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Artificial Intelligence and Democracy: A Double-Edged Sword

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a key technology for the future. In current political debates, it is often viewed critically due to its deployment and the possibilities that this technology entails. Beyond the growing influence of large Big Tech companies from the USA on political discourse, the geopolitical impacts of key components such as know-how, chip manufacturing, and resources have long become significant decision-making factors in political discussions. Additionally, the extensive use of personal data and the opaque and non-transparent decision-making processes of AI are subject to criticism. Many AI models, particularly those based on deep neural networks, operate as “black boxes”, whose internal workings are difficult for users and regulatory authorities to comprehend. Furthermore, phenomena such as fake news, deepfakes, algorithmic biases, and the targeted manipulation of public opinion are viewed critically as new developments with far-reaching consequences. However, beyond these legitimate concerns, AI holds considerable potential for democratic structures. In particular, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), which play an important role in society, can potentially benefit from the use of AI. For example, welfare-oriented human rights and environmental protection organizations, as well as health and social service providers, can benefit from automated processes by utilizing resources more efficiently. At the same time, AI can enable citizen participation, projects that strengthen democracies, more targeted campaign planning, optimized resource utilization, and broader public engagement through digital participation formats and citizen science initiatives. There is currently little research addressing these questions: What are the needs of NGOs regarding new technologies? What resources are available, and which are still required? What is the level of acceptance, and what are the reasons for non-acceptance? Most importantly, how is AI being used in NGOs, what implementation possibilities do NGOs already have, and what potentials do they see in the use of AI? The project “XXX” investigated the needs, acceptance, and potential implementation possibilities of AI in NGOs in Germany. Initially, a scoping review was conducted to assess the current state of research. This was followed by a mixed-methods research design, consisting of initial exploratory interviews (n = 5, March 2024) to gain preliminary insights into the emerging research field. The initial findings were then expanded through a large-scale quantitative survey (n = 335, June 2024) among NGOs operating in Germany and subsequently supplemented by in-depth expert interviews (n = 10, October 2024). This approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the current situation and the publication of initial findings. The results indicate that while there is a fundamental interest in AI, financial, personnel, and technological barriers often hinder broader adoption. In addition to financial and staffing constraints, the development of technical infrastructure poses a challenge, especially for smaller organizations that lack sufficient IT capacities. These structural hurdles are accompanied by significant concerns regarding data protection, algorithmic biases, resource consumption, misinformation, and deepfakes, which are viewed critically. The NGOs are at different stages of AI adoption. The analysis also shows that organizations are in varying phases of AI deployment. While some are already conducting pilot projects and integrating initial applications into their workflows, other organizations are still in the early stages of engaging with the topic. The release of ChatGPT has often been a decisive factor for NGOs to adopt AI. In implementing AI into their processes, NGOs have encountered a wide range of problems and developed diverse solutions.

Network Value for Blockchain

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For Bitcoin to surpass the \$100,000 threshold, a theoretical framework is necessary to understand its price formation mechanism. Similar to the self-organizing behavior of ant colonies, the Bitcoin network operates autonomously. Since its emergence, Bitcoin (BTC) has rapidly evolved within the cryptocurrency market, offering both investment opportunities and risks. This study explores structural and governance transformations within the cryptocurrency ecosystem, specifically analyzing the transition from Proof-of-Work (PoW) to Proof-of-Stake (PoS) and Bitcoin's evolution from "digital gold" to "digital oil."

Based on blockchain technology, Bitcoin and other crypto-assets are examined from three primary perspectives in this study. First, we assess Bitcoin's role as the benchmark for cryptocurrencies, clarifying its unique position by comparing it with other digital assets. Second, we investigate how the blockchain network structure exhibits value amplification functions similar to Google's PageRank and Adam Smith's theory of sympathy, incorporating both technical and economic perspectives. Finally, we apply statistical power-law models to PoW-based networks to illustrate how Bitcoin's market behavior follows a long-tail distribution, dominated by a small number of influential participants.

● Network Characteristics

Information and communication models can be utilized to understand Bitcoin's network structure. For example, the relationship between Bitcoin and ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) investment is analyzed through network theory. Bitcoin's technical performance is not solely determined by transaction speed or security but is significantly influenced by network effects. The increasing number of users, miners, and transaction volume enhances Bitcoin's value through Metcalfe's Law, which states that the economic value and influence of a communication network are proportional to the square of the number of connected users. Furthermore, institutional investors have entered the network as participants, inserting financial assets into the system and thereby providing indicators of economic value. A comparative analysis of Bitcoin's growth trajectory with traditional companies like Amazon and Microsoft, in terms of financial networks, demonstrates that its exponential network effects align with Metcalfe's Law. Bitcoin reached a market valuation of \$1 trillion within 12 years, outpacing conventional GAFAM companies and expanding its decentralized scalability. While Bitcoin has technical limitations (e.g., transaction capacity), its success as a currency network is boundless. The rise in price from a few dollars to tens of thousands of dollars demonstrates that demand and recognition can surpass technical constraints, a phenomenon further reinforced by adoption in financial markets (ETFs and institutional investments).

● Network Dynamics and PageRank

Bitcoin's decentralized architecture shares similarities with Google's PageRank in its value-determination mechanism. While PageRank is managed through centralized information surveillance, blockchain networks like Bitcoin employ a decentralized consensus mechanism (solving the Byzantine Generals Problem). Applying Albert-László Barabási's Law of Success to Bitcoin suggests that, while its technical performance has limitations, its network effects exhibit infinite potential. ESG institutional investors have been funding self-organizing structures with boundless possibilities for self-replication.

● Statistical Models and Price Behavior

Bitcoin's price fluctuations exhibit power-law distribution characteristics, which explain rare yet significant "Black Swan" events and long-tail phenomena. This study applies this concept to Bitcoin's price formation. A logarithmic scale analysis of Bitcoin's price reveals a long-term correlation between price and time. Previous research has argued that capital inflows into financial assets contribute to price increases based on cointegration relationships. However, this study emphasizes the theoretically limitless expansion of network effects as proposed by Barabási. This perspective aligns with the Super-Generalized Central Limit Theorem (SGCLT), a concept used in earthquake prediction research. It provides a foundation for explaining Bitcoin's relationship with other cryptocurrency portfolios, Pareto distributions in ownership structures, and market bandwagon effects. By demonstrating the cointegration relationship between Bitcoin's price and time on a logarithmic scale, this study substantiates the aforementioned observations.

● Tokenization of Time and Economic Impact

Marx's labor value theory positions Bitcoin as a tokenized representation of time, akin to the historical advancements in energy efficiency from Babylonian oil lamps to modern LED lighting. Alongside altcoins like Ethereum and Polkadot, Bitcoin holds the potential to enhance economic efficiency, optimize energy consumption, and reduce transaction costs. By integrating blockchain-based financial mechanisms, Bitcoin's role extends beyond speculative investment to a fundamental element of the decentralized financial ecosystem within Web3.

As previously mentioned, the tokenization of time (a shift away from inefficiencies caused by reliance on a single fiat currency as an economic benchmark) could lead to a paradigm where value is no longer merely probabilistically forecasted through technologies like AI and Markov chains. Instead, it could lay the foundation for a transcendent framework of human prosperity beyond time.

Conceptual evolution in times of digital transformation and climate crisis: rethinking human autonomy

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In a political context where both digital technologies and the climate crisis frequently make the headlines, it is interesting to observe that digital ethics and environment ethics set partly conflicting normative constraints on our concepts of human selves, and specifically on the way we account for interdependence and relationality. The concept of human autonomy is arguably central to this tension.

Indeed, on the one hand, scholars in the ethics and design of digital technologies commonly call for different forms of human-centeredness, such as human-centered technologies (e.g. Schneiderman 2022), or human-in-the-loop ethical and design principles (e.g. Zanzotto 2019). In the context of digital technologies regulation, the protection of human autonomy is often stated in the various guidelines and regulatory frameworks as one of the main values to be protected. I believe this is primarily for two reasons. The first is the concern over humans keeping control over their actions as they interact with digital technologies. Indeed, the rapid and disruptive development of the capabilities of digital technologies has given rise to more or less realistic fears that humans might be left out of the loop of decisions that crucially matter to us or even lose control over the technologies that we have created, as well as related worries that digital technologies could favor manipulative practices (Susser et al 2019). The second reason to emphasize the autonomy of users, designers or provider of digital technologies is to avoid the harmful deflecting of responsibility onto the technology, through debatable attributions of agency to machines (e.g. Johnson 2004).

Conversely, the ecological sciences, the philosophy and ethics of environment or ecofeminism tend to emphasize the need to decenter from the human perspective and to understand humans as part of complex networks of many kinds of interdependent beings (e.g. Serres 1995). Scholars in these fields often call for a better accounting of our relationality, our dependence on other beings (Nurmi 2023). The work of Bruno Latour, spanning science and technology studies to philosophy of environment, has sought to account for this relationality, theorizing the embedding of humans within networks of human and non-human actors (Latour 2007, 2013). A relevant illustration of the tension I have described is that actor-network theory has been critiqued for putting too much emphasis on non-human agency, thereby hindering the epistemic and ethical analysis of socio-technical systems (e.g. Whittle and Spicer 2008).

Based on the observation of this tension, this article seeks to address the following question: considering that we need to confront both of these challenges simultaneously, how can we reconcile the aforementioned divergent expectations on human selves in a unified conceptualization of autonomy? A useful framework within which to answer this question is that of pragmatic conceptual ethics (Thomasson 2021). According to this metaphilosophical framework, concepts serve various functions that can be epistemic, but also instrumental, moral, political. This pragmatist approach to conceptual choice entails a philosophical and ethical negotiation around which purposes ought to be fulfilled by a given concept. I therefore discuss the functions that a concept of autonomy should fulfill in the context of this dual challenge.

Drawing from different strands of feminist moral philosophy, I argue that the concept of autonomy should crucially account for our relationality and the social nature of selves (Mackenzie and Stoljar, 2000), while at the same time maintaining the individual core of autonomy that enables it to fulfill its emancipatory purpose (Christman 2004, Khader 2020). I hence propose that working with a concept of autonomy as the ability to structure our dependences can help addressing the tension between digital and environment ethics, by recognizing our necessary dependence on others, broadly conceived, while at the same time emphasizing the importance of being able to act on these dependences. This conception does justice both to a characterization of human selves as fundamentally relational, and to the legitimate demand that a concept of autonomy serve the right claims for emancipation.

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Algorithms, Explanatory Epistemic Injustice, and the Black Box Tu Quoque

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Algorithmic decision systems (ADSs) are now used in a variety of sensitive contexts that traditionally involve human judgment and discretion. ADSs are often criticized as opaque: their workings are insufficiently understandable for some or all of those involved in their use.

A typical response is what may be called “black box tu quoque”: arguing we don’t understand processes underlying human judgments any better than we understand opaque ADSs (e.g. Zerilli et al. 20219). This point is valuable insofar as the opacity of the trial procedures against K. in Kafka’s *The Trial* is no less disturbing for the fact that it does not involve ADSs. I develop an account of the injustice that opacity (whether in human or algorithmic judgments) inflicts in terms of epistemic injustice (Fricker 2007) and push back against the black box tu quoque by arguing that two abiding problems, the alignment problem and automation bias, provide good reasons for viewing opacity in ADSs as especially problematic.

I identify explanatory epistemic injustice (EPI) as a type of epistemic injustice that occurs when the right to explanation (Verdenburgh (2021) is violated. EPI involves an authoritative judge who judges some individual as a person where this will significantly impact the individual’s vital interests, but without providing an adequate explanation (following elements of the accounts of Zerilli et al. (2018) and Verdenburgh (2021) in characterizing adequate explanation). Individuals so-judged have an interest not only in the vital interests affected by the judgment, but also in understanding the basis for the judgment—in receiving an explanation. As epistemic injustice, explanatory injustice involves affront to and gradual undermining of victims’ personhood qua knowers (Fricker 2007, chs. 2.3 & 7.3). It is thus particularly damaging and disenfranchising. So, in both human and ADS cases there is a strong obligation to provide explanations for judgments about persons that affect their vital interests. Further, opacity in the ADS case is more concerning than in otherwise equivalent human cases due to the alignment problem and automation bias.

Alignment is the problem of ensuring machine learning systems try to pursue the goals their designers want them to. Dung (2023) argues specific misalignments are difficult to predict, detect, and correct in many ADSs, but that the way such ADSs are trained makes some misalignment generally likely. By contrast, I argue human judgements are “the devil we know”: we have experience dealing with them in a wide variety of individuals and contexts and are familiar with their general alignments and constraints. The conjunction of opacity with the alignment problem in ADSs amplifies the need for explanation because it is more difficult to anticipate whether or how misalignment will occur.

Further, ADSs require greater explanation because of automation bias (AB): “the tendency to use automated cues as a heuristic replacement for vigilant information seeking and processing” (Mosier and Skitka 1996). AB suggests judgments made or assisted with ADS will tend to have increased default credibility. Such increased credibility makes challenging such judgments more difficult and should correspond to stronger explanatory requirements.

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Wisdom in the Age of Intelligent Wisdom, the Peculiar Knowledge of Humans, Gods and Machines

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"That which we are, we are. That is the wisdom of great age, the acceptance of our impermanence while drawing consolation from the memories of what we did and what, with luck, we might yet do. Also, perhaps, we can hope that our contribution will not be entirely forgotten as wisdom and understanding spread outwards from the Earth to embrace the cosmos"(James Lovelock, *Novacene: The Coming Age of Hyperintelligence*, London, Allen Lane, 2020, p. 130). Starting with a brief overall global view of wisdom, shared by gods and humans stretching through ancient times to the present from East to West incorporating sacred texts from Judaism, Hinduism, Buddhism, Taoism, Islam and other Indigenous religions and cultures including of course the ancient religion and myths of Rome and Greece, this paper's main focus is the examination and normative evaluation of the impact AI Technology has on our wellbeing now and potentially in the future.

To answer that question, the paper develops and applies a meta-normative model of wisdom whose primary purpose is to determine the essential conditions that any normative theory that seeks to assess the impact of technology on wellbeing must adequately address in order to be able to account for, explain and evaluate the capability of any technological product or process in its design and/or its use to contribute in some way, if any, to the good life for the wellbeing of individuals and society generally.

Using a theoretical normative tripartite model of Wisdom, the Dual Obligation Information Theory-Wisdom (DOIT-Wisdom) (Spence 2011, Dual Obligation Information Theory-Wisdom) that comprises three inter-related normative components, the epistemic, ethical and the eudaimonic, within an overarching conceptual framework, this paper examines the actual and potential impact of AI technology on wellbeing. For example, ICT and AI Technologies that do not protect the justified autonomy and privacy rights of its users or allow and do not restrict the indiscriminate dissemination of misinformation and disinformation, as well as the indiscriminate harvesting of user's information for the primary gain of Big Tech companies such as Facebook and Google, would have a low and negative capability for wellbeing. As such, it would potentially generate a negative epistemic, ethical and eudaimonic impact for its users and generally, a negative impact on society and the global community overall and therefore would not be wise to use such technologies.

Following from the question, what is technology good for and specifically AI technology, the overall aim of this paper is to address more specifically, the question of how the epistemology and ethics of information and communication technologies (ICTs), as well as the epistemology and ethics of AI technologies can be expanded to include more centrally the issue of its eudaimonic impact of technology on wellbeing for individuals, and society. To answer that question, the paper provides by way of a theoretical groundwork, the concept of wisdom understood as a type of meta-knowledge as well as a type of meta-virtue, which can enable us as individuals and collectively as a society, and humanity generally, to both know in principle what constitutes a good life, and how to successfully apply that knowledge as know-how in living such a life in practice, for the ultimate purpose of attaining wellbeing or eudaimonia. This answer will be based on the main argument presented in this paper that the notion of wisdom understood as a triadic concept, at once a meta-epistemological, meta-ethical and meta-eudemonic, provides the essential conceptual link between information on the one hand and wellbeing on the other. In the Digital Age of Information, both the theoretical examination and analysis of the question of how information in its technological construction and dissemination, relates to wellbeing, as well as the provision of an adequate answer to that question, are essential for developing a deeper understanding of how to evaluate the theoretical and practical implications and impact of digital information on wellbeing for individuals and societies.

In sum, the paper will seek to show that although related, wisdom is conceptually distinct and conceptually different from both information, intelligence, and knowledge in a crucial way. For wisdom unlike information and first-order knowledge provides a person with understanding concerning the *techne viou* or craftsmanship of living in the sense of knowing how to evaluate and apply relevant information or knowledge for living a good life for the attainment of eudaimonia, and in addition, an appreciation in knowing why such a life constitutes a good life.

A central and important aspect of this paper is to examine if Intelligent AI Machines, such as ChatGPT and Gemini, among others, can be wise and if not, why not? Can there be a Hybrid Notion of Wisdom that combines a human notion of wisdom with that of an AI Digital notion of Wisdom?

LLMs, Autonomy, and Narrative

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Suppose Jane talks about Joe to several of her friends, to strangers, indeed, to whomever she meets. While this issue has been phrased in terms of privacy rights violation, we sidestep that discussion and focus on how Jane might affect Joe's ability to define his own persona, his personal identity, the narrative about his person. However, we are not focused on people talking about other people, but on how technology shapes these narratives.

Our focus here is on large language models (LLMs), which have raised a plethora of ethical discussions (e.g., authorship, copyright). Here we instead focus on an issue that has garnered less—if any—attention in the literature: How LLMs shape our personal narratives.

In our talk we aim to explain two main things. First, we aim to explain how LLMs might diminish an individual's control over their self-narrative and how that reduced control, in turn, affects their ability to shape their own narrative, and thus identity (see Titz 24). The result is a potential diminishment of their autonomy. Here we will also argue (contra Marmor 2015) that people's interest in having reasonable control over self-presentation is an autonomy rather than privacy rights issue (see Lundgren 2020; b; Munch 2020).

We aim to show that LLMs diminishing control over self-narratives has to do with their presenting content by making use of a distinct narrative framing. Second, we will argue that this might be one specification of a more general loss of control over narratives. The production of narratives is changing from a human to a computational activity.

Thereby, AI systems are reducing our human control (i.e., our collective autonomy) over the production of narratives. Story-telling is an integral part of human social binding and cultural productions, and it is expectable that LLMs negatively impact on its quality.

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"It's not actual sexual violence – or is it?". Non-consensual and Deepfake Pornography and the Ambivalent Moral Impact of the 'Unreality Aura'.

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The circulation of non-consensual pornographic material is a pernicious issue in the digital era (Henry et al., 2021). Recently, this issue has been exacerbated by the rise of deepfake pornography: AI-generated intimate videos or images that are nearly indistinguishable from authentic content and depict sexual acts that never occurred. Victims of deepfake pornography often experience severe harm, comparable to those affected by non-consensual pornography involving authentic content (Flynn et al., 2022).

This talk addresses the following question: is there a meaningful moral difference between non-consensual materials presented as authentic versus those explicitly fabricated? This question is deeply intertwined with the perceived veracity of digital non-consensual pornography and its potential effects. On one side, Viola and Voto (2023) argue that the primary motivation behind the creation and distribution of non-consensual pornography lies in its perceived authenticity. Such content aims not merely to provide sexual material but to violate the depicted person's privacy and intimacy. If content is believed to be fabricated, it may cause less harm. As Scarlett Johansson, a frequent target of pornographic deepfakes, stated in an oft-cited interview: "Clearly this doesn't affect me as much because people assume it's not actually me in a porno, however demeaning it is." Viola and Voto predict that the proliferation of deepfakes may erode the credibility of all pornographic content, thereby undermining the motivation for producing non-consensual pornography and reducing its harm. They suggest that the 'unreality aura' could be leveraged as a tool to combat non-consensual pornography or mitigate its effects. However, they also note the risk of extreme measures, such as perpetrators resorting to independent verification of victims' identities—e.g., doxing—to restore credibility to the content.

Conversely, Striano (2024) highlights a danger inherent in the 'unreality aura.' He observes that "violent behavior deemed unacceptable offline seems to be more tolerated, or at least more frequent, online" (p. 77). This tolerance, he argues, stems from the assumption that digital abuses are less 'real.' Such an ontological bias unjustly diminishes the perceived moral gravity of digital offenses, despite their very real and damaging consequences (Flynn et al., 2022). As a result, the feeling of unreality might actually hinder efforts to combat non-consensual pornography. Striano's perspective may also help explain why legal frameworks addressing non-consensual pornography, particularly deepfake content, are lagging behind (Mania, 2024).

I propose that non-consensual pornography—whether authentic or fabricated—should be unequivocally recognized, both legally and culturally, as a morally culpable act in itself, irrespective of its claim to authenticity. The moral philosophy surrounding deepfakes already establishes that deepfake pornography is harmful and blameworthy regardless of whether it is perceived as real or fake. This is due to various factors, including its role in promoting unwanted associations between individuals or groups (e.g., women) and sexual acts (Harris, 2021), violating the right to self-determined representation (De Ruiter, 2021), and reinforcing the objectification of women (Rini and Cohen, 2022). Nevertheless, presenting intimate content as authentic should be regarded as an aggravating factor, as it has the potential to inflict additional harm on victims.

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Reconciling Clinical Research with AI Fairness Requirements: a Methodological Challenge in AI based Healthcare research

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The implementation of AI fairness requirements in high-risk medical applications reveals a tension between regulatory mandates and established clinical research practices. While frameworks like the EU AI Act and ongoing harmonised standards (e.g., CEN/CLC TR 18115:2024) demand representativeness of training data as a requirement for data quality and fairness across social groups in healthcare AI based systems, traditional clinical study design often restrict population heterogeneity (e.g. through strict inclusion criteria), or implicitly flatten social differences by considering the study population as a homogeneous group. Both approaches aim to maximize statistical power and internal validity, but they do so at the cost of obscuring potentially significant social, cultural, and demographic variations in health outcomes. Such methodological choices, while statistically sound within the paradigm of clinical research, inevitably create a fundamental tension with AI fairness requirements that mandate representative data in order to avoid discrimination across social groups.

This tension uncovers bias in biomedical research as a multifaceted issue, potentially affecting the validity and generalisability of findings. Researchers and ethicists agree on the fact that a concerted effort to standardise methodologies, enhance diversity, and promote ethical practices will generate more reliable and inclusive evidence leading to an improvement of healthcare and prevention globally, however there is no consensus on the best practices to addressing these biases. Such tensions pose fundamental methodological challenges not only for AI research and development but for clinical research.

Based on the ongoing work within COMFORTage project (1), an EU-funded Research and Innovation initiative on AI-based dementia risk prediction, this paper examines a case in which the abovementioned tension manifests in practice and why purely technical solutions prove insufficient.

Dementia research presents a particularly compelling case for examining these dynamics. Current scholarship suggests complex interactions between biological, social, and cultural factors in dementia risk and progression. Current literature within the field, indicate differential incidence patterns across different sexes and social conditions, including more elevated risks among migrants in Europe compared to the same ethnic groups in their home countries. However, understanding these variations remains limited due to historical underrepresentation in clinical studies and insufficient attention to socio-cultural dimensions. The challenge seems circular: understanding group differentiated incidence requires diverse data, but effectively collecting such data requires prior knowledge of these differences to inform study design.

Drawing on Science and Technology Studies perspectives, this paper analyses how the understanding of algorithmic bias within COMFORTage project evolved from a purely technical consideration to a more complex socio-technical challenge. Initially viewed as a matter of technical compliance with AI ethics requirements, team discussions revealed deeper questions about knowledge production, power dynamics in interdisciplinary research and how big data analytics reposes problematisations of how segregating human beings in discrete groups or classes. This evolution highlighted how decisions about what constitutes 'representative' data are not merely technical choices but reflect broader questions about whose knowledge and experiences are valued in medical research.

This paper argues that addressing algorithmic bias in dementia research requires engaging with fundamental questions about knowledge production in biomedicine. The interdisciplinary research environment of COMFORTage proved crucial in surfacing these issues, demonstrating how AI development can serve as a catalyst for examining and challenging established research practices. By framing algorithmic bias as a socio-technical challenge rather than merely a technical problem, we can better understand and explore the tensions between research feasibility, clinical validity, and algorithmic fairness. This approach enables the exploration of more inclusive methodologies while maintaining scientific rigor, contributing to broader discussions about responsible AI innovation in healthcare.

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Artificial Intelligence, Bias and Practical Philosophy

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This paper looks at the nature of informing systems as sociotechnical systems that are intended to support people in their efforts to self-inform or help others to inform themselves.

It discusses informing as a process dependent in no small part upon possibilities to communicate between individuals. Theories relating to communication are considered and difficulties that may arise leading to problems of misinforming. Types and forms of bias are considered, and how they may be inherent or even necessary in informing systems. The special cases of Artificial Intelligence and Generative Artificial Intelligence are considered in relation to the incidence of bias. It is suggested that attempts at objectivity are unlikely to become successful, and that ways should instead be found to surface and recognize different sources of bias within individuals' experiences of informing. Approaches to inquiry into informing systems are considered, paying attention to the works of different researchers who have contributed to debate on interpretive and critical strands. Critical systemic approaches to inquiry as exercises in practical philosophy are highlighted.

Implicit Ideology in Emotion Detection Technology

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When discussing concerns about emotion detection technology (EDT) one question comes up frequently: Isn't emotion detection technology helpful for autistic people to teach them emotion recognition? In my talk I will address this very question and use this application example to illustrate my thesis that EDT contains implicit ideology. EDT is originally and still commonly designed and implemented using facial analysis for emotion recognition on basis of the concept of basic emotions (Weber-Guskar, 2023; Weigel, 2020; Ekman, 1999; Picard 1997; Ekman, 1992; Ekman and Friesen, 1978). EDT is, for example, applied in Education and Health Care (Misselhorn, 2021; Hernandez et al., 2021), including autism therapy (Kouo and Egel, 2016; Baron-Cohen et al., 2001) — e.g., the Reading the Mind in the Eyes test (Engelbrecht, 2022; Baron-Cohen et al., 2001) or the humanoid robot NAO (Ham, 2018). Yet, the technology reproduces a historically normative narrative of the prevailing Western theoretical understanding of emotion expression and recognition (Canal et al., 2022; Hernandez et al., 2021; Weigel, 2020; Barrett et al., 2019; Bollmer, 2019; Nussbaum, 1995; Jaggar, 1989). To fully understand the resulting consequences for EDT in autism therapy, one must uncover what norms are implied.

In my talk, I start with an introduction to examples of EDT in autism therapy (Engelbrecht, 2022; Baron-Cohen et al., 2001, Ham, 2018). Next, I will roughly outline EDT's historical development (Canal et al., 2022; Hernandez et al., 2021; Picard 1997), including the influence of experimental psychology (Ekman and Friesen, 1978), which in turn is informed by contributions in philosophy of emotion in coining facial analysis as method for (computational) emotion recognition (Bollmer, 2019; Descartes, 2014; Aristotle, 2002; James, 1884). My aim is to show that related claims of universality of emotion expressions result from a value-driven narrative. By drawing from the critique of the value-free ideal in science (Intemann, 2020), I will further argue that this narrative is promoted to be objective in terms of being value-free while actually striving to reach e.g., the ideal of neurotypicality. Finally, I will discuss the extent to which utilising EDT in autism therapy may be helpful or harmful.

My argument will be that, partly because of the widespread acceptance of normative standards in human emotion recognition, autistic people often need support to learn meeting the normative standards to be able to navigate in social interaction. Yet, that this education does not translate well to real-life contexts (Barrett et al. 2019; Berggren et al., 2018; Kouo and Egel, 2016). I will show that this approach assumes autistic people to be deficient rather than having a way of communicating which deviates from the neurotypical norm (Wharmby 2022). As a result, such approaches promote autistic masking which in turn can have serious health consequences (Evans et al., 2024; Wharmby 2022; Shkedy et al., 2021). Ultimately, my thesis is that autism therapy utilising EDT can be a practice of striving for the neurotypical ideal that perpetuates and promotes ableist assumptions about autistic people which at the same time hinders learning about autistic communication. Yet, I will leave with an application example, namely the Triple-A training tool that was first launched in March 2022 (Durham University, n.d.), that shows that this does not have to be the case, and that the very same EDT (in this case eye-tracking technology) can be rethought and utilised in different ways to even promote education about neurodiversity.

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Digital Civil Disobedience and the Question of Anonymity

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In democratic theories, the public sphere helps maintain four functions of modern democracies: An aggregation function, a control function, a translation function, and a social integration function. While the digitization of the public sphere as often been seen as a remedy to overcome some of the difficulties of traditional public spheres, such as polarization, fragmentation, and communicative asymmetries, it is questionable whether a digital public sphere can

actually ameliorate some of these shortcomings. This is especially dubious as it becomes increasingly apparent that the digitization of the public sphere creates its own polarizations, fragmentations, and power asymmetries. In this talk, I will argue that acts of digital civil disobedience (DCD) as illegal, entirely web-based forms of protest (e.g. DDoS actions, website defacement, leaking, doxing etc.) can make essential contributions to the control as well as translation function of digital publics. Therefore, DCD can be a legitimate – albeit illegal – form of political contestation online, as long as it meets certain formal conditions. In order to de-criminalize and legitimize some of these forms, I will employ Rawls' four central criteria for civil disobedience (publicity, nonviolence, political aim, illegality within fidelity to law) and assess, whether and to what extent different types of online protest meet these criteria. Specifically, the anonymity of the actors behind a variety of political contestations online pose a serious threat to the fidelity-to-law condition, as it becomes unclear whether the action in question is really aimed at “addressing the sense of justice of the majority” (Rawls) and whether its proponents in general deem the political order as legitimate. Rather than exposing themselves to the public and thereby giving the authorities the opportunity to arrest them for their illegal actions, they typically try to remain anonymous and avoid arrest and trial. This casts doubt on their fidelity to law, i.e. their general adherence to the legal order. As a result, the civility of their protest as a whole is in dispute. In what follows, I will call this position – i.e. that protesters have to accept the legal consequences, in order to commit acts of civil disobedience – the Acceptance-of-Legal-Consequences-Condition. Other authors tackling this question typically widen the “civility”-condition of civil disobedience to accommodate forms of digital illegal activism and protest, or even abandon this condition altogether. In contrast, in this talk I argue that the ALCC is not mandatory to demonstrate fidelity to law, and therefore not a necessary condition for the categorization of a form of protest as “civil disobedience”. By sticking with the Rawlsian liberal definition of civil disobedience and its fairly narrow notion of civility, my account has two advantages: First, it can garner a broader acceptance for the forms of illegal digital activism that can still be categorized as civil disobedience under this narrower notion. Such a notion is more likely to be in line with a fundamental agreement about civil disobedience across the political spectrum. Especially among actors within the legal system (law enforcement officers, criminal prosecutors, judges), this notion is more commonly accepted, as it will presumably have been part of their legal education. Second, the forms of digital illegal protest thus categorized will probably also be captured by broader definitions of civil disobedience, as the liberal notion typically is a proper subset of these. In addressing these questions, I will argue for a recognition of some forms of digital political contestation as DCD. Legitimizing these forms should result in penalizing them instead of punishing them, as they serve important purposes for transnational digital spheres. Decriminalizing online protest as DCD without legalizing it is therefore an important aspect of strengthening transnational digital publics.

AI and Cultural Heritage: Sustaining Rural Identity Beyond Commodification

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Artificial intelligence (AI) can potentially revolutionize the preservation of rural communities' intangible cultural heritage (ICH). From folk music to dialects, it can effectively solve problems caused by urban migration, globalization, and the slow erosion of regional customs. However, such potentials pose pressing ethical questions, such as maintaining authenticity, preventing the commodification of heritage, and respecting community agents.

This article discusses how AI can ethically preserve and promote rural cultural heritage without erasing the community's living relationship to that heritage and reducing it to disembodied commercialized artifacts. It addresses key issues: How could AI help protect and preserve rural ICH without losing its authenticity? What are the dangers of AI-generated cultural representation? More importantly, how might rural communities have a rich opportunity to intentionally craft their uses of AI applications for cultural conservation rather than simply being consumable by those who own the large tech culture factory?

Applications and Case Studies

Preserving Traditional Music and Language With natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning, AI technologies are transforming how we document and archive traditional songs and regional dialects. These tools offer a lifeline for endangered cultural expressions but risk oversimplifying or misrepresenting them without local expertise. For instance, biases from AI training data could skew linguistic subtleties that may not align with cultural contexts. Moreover, the use of AI in cultural representation has resulted in the homogenization of diverse cultural expressions, potentially herding unique aspects of rural heritage (Hellwig et al., 2020).

Enhancing Tourism with Virtual Reality (VR) and Interactive Storytelling Platforms

Virtual tourism using AI technology uniquely brings rural festivals, landmarks, and cultural activities to life. While such initiatives have the potential to draw tourists from around the globe, there are concerns that such traditions may lose their original meaning and turn into commodities. This is because such applications can reach a wide number of people (Rodríguez-González et al., 2021). AI systems inherit biases from the data they are trained on, so they can alter rural stories to appeal to a modern audience. However, the affordability of machine learning often comes at the cost of

cultural distortion. With the help of varied documentation that explains how AI technologies employ cultural data, the chances of misrepresentation can be substantially less, thereby saving trust in preserving heritage (Chang & Rosenthal, 2019).

Ethical Considerations

- Risks of Commodification Cultural heritage risks losing value when turned into digital assets for financial gain. Market-driven strategies frequently reduce cultural expressions to commodities by emphasizing appeal over authenticity (Smith, 2006).
- Community Agency and Ownership Involving rural communities at every stage of the process is essential for the ethical deployment of AI, as there is a greater chance of cultural exploitation and misrepresentation without participatory design (Díaz-Andreu, 2017).

Proposed Solutions

- Engaging Communities in Design Collaborative efforts with local communities focus on ensuring that preservation measures align with their principles as actively involving community members and purposefully including them in decision-making processes, from AI application development to cultural data collection and use, could foster trust and a sense of community ownership (Binns, 2018).
- Developing Transparent AI Models Transparent and precise documentation of how AI models analyse cultural material may decrease the dangers of misrepresentation while maintaining the authenticity of the conserved legacy, creating trust in the preservation process (Doshi-Velez & Kim, 2017).
- Creating Ethical Guidelines Comprehensive ethical standards guidelines should emphasize authenticity, respect for community agency, and equitable representation to balance cultural preservation and business interests (Floridi & Taddeo, 2016).

Conclusion

AI provides groundbreaking technologies for preserving rural communities' intangible cultural and cultural integrity so that they can be put into practice and implemented. By fostering multidisciplinary modification among technologists, ethicists, and rural stakeholders, AI can become a powerful ally in the protection of cultural identities without modifying them.

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